

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Proof of concept

Authors: Jacob Torfing (RUC), Eva Sørensen (RUC), and Rasmus Øjvind Nielsen (RUC).
Delivery date: 30/06/2023

Project acronym	ROBUST
Project title	Robust Crisis Governance in Turbulent Times – Mindset, Evidence, Strategies
Work package	WP2 – Defining robust crisis governance
Task	T2.1, T2.2, and T2.3
Deliverable number	D2.1(D5) – Proof of concept
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Due date	31/05/2023
Lead partner	Roskilde University (RUC)

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program
under grant agreement no. 101061272

Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Turbulence as the new normal	3
1.2	Turbulence as a growing problem for public governance	5
1.3	Robust governance in response to heightened turbulence	7
1.4	Robustness as an alternative to resilience and agility	9
1.5	The methods applied in making this report	10
1.6	The structure of the report	11
2	Turbulence	12
2.1	From simple and wicked problems to turbulent problems	12
2.2	Interdisciplinary literature review of turbulence	14
2.3	Generic definition of turbulence and societal turbulence	20
2.4	Operational definition of societal turbulence	21
2.5	Turbulence and crisis	21
2.6	Turbulence as a challenge to governance	23
2.7	How to analyze turbulence?	25
3	Robust governance	29
3.1	Robust governance as a response to turbulence beyond agility and resilience	29
3.2	Interdisciplinary literature review of robustness	32
3.3	Generic and operational definitions of robust governance, democracy, and legality	37
3.4	Robustness strategies	39
4	Proof of concept	53
4.1	Analyzing three recent societal crises through the lens of turbulence and robustness	53
4.2	Lessons learned from literature studies	62
4.3	Interaction with practitioners	64
4.4	Practitioners' responses	65
4.5	Lessons learned from our engagement with practitioners	66
5	Conclusion: summarizing key findings	67

1 Introduction

The EU financed research project ROBUST aims to address the fact that poly-crises and heightened turbulence seem to have become the new normal. For decades crises and rising turbulence were relative rare, occasional, and short-lived together with expert-driven crisis management that quickly restored normalcy. Now we are facing a new predicament where crises are increasingly frequent, multiple, overlapping, and mutually reinforcing and seem to trigger unpredictable dynamics 'where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways' (Ansell & Trondal, 2017). The ROBUST project claims that we are living in times of heightened *turbulence* that calls for *robust governance* that allows to maintain some degree of *stability* in the fundamental values, goals, and functions of public governance while *changing* the modus operandi of the public sector by means of adaptation and innovation that might open up new possibility and bring us to a new and better place. As such, the ROBUST project builds on the assumption that the choice for public leaders and governors is not between stability and change, but between different combinations of stability and change that mutually support each other (Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2023).

The overall purpose of WP2 is to construct theoretical and operational definitions of the key concepts of turbulence and robustness. WP2 lays the conceptual foundation for the ROBUST project by providing generic definitions of turbulence and robustness based on interdisciplinary literature reviews and theoretical and operational definitions of crisis-induced turbulence and robust governance, democracy, and legality. WP2 also aims to provide proof of concept through secondary empirical research and stakeholder engagement and to develop initial diagnostic tools for decisionmakers aiming to respond robustly to turbulence.

This WP2 report provides generic, theoretical, and operational definitions of turbulence and robustness and delivers proof of concept through empirical applications of the concepts and discussions with relevant stakeholders (D2.1). A subsequent WP2 report will discuss how to diagnose societal turbulence, present a broad repertoire of robustness strategies supported by a robust mindset, and finally reflect on the choice and evaluation of robustness strategies (D2.2.)

1.1 Turbulence as the new normal

Human life on the planet earth has always been turbulent and full of perils and risks, including personal injury, famine, natural and man-made catastrophes, the spread of infectious diseases, economic depression, social and political unrest, violent clan struggles and devastating wars. Political philosophers from Aristotle and Plato, through Hobbes and Locke, to Hegel and Marx have spent much time pondering whether and how a stable social order is at all possible. In

modern times, we have tried to predict, forecast, and prepare for the inevitable spells of turbulence inherent in social life. We have built systems for national security and economic regulation together with elaborate welfare systems that socialize the individual risks of poor health, occupational hazards, unemployment, and old age. While these systems offer safety and comfort to the members of society, they are prone to failure and seem to generate new risks, either because the societal conditions for their functioning change or because the various systems interact in complex and unforeseen ways, giving rise to externalities and occasional breakdowns (Beck, 1992).

In the new age of globalization, digital communication and accelerated technological innovation, the speed of societal transformation and the interpenetration of socioeconomic systems have increased, and the world has shrunk to a global village. These trends stimulate the production and experience of turbulence defined as the complex interaction between unpredictable, partly unknown, and constantly mutating problems, demands and events with inconsistent and ambiguous effects (Ansell & Trondal, 2018). Without denying the presence of a heightened turbulence in the past (e.g., in the run-up to World Wars I and II), turbulent events, demands and developments seem to be lining up in a hitherto unprecedented manner. Turbulence, we will argue, has become the new normal.

There are multiple sources of societal turbulence, including government failures to address pressing problems properly and the implementation of ill-conceived solutions, both possibly provoking social protests, political conflicts, and economic problems that are difficult to resolve. Political scandals may trigger media storms, intensified political struggles, and government crises that lead to new elections, unpredictable political negotiations, and enhanced volatility. International conflicts and war sometimes prompt sanctions that challenge established supply chains, resulting in inflation, shortages, social unrest, and political disputes. Economic crises caused by a massive public debt combined with lost tax revenues resulting from tax evasion may give rise to austerity measures that create social problems, catalyze the formation of protest parties, and transform the structure of the national economy and its relations to international financial organizations. Demographic changes, changing values, and new family structures may gradually undermine the eldercare system and create labor-market problems, which in turn give rise to demands for change, political disputes, and new migration patterns. Indeed, these and many other disruptive events demonstrate how public governance rarely operates in calm waters, often facing rough seas – and sometimes even a tsunami of unpredictable social, political, and economic dynamics that challenge the ambitions and effectiveness of governance.

Public governors rarely acknowledge this challenging turbulence explicitly; instead, they assume it to be business as usual. They can carry on with their standard procedures for formulating and achieving public goals, calculating the costs and benefits of different solutions, improving

administrative structures and procedures, monitor regulations, and deliver services in accordance with traditional Weberian values of fairness, transparency, and predictability. While the odd extraordinary crisis situation calls for a particular type of crisis management, many government officials assume that the crisis will blow over and allow them to return to business as usual.

Today, however, this tendency to neglect the pervasiveness of turbulence is becoming increasingly difficult to maintain. The basic level of societal turbulence has increased due to a combination of intensified globalization, structural transformations of the international order, the spread of new technologies and communication systems, the emergence of new lines of social and political conflict, etc. Moreover, the level of turbulence is constantly heightened by a growing frequency of economic, political, social, and environmental crises that overlap and co-exist and are only partially resolved, if at all. In effect, governments around the world are continuously struggling to make sense of and deal with all kinds of interrelated crises, chaos, and turmoil that come and go in unpredictable ways. This development seems to produce a new and growing sense that turbulence is a chronic and endemic condition for modern governance. The COVID-19 pandemic has magnified the importance of building governance capacity to deal with turbulence. Experts may have warned us that a pandemic was imminent, but it was still unexpected when it hit and spread surprisingly quickly. The impact of the new virus in different countries and on different population groups varied, changing over time with new mutating variants. All parts of society were negatively affected by the attempts to contain and fight the virus through lockdowns and extensive health regulations. The government response strategies around the globe varied in timing, scope, content, and impact, which created a series of social and economic problems that generated demands for compensation. The development, purchase and administration of vaccines added yet another tumultuous chapter to the unfolding story of governance responses to turbulence. Perhaps more than anything else, COVID-19 pandemic convinced government officials that turbulence is less exceptional and more the new normal – and that something must be done to tackle unpredictable societal dynamics.

1.2 Turbulence as a growing problem for public governance

The rise of turbulence is a growing problem for public governance (Boyne & Meier, 2009; Ansell & Trondal, 2018). Governance is basically about formulating and achieving common goals (Torfing et al., 2012), and the public demands for and political ambitions of public governance have drastically increased in recent decades. One driver of these increasing public demands is that the frequent and overlaying crises create social and economic hardships calling for government intervention. Moreover, the rapid pace of technological and societal development creates new needs that are translated into new demands. Another driver of is the digitalization of information flows, which bring to light new problems and potential solutions at breathtaking

speed that were previously unknown or ignored by citizens, organized stakeholders, and policy experts but are now generating demands for action (Aksin-Sivrikaya & Bhattacharya, 2017). A final driver is the rise of new social media which provides low-threshold opportunities for citizens and organized interests to set the agenda and voice their demands. In many countries, such opportunities are exploited by a growing number of competent, assertive, and critical citizens (Dalton & Welzel, 2014; Esser & Strömbäck, 2014). Equipped with new knowledge and new communication channels, politically self-confident citizens are keen to demand tailor-made, high-quality public services that increase their quality of life; and when their life is negatively impacted by crises, they use all available means to cry for help, thus expecting government to find new governance solutions.

The pressure on public governance does not only come from the citizens and their rising demands in the face of socioeconomic crisis, the ambitions of elected politicians and public managers have also increased. Health care is no longer merely about curing illnesses, but about preventing disease from occurring through health promotion. Employment policy is no longer merely about securing the livelihood of those who become unemployed, but about training and educating these people to get them back into paid employment. Education policy is no longer about providing people with the right skills prior to their entry into the labor market, but a life-long education effort. Economic policy is no longer only focused on stabilizing markets, seeking also to enhance the structural competitiveness of national and regional economies. And the list goes on. The growing demands and ambitions of public governors seem ever more difficult to meet due to the fiscal problems currently facing the public sector. Public governors want to deliver new and better policy, regulation, and services, but the conditions for doing so are deteriorating. Many public leaders are increasingly busy putting out small and large fires and trimming the public sector to make ends meet, and the formulation and implementation of new public policies is constantly jeopardized by the unpredictable dynamism of politics, society, and the global economy.

Public governance must deal with an increasing number of turbulent events and developments that tend to interact and multiply, thus producing ever more turbulence. This snowballing effect is clearly visible in the wake of the Russian invasion in Ukraine, which has triggered a refugee crisis, an energy crisis, an inflation crisis, and a security crisis, all within a very short time span. The public sector is ill-equipped to deal with a heightened amount of turbulence. Public governors can no longer avail themselves of the classical risk strategies of prevention, foresight, and insurance. These strategies are unable to deal effectively with the unpredictable emergence of complex and partly unknown problems that are constantly changing and have inconsistent effects. Hence, an alternative strategy is required.

1.3 Robust governance in response to heightened turbulence

Public governors must learn to respond robustly to the rise of societal turbulence. Instead of merely trying to make the turbulent crisis situation go away or launching drastic response strategies that compromise important public ideals and objectives, public governors should carefully observe how turbulent events, demands and developments challenge core functions, goals, and values to then flexibly adapt and proactively innovate the modus operandi of the public sector in order to continue to deliver on its key ambitions, although in new ways that may or may not open up for new possibilities. In short, robust governance aims to maintain some basic functional stability by changing the forms of public governance. Or to put it differently, public governors may benefit from developing and adopting a strategy of 'dynamic conservatism' that change in order to preserve (Ansell, Boin & Farjoun, 2015).

Examples of robust governance can be detected in the suddenly emerging governance responses to the COVID-19 pandemic, which followed an unpredictable trajectory. The pandemic cost many lives, led to social and economic ruin for many, and it disrupted the normal functioning of the public sector. Many public organizations were forced to operate in a highly turbulent environment with recurrent lockdowns, new and constantly changing health regulations, and increasing demands from citizens who were hit by the health crisis. To illustrate what we mean by robust governance, let us briefly consider some of the strategies pursued by local public employees, regional middle managers and national policy makers. We shall present the strategies for robust governance as illustrative vignettes, which are based on real-life experiences.

At the local level, John and his colleagues at the local job center faced the challenge that the lockdown and health regulations prevented them from holding meetings with unemployed job-seekers to help them find work. To uphold the law and conduct the mandatory interviews, the job center workers were forced to adjust their standard practices. They came up with a new and innovative solution: walk-and-talks with the unemployed in a nearby park. They found that walking together while enjoying the greenery produced good and constructive conversations that unearthed the job seekers' dreams and wishes as well as their need for new competences. This new practice enabled the job center employees to provide helpful advice and training offers that facilitated the return of many of their clients to the labor market. Hence, flexible adaptation and proactive innovation of public services helped to maintain a key function in a public sector facing turbulence. While the new employment-interview format was not suspended after the pandemic, but important lessons were drawn that changed the interactive dynamics between the job seekers and job center personnel.

The pandemic also posed an obstacle to Charlotte and her team in the local child protection office, which works with at-risk children and youth who have been removed from their troubled

homes and placed with a foster family. Their job is partly to organize regular face-to-face meetings between the children, the foster care families, the biological parents, and the municipality, but the Corona restrictions prevented physical meetings. Fortunately, Charlotte's team quickly switched to online meetings, which were easy to organize, could be called by the kids themselves, and could include a wider set of actors (e.g., an uncle or an older sibling living in another town). The online meetings facilitated the mandated interaction, while also improving its frequency and quality. The experiences were so positive that the new format survived as a supplement to face-to-face meetings in the post-pandemic period.

Jane, the chief regional health services manager, trembled in the face of the growing number of Corona patients, the demands for testing and vaccination, and the risk that health personnel would need more sick leave. There were already staff shortages prior to the pandemic, and the situation would soon become untenable. Other urgent health care tasks would have to be cancelled to meet the COVID-related demands. Jane feared the public reactions and the critical news coverage if regional hospitals could not uphold their basic health services. Searching for solutions, Jane and her colleagues saw that another regional health authority had created a flexible reserve workforce comprised of retired nurses and doctors together with nursing and medicine students. This reserve workforce facilitated a flexible mobilization of hospital staff in response to the varying numbers of patients and vaccine availability.

National Deputy Minister of Employment Cavani, soon realized that the national activation policy was under strain from worsening unemployment resulting from the pandemic and the recurrent lockdowns. Moreover, the health restrictions and the stress experienced by many families made job-seeking increasingly hard. After consultation with the major labor-market organizations, it was decided to temporarily suspend the requirement of unemployment-benefits recipients having to demonstrate that they were actively seeking work and participating in mandatory job-training offers. Policymakers learned that the unemployed were less stressed during the pandemic and gained self-confidence from investing fewer emotional resources in hopeless job-search activities, which typically foster a sense of failure and rejection. Paradoxically, the outcome of the adaptive suspension of conditionality requirements was that the unemployed became better job candidates with better long-term job chances.

Finally, the Prime Minister Duvall, was informed that there was a severe lack of protective throughout the public sector, including many hospitals. Hence, at the beginning of the pandemic, the demand for protective equipment clearly exceeded what was in stock, and the rise of global demand made getting a new supply difficult. Her advisors helped to put together a task force that solved the problem by involving global logistics firms to use their contacts and transport systems to procure necessary equipment and by persuading private companies in the

plastic industry to re-tool flexible production techniques to produce-much needed protective gear.

1.4 Robustness as an alternative to resilience and agility

In other words, robust governance is about trying to do things in different ways in order to be able to uphold key public functions, goals, and values in a turbulent environment. This report aims to lay the foundation for future research on robust governance by defining the concept of robustness. When defining a concept, it is an often-used strategy to put some bounds on the concept by distinguishing it from adjacent concepts. In line with this approach, we shall here show how robustness occupies a conceptual space between resilience and agility.

Resilience emphasizes the need for system maintenance in the face of perturbations and thus aims for a rapid and effective return to the status quo ante when the system is disturbed. A socio-political system is resilient if it has the capacity to bounce back and restore its original equilibrium when exposed to a shock (Davoudi et al., 2012). To illustrate, a community resilience plan is a plan for how a community can rebuild itself after a disaster by mobilizing its citizens (Norris et al., 2008). While community resilience aims for adaptation to a one-time crisis, strategic resilience aims to continuously anticipate and adjust an organizational system in response to disruptive events (Shaw & Maythorne, 2013). This approach is sometimes summarized by the conceptual trinity of protection, response, and recovery, which serve to underscore how resilience must be built before, during, and after a crisis. The problem, however, with resilience as a strategy for dealing with crisis-induced turbulence is that a return to the status quo ante is sometimes neither possible nor desirable. The societal upheavals may prevent us from restoring past solutions and the destabilization of the established path may open a welcome window for change that means that we can develop new and better solutions in the future. Hence, resilience may be too conservative in its attempt to blindly preserve the status quo ex ante without critically assessing its attractiveness or the need and opportunity for changing (Capano & Woo, 2017).

Agility and agile leadership constitute the antidote to conservative resilience strategies. Leaders should not look back and try to maintain or restore the past, but instead observe and quickly respond to new and changing social, political, economic, and technical conditions through disruptive thinking (Attar & Abdul-Kareem, 2020; Theobald et al., 2020; Hayward, 2021). Agile leaders cut through bureaucracy, build relationships, promote organizational learning, and encourage self-managing teams to experiment with improved products and processes. The goal is to produce pervasive change at all levels of the organization in response to threats and opportunities and to stay ahead of the game in the pursuit of success. Agile leaders are visionary, curious, and willing to fail fast. They are good listeners, continuous learners, and “fast

executors," who typically accept the unpredictability of change (Lang & Rumsey, 2018). While initially developed in private business firms, agile leadership is also embraced in the public sector. Here, agile leadership is needed to reduce red tape, mobilize talent and tacit knowledge in public organizations, flexibly adjust policies in the face of changing conditions and produce innovative public value outcomes for citizens (Rulinawaty & Samboteng, 2020). However, while permanent adaptation and radical innovation of products and services, production technologies and marketing techniques are essential for private businesses to survive in cut-throat markets and may completely transform the form and function of a company as long as it makes a profit, public organizations are slightly different. Government organizations are formed to maintain and preserve some basic functions, goals, and values that cannot be sacrificed in the relentless search for radical innovation. They must adapt and innovate their organizational form and its different procedures, processes, and outputs in the face of heightened turbulence, but the need for change must be balanced against the need for stability with regard to their basic functions, goals, and values.

In sum, while resilience strategy may be too much of a conservative preserve-the-past-at-any-costs that risks blinding itself to the need for change, the agility strategy may be too much of a senseless and directionless change-for-the-sake-of-changing for the public sector that risks compromising its key functions, goals, and values. Compared to these polarized strategies that aims to deal with turbulence either by means of 'bouncing back' to what was before or 'bouncing forward' to whatever may come, robust governance offers a middle ground where stability is secured through change and change is made possible by the presence of a stable institutional core.

1.5 The methods applied in making this report

The objectives of this report are pursued based on sound methods that helps to secure research quality and replicability.

First, the development of generic of definitions of turbulence and robustness is based on *bibliometric studies* of relevant research literature. We searched Google Scholar and Scopus for books and articles combining 'turbulence' and 'robustness' with different scientific sub-disciplines such as public administration, political science, economics, statistics, fluid mechanics, physics, engineering, anthropology, communication, etc. We expanded the search by looking for 'related articles' in Google Scholar and then read through abstracts to identify the texts most relevant to our endeavor, thus looking for texts from different scientific sub-disciplines with explicit discussions of either turbulence or robustness. The report presents summaries of the most precise and interesting texts. There may be other sub-disciplines that refer to turbulence and robustness that we have not discovered, but we are sure that we captured the breadth of

studies referring to and discussing the two concepts, thus allowing us to identify both conceptual variability and family resemblance between the manifold usages and conceptualizations.

Second, the proof of concept was created by testing the empirical purchasing power of the concepts of turbulence and robustness based on a *secondary analysis* of the three most cited empirical studies of the financial, refugee, and COVID-19 crises. The three times three texts were identified through a Google Scholar and Scopus search that both looked for comprehensive accounts of the three crisis and for top-cited articles. The articles were critically analyzed to find resonance and dissonance between the concepts, observations, and arguments in the texts and our concepts of turbulence and robustness and to identify where our concepts would be able to add value to the analysis. The analysis also looked for aspects of the three crises that point to shortcomings of our concepts.

Finally, the empirical validation of the practical resonance and potential usage of the generic and operational definitions of turbulence and robustness was based on *dialogical interaction* with relevant practitioners with a stake in the matter at hand. Relevant practitioners from the Danish public sector were invited and relevant practitioners from the other partner countries and the EU were invited to online seminar meetings. At the meetings, the objectives of the ROBUST project were briefly explained, before the key concepts and the usages were presented to the group of practitioners. After a short Q&A to answer any clarifying questions, the participants were given time to discuss the concepts in small groups and challenged to see if they could find empirical examples resonating with either the content of the concepts and the different ways of pursuing robustness. The plenary session took the form of a facilitated dialogue focusing on how the concepts could potentially help practitioners to understand their rapidly changing environments and their ability to respond to turbulence. The meeting was ended with the practitioners being invited to help write a shopping list regarding what questions our research on turbulence and robustness should answer.

1.6 The structure of the report

The report is structured in the following way. *Section 2* tracks the emergence of turbulent problems, presents and compares different notions of turbulences from different scientific disciplines and sub-disciplines, provides generic and operational definitions of turbulence, analyzes the relation between turbulence and crisis as well as how turbulence challenges government, and discuss how to analyze turbulence.

Section 3 deepens the discussion of how robustness provides an alternative to resilience and agility, reviews and compares different notions of robustness, provides generic and operational definitions of robustness, and offers a repertoire of robustness strategies for decision-makers.

Section 4 provides proof of concept by conducting a secondary analysis of the three most cited and relevant empirical studies of the financial, refugee, and COVID-19 crises and by engaging practitioners in a discussion of the empirical relevance of the concepts.

Section 5 concludes the report by summarizing key findings and discussing how to detect turbulence as well as how to combine and evaluate robust governance strategies.

Large parts of this report will be published in *Robust Governance in Turbulent Times* that is written by two of the authors of this report and co-authored with Chris Ansell and Jarle Trondal from the ROBUST Advisory Board. The book will be published by Cambridge University Press in its Element series.

2 Turbulence

This section explains how we have come to focus on turbulent problems, compares the use of the concept of turbulence across different disciplines and provides generic and operational definitions of turbulence. It also analyzes the relation between turbulence and crisis and how turbulence challenges governance, before finally discussing how to analyze turbulence.

2.1 From simple and wicked problems to turbulent problems

After World War II, many countries expanded the public sector in order to solve a range of fairly simple and ‘tame problems,’ where both the nature of the problem and the likely solution were clear to the decisionmakers. Infants, children, and young people required daycare, education, and training before they could enter the labor market. Those who could not sustain their living through paid employment needed social assistance, unemployment benefits, or retirement pensions. The injured, ill, and frail required hospital treatment, healthcare, and nursing homes. In response to these well-defined and relatively predictable needs, the welfare state provided a broad range of public services that were often standardized and produced in large quantities exploiting scale economies.

In the 1960s and 1970s, researchers and practitioners discovered a new type of ‘wicked problem’ that became particularly visible in public planning (Churchman, 1967; Rittel & Webber,

1973). Wicked problems are difficult to define, and closer scrutiny tends to reveal them to be symptoms of other problems. The problem settings often comprise multiple stakeholders with different perspectives and interests, giving rise to goal conflicts precluding trial-and-error strategies. There is no ultimate solution to the wicked problems emerging in social systems that are open and subject to constant change. At the same time, there tends to be no room for error or delay in solving them due to their urgent character. In short, wicked problems are both cognitively and politically complex.

The scientific discovery of wicked problems was an important achievement that helped to explain why certain policy problems were difficult to solve and why there were so many examples of policy failures. Over the years, the diagnosis of wicked problems has become so popular that we must remind ourselves that not all problems are wicked and that there are different degrees of wickedness (Alford & Head, 2017; Peters, 2017). Critics have pointed out a series of limitations and flaws in the concept of wicked problems, but they tend to admit that talking about wickedness in terms of high levels of unstructuredness or problematicity around a policy problem and wide and conflictual distances between stakeholders (Turnbull & Hoppe, 2019). Other researchers have expanded the diagnosis of wicked problems and now talk about 'super-wicked problems' (Lazarus, 2009; Levin et al. 2012): Wicked problems where the time for solving them is running out, those seeking to solve the problems are causing them, government does not control the choices necessary to solve them, and the future is irrationally discounted as decisionmakers make short-term choices. The current climate crisis and COVID-19 pandemic are examples of super-wicked problems (Auld et al., 2021).

There is widespread agreement that wicked problems are best dealt with through collaboration in networks and partnerships that allows a plurality of public and private actors to arrive at a shared understanding of the problem at hand and to identify possible solutions (Head & Alford, 2015). Roberts (2000) argues that collaborative strategies for solving wicked and unruly problems are needed when power is dispersed across levels, sectors, and organizations. Such strategies will work well when actors recognize their mutual resource dependence and the need to exchange knowledge, ideas, and know-how in the pursuit of 'collaborative advantage' (Huxham, 1996). Weber and Khademian (2008) claim that wicked problems, which are characterized by being unstructured, crosscutting, and relentless, are best solved in networks of actors engaged in sending, receiving, and integrating different forms of knowledge and ideas. As such, the capacity for networks to spur collective learning through the integration of disparate forms of knowledge is key to solving wicked problems. Head and Alford (2015) contend that collaborative governance allows distributed actors to reduce conflict through dialogue, eventually agreeing on tentative solutions. Network governance facilitates "frame reflection," a more holistic inquiry into the causes and impacts of wicked problems and a flexible adaptation of agreed-upon solutions to subsequent developments.

New research emphasizes the temporal dimension of wicked problems and talks about turbulent problem situations that in addition to being cognitively and politically complex appear to be highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected, unpredictable, and potentially overwhelming (LaPorte, 2007; Ansell & Trondal, 2017; Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2021; Dobbs, Gravey & Petetin, 2021). Hence, problems are unstable and change over time, their occurrence and intensity vary, and their impact is inconsistent in time and space. When and how these problems emerge, and spread is surprising and largely unpredictable. Finally, the gradual accumulation of direct and indirect effects makes them appear overwhelming. As such, the temporal dimension introduces a dynamic flux and mutability to problem situations, meaning that governors must constantly reexamine, redefine, and reevaluate the situation in order to tailor new, provisional responses.

The unpredictable temporal mutability of the content, form, and impact of turbulent problems renders the traditional recommendation to embrace a collaborative strategy for solving complex problems insufficient. Although collaboration remains valuable for jointly assessing changing problems and flexibly adjusting and coordinating responses, it takes more time to negotiate problems effectively and to find solutions than is often available, particularly as the number of stakeholders and the complexity of the issues grow (Johnston et al., 2011; Klijn et al., 2010); the failure to build trust, spur mutual learning and develop shared understandings in networks and partnerships may produce 'collaborative inertia' (Huxham, 2003). Moreover, governance networks may confront challenges related to their flexibility, self-organization, and informality when operating in turbulent environments. These challenges point to the importance of the careful metagovernance of collaborative networks in order to improve their functioning and decision-making capacity and to the potential value of hybrid forms of governance that allow us to capitalize on the combined advantages of networks, hierarchies, and markets and to engage in bricolage by drawing on tools from different governance paradigms (Carstensen, Sørensen & Torfing, 2023).

2.2 Interdisciplinary literature review of turbulence

The turbulence concept was originally developed in physics to describe unsteady and chaotic fluid dynamics, such as stormy weather, cloud dynamics, river currents, or fire whirls (Schmitt, 2017). Coming from the Latin 'turbulentia', meaning perturbation, trouble, and irregularity, it has long been used to describe the movements within crowds of animals, children, or troops. In the early twentieth century, concept emerged and gained popularity in fluid mechanics as a way to characterize motion that is eddying rather than laminar (Eckert, 2012). Even today, there is a whole physics journal devoted to discussions of turbulence and a raft of physics books on the topic (Tennekes, Lumley & Lumley, 1972; McComb, 1990; Libby, 1996; Belotserkovskii, Oparin & Chechetkin, 2005; Wyngaard, 2010; Bradshaw, 2013; Bailly & Comte-Bellot, 2015).

In addition to the field of physics, the concept of turbulence is also used in technical fields (e.g., engineering and computer science) as well as in non-technical disciplines, such as anthropology, relational psychology, digital communication studies, and the social sciences, including its subdisciplines of economics, international politics, public administration, and governance. This section reviews some of the main contributions from the different disciplines and subdisciplines to gauge the conceptual variations and similarities.

We begin with *fluid mechanics*, which defines turbulence as a form of gas or liquid flow with random transverse pulsations (Kochetkov, Kravchik & Podymova, 2019). Researchers in the field of fluid mechanics insist that turbulence describes irregular but not totally disorderly movements. Sreenivasan (1999) purports: 'The swirling motion of fluids that occurs irregularly in space and time is called turbulence. However, this randomness, apparent from a casual observation, is not without some order' (Sreenivasan, 1999: 383). When observing turbulent fluids, we can therefore discern an irregular pattern in the dynamic movements. In other words, turbulence involves 'the co-existence of structure and randomness' (Falkovich & Sreenivasan, 2006). While the element of structure and order allows scientists to try to model turbulent phenomena, the irregularity and randomness makes it difficult to solve the 'problem of turbulence' by providing an accurate mathematic description. Lumley and Yaglom (2001) echo this observation: 'We are still discovering how turbulence behaves, in many respects. We do have a crude, practical, working understanding of many turbulence phenomena but certainly nothing approaching a comprehensive theory.' (Lumley & Yaglom, 2001: 241).

In *engineering*, an understanding of turbulence is important to calculate the aerodynamic drag on cars, airplanes, and buildings (Davidson, 2015). According to Menter (2011), engineers engage in turbulence modelling in an 'attempt to develop approximate formulations that, despite our incomplete understanding and limited computational resources, allow engineers to obtain approximate solutions for their pressing technological applications' (Menter, 2011: 1). A good example is the use of turbulence modelling in wind energy engineering (Murakami, 1998). Turbulence is here defined as a complex non-linear multiscale problem with both expected and unexpected risks that limit the validity of traditional planning approaches in engineering and make the outcome of strategic action unpredictable (Florice & Miller, 2001).

In the adjacent field of *computer science*, there are many debates on how to use computers to model turbulence. Here, much of the research in this field studies the influence of the evolution of computer power in recent decades on turbulence research (Jiménez, 2020). The speed and quality of computer simulations have increased significantly, the discussion now focusing on whether numerical simulations will someday replace experimentation (Jiménez, 2003; Reynolds, 2005).

In the non-technical field of *anthropology*, the notion of turbulence is used to characterize the troubled inner life of people (Wikan, 1990) or as a 'metaphor for the kind of "whirl" which characterizes human life, history and everything that has to do with the interpretation of meaning' (Strecker, 1997). Others analyze socio-cultural practices in turbulent times characterized by accelerated change (Pijpers, 2016) or study the local turbulence surrounding the discourses of climate change (Michaud & Ovesen, 2013; Bartlett, 2020). Turbulence is generally said to capture the moving, unpredictable, evocative, engaging, and therapeutic dimension of anthropology.

Turbulence is also used in *relational psychology* that focuses on courtship and romantic relationships (Theiss & Solomon, 2006; Knobloch, Miller & Carpenter, 2007). In this specialized literature, relational turbulence refers to the encounter of stress, irritation, and turmoil in the transition from casual dating to more serious courtship (Solomon & Knobloch, 2004).

In the field of *digital communication*, we find studies of how social media are affected by heightened turbulence (Antonakaki et al., 2017) and how social media creates turbulence (Margetts et al., 2015; Treppe, 2015; Manrique et al., 2022). However, this relatively small literature seems to have few and limited reflections regarding the nature of turbulence beyond the description of events as unpredictable, unstable, and unsustainable.

In the *social sciences*, references to turbulence first appeared in the late 1960s (Emery & Trist, 1965; Easton, 1965; Waldo, 1971). Since then, increasing numbers of scholars have used the concept when aiming to account for the dynamic complexity of social, economic, and political processes at the organizational, national, and international levels (Radford, 1978; Drucker, 1993; Rosenau, 1997a; Brown, Haltiwanger & Lane, 2008).

The subdiscipline of *economics* includes a wide literature on turbulence at the macroeconomic level in relation to financial and monetary flux (Aliber, 2011; Arellano, Bai, & Kehoe, 2019) as well as volatility in the business cycle (Arias, Hansen, & Ohanian, 2007), productivity (Bosma and Nieuwenhuijsen, 2000), and taxation (Ashworth & Heyndels, 2002). Here, turbulence is described as constant flux created by shifts in consumer demands, changes in technology, ongoing mergers and acquisitions, and increased competition. Some economists speculate that turbulence perceived as a constant process of creation and destruction contributes to a stronger economy by making it more flexible and adaptable (Brown, Haltiwanger & Lane, 2008).

There is an even wider literature on how companies deal at the micro level deal with turbulent environments that are complex and dynamic and characterized by rapid changes in industrial structure and global competition (Achrol, 1991). Many contributions in this area see firm and

product innovation as an important element in the response to external turbulence (Calantone, Garcia & Dröge, 2003; Buganza, Dell'Era & Verganti, 2009; Danneels & Sethi, 2011; Tsai & Yang, 2014; Bodlaj & Čater, 2019). Environmental turbulence calls for the development of ambidextrous firms that can maintain effectiveness while creatively exploring alternatives. The conditions for private firms to respond flexibly to environmental turbulence is also a key theme in the economic literature (see Lichtenthaler, 2009; Wilden & Gudergan, 2015).

A few articles broaden the conception of turbulent environments to include the global challenges to natural resources and human life conditions and recommend different types of adaptive management (Allen et al., 2011) and innovative strategies (Davidson & Ridder, 2006) and policies (Dobbs, Gravey & Petetin, 2021). In the face of the threats to socio-biological sustainability, Zuber-Skerritt (2012) recommends action research as a tool for promoting sustainable development. Turbulence is increasing in the world of today and is seen to have an unpredictable, sudden, and devastating impact on economic, social, and ecological life. Action research stimulate problem-focused learning and the development of innovative change strategies.

In the subdiscipline of *international politics*, scholars have focused on the rise of turbulence in international politics and the increasingly globalized world system. This literature contrasts the national-level studies of political turbulence (Griswold, 1999; Carty, 2006; Chaisty & Whitefield, 2017). Rosenau was the first to address the issue of turbulence in international politics, defining it as 'the tensions and changes that ensue when the structures and processes that normally sustain world politics are unsettled' (Rosenau, 2018: 8). The consequence of the heightened turbulence in world politics is that 'demands are intensified, tensions are exacerbated, policymaking is paralyzed, or outcomes otherwise rendered less certain and the future more obscure' (Rosenau, 2018: 8). Based on this diagnosis, Rosenau studies how turbulence in the world system necessitates and conditions global order, governance, security, multilateralism (Rosenau, 1966, 1995, 1997a, 1997b). Haas (1976) is another prominent scholar discussing the role of turbulence in international politics. His concern is that the growing turbulence in international politics undermines the central assumptions guiding theories of regional integration, which prevents the prediction of the patterns of integration. Related publications either tend to focus on particular turbulent crisis situations such as the financial crisis (see Busumtwi-Sam & Dobuzinskis, 2002; Maull, 2011) or the foreign policy challenges of particular nation-states operating in an increasingly turbulent world system (see Reus-Smith, 2002; Nimijean, 2018; Lieber, 2022).

In the subdiscipline of *public administration and governance*, an early contribution to understanding the role of turbulence is provided by Emery and Trist (1965). In the agenda-setting article, Emery and Trist offers a theoretical account of how public and private

organizations change in response to their environment. While some organizational environments are passive and random, reactive and clustered, or interacting with the organization, it is also possible that organizations face a turbulent field where internal dynamics produce uncertain and unpredictable change. Waldo (1971) observed how public administration confronts an increasingly turbulent environment. He identifies a growing conflict between the rising materialistic expectations related to urbanization, mass consumption, and industrial production and the emerging anti-materialistic revolt stressing the destruction of the biosphere, pollution of the environment, inner-city decay, and declining quality of life. There will be an increasing turbulence, to the extent that the two opposing logics collide, and public administration will find itself in the midst of this turbulence and must prepare to act or react intelligently (Waldo, 1971: 277-78). Drucker (1993) tends to agree with Waldo's diagnosis of a rising social, economic, and political turbulence from the early 1970s onwards. While rapid but predictable change characterized the postwar period, the new turbulence was characterized by less predictable rapid change marked by radical structural shifts and changed the critical parameters of the world in which public managers operated. While both Waldo and Drucker focus on the need for the public administration to respond to societal turbulence by intervening in socioeconomic processes, more recent contributions investigate how turbulence may enhance administrative discretion (Holzer & Yang, 2005) and how turbulence may enable organizational leaders to pursue internal organizational politics (Kurchner-Hawkins & Miller, 2006).

Going beyond the organizational perspective of the public administration literature, the new governance research aims to understand how dynamic interactive change challenge governance, defined as the formulation and realization of common goals (Ansell, Trondal & Øgård, 2017; Ansell & Trondal, 2018; Nolte, Bushnell & Mews, 2020; Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2021; Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2023; Lund & Andersen, 2023; Zhong, Hu & Kapucu, 2023; Carstensen, Sørensen & Torfing, 2023). Turbulence is typically defined as 'situations where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways' (Ansell & Trondal, 2018: 1) and it is seen to provide a problematic condition for public governance that test the sustainability of existing institutional arrangements, forcing public and private actors to act in new ways.

Drawing on the previous literature on turbulence, the new governance research sees turbulence as a property of organizations, their external environment, and broader multi-scalar systems. Ansell and Trondal (2018: 4-5) distinguish between: 1) Turbulent organizations where turbulence is institutionally embedded in factional conflict, staff turnover, conflicting rules, internal reform, clashing governance paradigms, complex operations, etc.; 2) Turbulent environments where turbulence is produced by external factors, such as legal rulings, accidents, rapid technological change, wars, protests, partisan conflict, etc.; and 3) Turbulence of scale that appears when what

happens at one level of governance or scale of activity negatively affects what happens at another level or scale. The three types of turbulence may interact. Environmental turbulence may trigger organizational turbulence, which may in turn have negative cross-scale consequences.

The growing appreciation of turbulence in the social sciences is echoed in Popper's influential distinction between clouds and clocks. Popper asks us to imagine a continuum of systems stretching from the most irregular, disorderly, and unpredictable 'clouds' to the most regular, orderly, and predictable 'clocks' (Popper, 1966). While Newtonian physics aimed to reduce clouds to clocks, ultimately claiming that 'all clouds are clocks' *and* quantum physics insisted on the presence of indeterminacy at the heart of every system, thus claiming that 'all clocks are clouds', Popper claims that we are seldom in a world of complete determinacy or complete indeterminacy (see also Almond & Genco, 1977). When dealing with socio-political systems, we are facing a shifting balance between constraints and opportunities that makes us move between the extreme ends of the continuum without ever reaching the end point; systems appear to be relatively stable and controlled – at other times, they are highly turbulent.

It is important not to succumb to the urge to reduce turbulent cloud problems to stable and well-structured clock problems, as that would neglect important aspects of the problem and lead to a flawed problem-solving strategy. Turbulent cloud problems cannot be solved through expert-driven managerial strategies based only on convergent thinking; they require a combination of emergent, divergent, and convergent thinking (Fasko, 2001). Experiences, knowledge, and ideas from a broad range of actors must be mobilized, scrutinized, integrated, and adapted to properly deal with cloud problems that constitute a complexly moving target.

Despite the growing recognition among social scientists of the challenge posed by turbulent cloud problems, the scholarship in this area has remained marginal, perhaps mirroring how many social scientists prefer to study routine governance and administration in stable contexts while using sophisticated quantitative methods to build simple, logical, and rigorous models based on well-established causalities. As shown above, however, the scholarship on turbulence in the social sciences is growing. Triggered by tumultuous events such as the financial crisis, the refugee crisis, the climate crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic, the 2022 Transatlantic Dialogue conference, 2023 IRSPM conference, and a special issue of *Public Administration: An International Quarterly* have drawn new attention to the importance of studying turbulence and its implications for public administration and governance.

2.3 Generic definition of turbulence and societal turbulence

The literature review shows that the concept of turbulence emerged in natural and technical sciences and later was translated into the humanities and the social sciences. This translating is perhaps most clearly visible in the work of Emery and Trist (1965), Popper (1966), and Rosenau (1990). In the social science, and not least in the subdiscipline of public administration and governance, there seems to be a growing interest in turbulence as condition for public policy and service provision. This growing interest is motivated by the increasing frequency of crises in advanced industrial societies.

Across the different scientific disciplines and subdisciplines, there is a clear family resemblance between the different descriptions of turbulence. Turbulence refers to 'irregular pulsating flows' and 'random movements' giving rise to a 'dynamic complexity' that contains and engenders 'non-linear multi-scale disturbances'. Turbulence is characterized by 'accelerated change', 'unpredictability' and 'unexpected risks'. It fosters 'turmoil, irritation and stress', produces 'unstable, inconsistent, and unsustainable events' and leads to enhanced 'volatility and constant flux'. Turbulence is 'sudden and devastating', creates 'exacerbated tensions', 'policy paralysis' 'uncertain outcomes' and 'obscure futures'. It 'moves the ground' because 'logics are colliding' leading to 'radical structural shifts'. Hence, turbulence is described as a particular form of sudden, surprising, and accelerated change that involves complex, dynamic, conflictual, and unpredictable interactions between events, developments and demands that tend to create technical or socio-political challenges, irritations, and stressful uncertainties.

In summary, a generic definition of turbulence covering most of the usages of the concept across scientific disciplines and subdisciplines is that turbulence is a more or less enduring situation characterized by unpredictable and unsteady dynamics arising from the interaction between highly variable, inconsistent, and unexpected flows.

At the generic level, turbulence is an emergent property of processes, relations, environments, organizations, and systems. When actors face a turbulent situation, they tend to see it is a problem for continued stability, but also sometimes as an opportunity for something new and promising to emerge. Turbulent movements may break you if you fail to react, but if you move with the flow and adapt and innovate you may come out on top.

The actor perspective on turbulence is particularly important in the social sciences where social, economic, and political turbulence may trigger demands and stimulate maladaptive practices that fuel the turbulent interaction between highly variable, inconsistent, and unexpected events and developments, thus creating increasing tumultuous and unpredictable situations that problematize the existing forms of governance and administration. *Hence, we can define societal turbulence as a situation where cascading and interrelated social, natural, economic, and political*

events, demands and developments unexpectedly create unpredictable temporal dynamics that jeopardize the preservation of core functions, goals, and values of society and/or particular sectors of society.

What turbulence adds to previous diagnoses of governance challenges is temporal variation and unpredictability. Public governance is not merely bugged by complex problems that are hard to solve due to a combination of cognitive and political constraints. It is challenged by the surprising emergence of enduring situations where events, demands and developments interact in complex and unexpected ways and change unpredictably over time, thus requiring new and malleable solutions.

2.4 Operational definition of societal turbulence

Turbulence is an increasingly permanent condition for public governance and administration, but we need to know when we are facing turbulence rather than a passing threat to stable governance or a wicked or tame problem. Hence, we need an operational definition of societal turbulence.

The operational definition of societal turbulence involves three steps. First, an unexpected and troubling situation has emerged and makes it clear for the main governance actors that some of the core functions, goals, and values of the public sector can no longer be maintained based on its current *modus operandi*.

Second, a closer analysis of the unexpected and troubling situation reveals a complex and dynamic interaction between several events and developments that tend to generate new demands, social and political tensions and maladaptive governance practices that makes the situation even more tumultuous.

Finally, the dynamic interaction between events, developments, and demands create unique, changing, and unpredictable conditions for public governance and administration that force public governance to observe and respond rather than predict and deliver.

2.5 Turbulence and crisis

To better understand the concept of turbulence, we need to further explore the relation between turbulence and crisis. The widely used concept of crisis does much of the same analytical work as the concept of turbulence; they both emphasize turmoil and disruption that calls for special treatment and dedicated governance responses. However, for three reasons, the two concepts should be treated as different and complementary, albeit closely related concepts.

First, whereas crisis is often associated with a critical moment of threat that leads to the survival or collapse of the health of a person, organization, or wider system, turbulence is seen to characterize a situation that has a certain extension in time (Ansell & Trondal, 2018). True, a critical moment may be “creeping” and last for a while (Boin, Ekengren & Rhinard, 2020), but crises are not assumed to endure and be near-chronic in the same way as turbulence. To illustrate, racial conflicts have produced high levels of turbulence in and around American schools for decades, eliciting shifting political and administrative responses, whereas a school shooting produces a momentary crisis for the local school management that calls for swift action. In short: Crisis is momentous, but turbulence may endure.

Second, crisis is often associated with a single triggering event that may lead to a breakdown or collapse. For example, government crisis may be triggered by a mediatized political scandal or losing a parliamentary majority in a by-election. An economic crisis may be triggered by a cascade of major bankruptcies. Social crisis may be prompted by a clear and horrifying example of racially motivated police violence. By contrast, turbulence is a condition characterized by a dynamic and unpredictable interaction between a several disruptive events, developments and demands that seem to amplify each other and give rise to new perturbations. The decentered turmoil associated with turbulence is exactly what makes it so difficult to comprehend.

Third, crisis is commonly seen as threatening to the structure and functioning of a particular system, which prompts an urgent response to prevent its partial or wholesale breakdown (see Rosenthal et al., 1989). Turbulence may also problematize the core values, goals, or functions of a system, but it rarely constitutes a threat to the system as such. Some systems may even tolerate and learn to cope with relatively high levels of turbulence. Crisis management organizations are a case in point.

Yet because the crisis and turbulence concepts both capture the sense that cherished goals, stable functions, and standard procedures are disrupted by stress, turmoil, and surprise, we must consider how they are related. Here, we shall argue that the two concepts are contingently related and may mutually produce each other; but that neither of them provide the sufficient or necessary conditions for the emergence of the other. Let us consider the reciprocal causal relations in turn.

Starting with the impact of crisis on turbulence, this is by no means a simple relationship. On the one hand, surprising and disruptive crisis events with widespread repercussions, such as a financial meltdown, a sudden influx of refugees, massive flooding in the wake of a hurricane, or the outbreak of a lethal virus, tend to lead to heightened levels of turbulence, as new demands will tend to proliferate and interact with the repercussions of the crisis and create spill-over into new areas. On the other hand, crises may sometimes be contained within the system in which it

emerges and only have a limited impact on the level of societal turbulence. To illustrate, a political leadership crisis in the British Conservative Party may trigger a well-versed leader-election procedure that resolves the crisis without causing the level of societal turbulence to rise. The impact of crisis on turbulence depends on the circumstances and the initial crisis response. Sometimes a crisis really heightens the level of societal turbulence, as we have seen with the COVID-19 pandemic, and sometimes they do not, as we have seen with some of the recent wildfires in California, which are devastating for the local communities but are expected during the autumn fire season. That said, we should bear in mind that turbulence is often induced and intensified by the interaction of multiple small events and developments that produce unexpected and stressful irregularities without being triggered by crisis events. In short, turbulence may be triggered by crisis events, but is not always crisis-induced, and may expand in the absence of crisis, sometimes remaining largely unaffected by crisis events.

We find an equally complex relationship when considering the impact of turbulence on crisis. On the one hand, the failure to respond to increasing societal turbulence, such as the proliferation of official and unofficial strikes in the UK during the 1978-1979 Winter of Discontent, or the choice of a maladaptive response to growing turbulence, such as reacting to the growing number of “anti-vaxxers” by fining the parents of unvaccinated children, may trigger a threatening crisis due to the failure to tackle rising turbulence adequately. On the other hand, turbulence may persist before, during and after a major societal crisis without either causing or accelerating it. To illustrate: Denmark, being a highly homogeneous society, has seen much racially induced turbulence in the wake of a growing influx of immigrants and refugees, but it hardly affected the refugee crisis in the spring of 2022 when Denmark received more than 25,000 Ukrainian refugees. Volunteers and municipalities across the country welcomed them, and they were granted a two-year residence permit that allowed them to be full members of Danish society. In short, while turbulence that is not met by a proper response may trigger a crisis, crisis may be sheltered from any impact of ongoing societal turbulence.

In conclusion, turbulence and crisis are different but intrinsically linked concepts that are contingently related in the sense that under certain conditions one may lead to the other and vice versa, while they may also emerge independently, thus being *causa sui*.

2.6 Turbulence as a challenge to governance

Accepting the verdict that we are living in increasingly turbulent times; the question becomes how turbulence challenges how governments are governing present-day societies. Short of an exhaustive list, we believe that governments face five significant challenges in turbulent times.

The first challenge is that the rationalistic faith in forecasting, preparedness, and insurance is of limited use when confronting turbulent problems characterized by dynamic unpredictability. Forecasting uses historical data as input to make informed projections and estimates about the direction of future trends, but turbulence introduces an unpredictable volatility that questions the use of foresight. Preparing for the next situation of heightened turbulence will tend to look back and try to learn from the last series of tumultuous events, but the whole point of turbulence is that the next time the problem and the associated demands will have changed and, therefore, the preparedness strategy, the policy tools and the equipment stored in warehouses may prove useless. Finally, protection through the creation of different types of insurance schemes builds on risk calculations, but such calculations are impossible if the form and content of problems and challenges are constantly shifting. In short, turbulence jeopardizes classical risk-minimization strategies.

The second challenge is for government actors to act with confidence and determination in highly stressful situations with limited and uncertain information about the problem at hand, a poor and incomplete understanding of the situation, and clear signs that problems and demands are constantly mutating. In situations with crisis-induced turbulence, government actors are forced to make decisions under time pressure and with limited knowledge of the problem and the range of possible solutions. They must act swiftly and appropriately to maintain public trust in government, but they cannot commit wholeheartedly to a particular strategy, as the problems and challenges they are acting upon are likely to change. They must rely on 'good enough' solutions that are subsequently changed in response to new and emerging events, demands, and developments.

The third challenge is to build the capacity to combine—in flexible and unforeseen ways—public, private, and civic capabilities when hit by turbulent problems and events. Administrative silos and sectoral boundaries must be pierced, weakened, or broken down to mobilize the resources that are needed to deal with turbulent situations, which is a tall order in a public sector where leaders and managers have been told for decades to solve problems and deliver on key performance indicators by drawing on their own budget, organizational resources, and employees. Turbulence requires the formation of crosscutting teams that facilitate knowledge sharing, coordination, and collaboration across organizational boundaries. The authority to request resources from other organizations and sectors must be distributed to allow flexible and creative combinations of manifold resources.

The fourth challenge is to act quickly, intuitively, and creatively in situations with an urgent need for cross-boundary deliberation and coordination and for safeguarding core public values (e.g., legality, transparency, and democracy). The pressure to deal with spiking turbulence often leads to executive elite decisions that are not tested in and through open deliberation and that risk

violating key principles, values, and procedures because the available knowledge and ideas is not properly assessed due to the need for swift decisions. During the COVID-19 pandemic there were several examples of this apparently 'necessary' decision-making style leading to decisions that were illegal or conflicted with democratic and administrative norms. Hence, finding ways of considering the available information and forms of knowledge and getting second opinions in turbulent environments with high levels of stress and pressure to act is a yet unresolved challenge.

The fifth challenge is for public decisionmakers to constantly adapt their problem-solving strategies without eroding public trust. When problems and challenges are changing, public response strategies must follow suit. The public might perceive the changing course of public decisionmakers as confused, or purposeless, and public governors must make a huge effort to explain and justify sudden shifts in policy, governance, and administration. New provisional responses to turbulence often rely on experimentation. When there is no standard solution available, one must resort to experimentation, which risks failure and must be managed.

Turbulence has become the new normal, which clearly seems to challenge the normal way of governing society and the economy. The challenges are so overwhelming that we need to rethink public governance. That said, turbulence may be perceived differently by different public organizations: some organizations (e.g., disaster management agencies) will tend to see turbulence as a standard condition whereas other organizations such as a ministry of education or taxation will tend to view turbulence as an exceptional disturbance. Hence, whereas the former tends to see turbulence as a manageable part of the organizational context, the latter perceive turbulence as a threat to their modus operandi and organizational performance. Such organizations may benefit from new ideas about how to deal with turbulence.

2.7 How to analyze turbulence?

While governments and public agencies strive to be proactive and shape the future by crafting ambitious visions, launching bold missions, and developing strategies, plans, and scenarios, they are often reactive in the sense that they spend most of their time responding to emerging problems and challenges. Governments face an abundance of problems that seem to come from everywhere. Citizens complain over unsolved societal problems, inaccessible or low-quality services, or failing governance solutions. Interest organizations draw attention to mounting socioeconomic problems and criticize the ignorance and inaction of government and the frequent policy failures. Monitoring watchdog organizations join the chorus of policy experts and scientists to arrest social inequalities and potential threats to the environment or public health and security. Public agencies underline ambiguities in political decisions, identify conflicts between different policy strategies, and report implementation problems. They may also

implode due to the lack of leadership or internal administrative blunders and scandals. Finally, international organizations reveal government underperformance by publishing all kinds of league tables and they take issue with nation-states that are not complying with international rules and conventions. Global crises such as wars, financial meltdowns, pandemics, refugee crises, etc. hardly need any messenger, but send a clear signal to government that national security in a broad sense of the term is threatened. Old and new mass media compete to present a daily buffet of problems, challenges, and crises, some of which are amplified whereas others are toned down depending on how they fit with the news criteria of the commercial mass media.

This constant problem bombardment forces governments to carefully select the problems they will address and to create a prioritized list of solvable problems (Jones & Baumgartner, 2005). When assessing the nature and importance of the myriad of small, medium, and big problems, governments rely on a combination of ideological norms and values, political and practical intuition, and data-driven administrative reports. The easy solution is to prioritize problems that appear to be urgent and politically opportune and possible to solve (Green-Pedersen & Stubager, 2010). However, problems that are neglected may grow big and become even more difficult to solve over time. Hence, giving all problems a fair hearing might be a good idea and in so doing, public decisionmakers may want to assess whether problems are simple, complex, or turbulent.

When governments face turbulent problems, these will neither seem simple and manageable nor complex in a cognitive and political sense, but also sudden, unpredictable, unique, and dynamic (Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing, 2021). The test for turbulence is whether there were any credible predictions or forewarnings of a problematic situation and whether there has been a similar problem with the same form and gravity as the current problem. Even more importantly, decisionmakers must look at the dynamics of the emerging problems and challenges to ascertain whether the problems and challenges are interacting, multiplying, and changing in unexpected ways and tend to have varying and/or inconsistent effects, just as the COVID virus that constantly mutated and affected different age groups in different ways. If the problems and challenges tick these boxes, then decisionmakers will know that they are facing heightened turbulence in which events, developments and demands combine in unstructured and surprising ways. This raises the pertinent question of whether the decisionmakers and the system of governance within which they operate has the capacity for robust action.

While important for deciding which problem-solving strategy to pursue, the categorization of problems and challenges is demanding and complicated. Often problems must be explored and assessed on a regular basis since what appears to be simple problem may later turn into a complex problem, which in turn may develop into a turbulent problem situation. Problems may

also lose their turbulent character over time and become complex or even simple. To illustrate, the COVID-19 pandemic gradually became less turbulent and called for static rather than dynamic resilience (Cristofoli et al., 2022).

When public organizations and their network of related actors are hit by turbulence, the next task becomes to diagnose the turbulent events and developments to learn more about their form and character (see Arvidsson, 2014). Turbulence is a moving target, but it might be relevant to assess the scope of turbulence and the prospect for containment or spread. Turbulence may be internal to an organization, pervade an entire policy area, or cut through policy areas, sector boundaries, governance levels, and national borders to become a near-global phenomenon. The scope of turbulence may expand or shrink over time. Much depends on the ability to contain turbulence. New unexpected events may either facilitate or prevent the containment of turbulence.

It is also important to analyze the varying degrees of adversity of turbulent events, demands, and developments. Is turbulence merely annoying because it disrupts a planned set of actions? Is it creating a growing amount of stress for the members of one or more organizations and their organizational leadership? Or is turbulence seen to constitute a threat to national or global security? The degree of adversity will tend to determine how much attention the turbulent events and developments will receive and how much resources are invested in developing a response.

Another dimension of turbulence that calls for analysis is the varying degrees of newness of the emerging turbulence and the existence of relevant past solutions. Is the tumultuous unfolding of unpredictable events and developments similar or dissimilar to previous experiences? Wherein lies the newness and what is its impact? These questions are important because the answers determine the ability to draw on modified versions of past solutions and the need to come up with innovative solutions.

The unpredictable and volatile dynamics deprive us of the ability to forecast turbulent events and developments. Modelling the complex interactions between a plethora of disruptive events, surprising developments, unexpected repercussions, and changing demands is impossible. However, decisionmakers may still create, discuss, and evaluate alternative trajectories of turbulent events and developments to try to stay ahead of the game by thinking through different best- or worst-case scenarios and what they will require in terms of new and changing responses (Schultz, Crews & Lum, 2012). The scenarios may be proven wrong by reality. Nevertheless, they may help decisionmakers to meet the future with an open mind because they demonstrate the need to keep all options open.

A last point in the diagnostic analysis of turbulence is the assessments of the likely endurance of the turbulent predicament. Turbulent predicaments come and go unexpectedly, but the governance response of the actors placed in the eye of the storm may in part depend on their estimated endurance. If turbulent events and developments are expected to blow over or be fading, the investment in finding adequate responses may be smaller than if turbulence is on the rise and likely to continue. A high degree of adversity may, of course, prompt actors to scale their response even in the turbulence predicament is deemed to be short-lived. As such, researchers may study what different actors think about the endurance of turbulence and how it influences their actions.

It is by no means easy to make a precise diagnosis of the different dimension of turbulence because of its unpredictable dynamism. The diagnosis will change over time and may also be ambiguous as it reflects the ambiguity of turbulence. Moreover, real actors engaged in diagnosing a turbulent predicament may disagree about the diagnosis or the most prevalent diagnosis may be contested.

The analytical endeavor to diagnose turbulence by describing its inherent features provides us with a better understanding of what we have in front of us. This begs the question of how to explain turbulence. While it is impossible to explain the movements in a flock of birds flying in the sky, a crowd of children in a playground, or troops engaging in skirmish, we may meaningfully enquire into the necessary and sufficient conditions of the complex movements. Birds gather in big flocks when the season change and it is time for migration, children may come to a playground to play tag as a part of birthday party, and troops may move around because they are aiming to take control within a city. Societal turbulence can be subjected to the same type of explanatory analysis. Hence, we may ask what triggered a sudden heightening of the normal level of turbulence in society. As explained above, societal turbulence may be caused by a crisis that remains uncontained despite different authoritative crisis responses and therefore has widespread repercussions that jumps from one area to another and generates a cascade of disruptive events, developments, and demands. However, there is also another possibility, namely that turbulence is triggered by a few independent political, economic, and social events that creates societal turmoil that give rise to maladaptive responses that feed the turbulent events and developments that expand and grow in numbers.

Following this argument, the analysis of turbulence should aim to explore the conditions for containing a sudden political, economic, or social crisis and seek to unravel the spill-over mechanisms and feedback loops between different events, developments, and demands that may exacerbate and deepen the overall experience of turbulence. Attention should also be paid to the role of maladaptive responses to growing societal turbulence that may fuel a self-accelerating process of growing turbulence.

3 Robust governance

The disruptive presence of societal turbulence is increasingly seen as normalcy rather than a rare exception. Hence, public governors must ready themselves to tackle turbulent events and developments on a regular basis. This predicament prompts governance researchers and policymakers to find answers to the question of how to deliver effective and legitimate governance in tumultuous situations characterized by considerable unpredictability, irregularity, and inconsistency. This section claims that public governors facing a heightened societal turbulence must deliver robust governance that aims to preserve key functions, goals, and values, and perhaps even some important governance architectures by means of adapting and innovating the modus operandi of the public sector. The section begins by presenting robust governance as an alternative to resilience and agility and then presents the results of an interdisciplinary literature of robustness. Based on this review, it offers generic and operational definitions of robustness and related concepts such as robust governance, robust democracy, and robust legality. The definition of robust governance is followed by the presentation of the repertoire of different robustness strategies that public governance may draw upon and combine when dealing with societal governance. There will also be a discussion of the mindset and institutional and societal conditions that may support robust governance before the section is concluded with some reflections about how to study robust governance of turbulence.

3.1 Robust governance as a response to turbulence beyond agility and resilience

The increasingly fashionable resilience and agility strategies both tend to view turbulence as an inherent trait of modern society. Both pay full attention to the factors influencing the capacity of a particular unit—whether it is a system, an organization, or individual actor—to respond to unpredictable perturbations. Yet, the conclusions they draw about the type of strategic action that derives from the appreciation of turbulence differ considerably.

In a review of *resilience theory* in disciplines such as developmental psychology, psychiatry, biology, and environmental sciences, Windle (2011: 163) defines resilience as ‘the process of effectively negotiating, adapting to, or managing significant sources of stress or trauma, which requires “a capacity for adaptation” and “bouncing back” in the face of adversity’ (Windle, 2011: 163). This definition highlights two slightly different understandings of what being resilient entails: 1) to recover and restore the status quo ex ante, and 2) to adapt to an emerging reality. Cretney (2014: 630) identifies the same two aspects of resilience in a review that includes both natural and social science disciplines. Building on the identification of these two different aspects of resilience, the most recent contributions draw a distinction between static and dynamic resilience (Simonovic & Arunkumar, 2016; Ansell et al., 2017; Deloukas & Apostolopoulou, 2017; Chen et al., 2022). Static resilience is when a unit manages to fully recover

and preserve its form and functioning in the wake of disruptive perturbations while dynamic resilience is when the unit adjusts its form and functioning to the new and unforeseen circumstances to maintain some key aspects of the status quo ex ante. Although static and dynamic resilience differ in terms of how much change they aim for, both strategies are inherently conservative in the sense that their goal is to return to the equilibrium that was disturbed by crisis and turbulence (Walker et al., 2006; Folke, 2006). While static resilience seeks to return to the original equilibrium, dynamic resilience aims to stay within a 'zone of equilibrium', which allows for incremental re-positioning (Holling, 1973).

The explicit or implicit references to 'equilibrium' as the ultimate success criterion attest to the predominance of systems theory in resilience research. A core assumption of systems theory is that a system only survives if it maintains its equilibrium and manages to secure its functional prerequisites (Parsons, 1951). There are also strands of social science research that are more inspired by institutional theory and social network theory, but these alternative theories also tend to associate resilience with propensity for stability (Adger, 2000; Norris et al., 2008; O'Malley, 2010; Simmie & Martin, 2010; Comfort, Boin & Dumchak, 2010; Cashman, 2017; Duit et al., 2010; Mingus & Horiuchi, 2012; van den Heuvel, et al., 2014; Boin & Lodge, 2016; Hartley & Howlett, 2021). There is nothing wrong with the ambition to restore equilibrium or maintain stability in the face of flux and chaos. However, the status quo ex ante may not be possible to restore in the light of the new and shifting circumstances, and stability based on pattern maintenance may not be very attractive compared to the new opportunities that become visible when society is hit by crisis and turbulence.

In contrast to the conservative and somewhat reactive approach of resilience theory, *agility theory* takes a more proactive, entrepreneurial, and almost revolutionary approach, and it is more inclined to accept disequilibrium in the same way as does much of business innovation theory (Mathews, 2006). The main message of agility theory is that the most effective approach to unpredictability for leaders and organizations is to build structural and operational readiness to explore, exploit, and shape emerging events and opportunities. The concept of agility comes from business management and leadership research and is widely used in information systems theory (Conboy, 2009), but it has also found its way into public governance research (Light, 2005; Mergel et al., 2020). Drawing on these different literatures, we will define agility broadly as a continual readiness of units such as systems, organizations, groups, and/or individuals to embrace, learn from, exploit, and even sometimes actively stimulate creative disruptions and perturbations through interactions with their environment. Hence, agility is an ever-present competence and ambition of a unit to transform what exists to meet what comes and to exploit the opportunities arising in this process through a dynamic formation of productive interactions within as well as beyond its own perimeters. There are two agile responses to turbulence: 1) to organize for lightning by deliberately using challenges and disruptions as triggers for learning

and innovation; and 2) to create lightning by orchestrating perturbations and disruptions to stimulate creativeness and revolutionary breakthroughs (Light, 2005; Room, 2011; Sarasvathy et al., 2014; Johnson, 2018). While agility sees turbulence as a window-of-opportunity for change, it is less attentive to the need for some degree of stability and preservation of core functions, goals, and values; qualities that might be more important in the public than the private sector.

It should now be evident that the proposed response to turbulence differs between resilience and agility theories. While the former seeks to overcome turbulence, the latter embraces it to some extent. Another difference is that the success criterion for responses to turbulence differs. In resilience theory, the goal is to secure stability by reestablishing some sort of equilibrium. In agility theory, the goal is to improve and advance the production of valuable outcomes. Whereas business and management theories talk about the production of value for customers and/or stockholders, public administration and governance theory emphasizes the production of value for service users and society at large (Conboy, 2009; Luna et al., 2014; Mergel et al., 2020). The fact that there is always more value to be harvested explains the restless urge for improvement, progress, and change in agility thinking. A third difference is that although an agile approach can also be inspired by systems theory, there is also stronger focus on the role of agency and especially on entrepreneurial leadership. The key issue for the agility approach to turbulence seems to be: How can public and private leaders make their organizations more agile to explore and exploit emerging opportunities through restless change?

Robustness theory takes us beyond both the conservative bias of resilience theory and the radical self-transformation recommended by agility theory. Although the concept of robustness is far from new, there seems to be a growing interest in the attempt of robustness to balance stability and change in scientific disciplines such as engineering, developmental biology, eco-systems theory, digital systems analysis, and the social sciences (Jen, 2005; Shahrokni & Feldt, 2013; Ansell et al., 2022). The conceptual attraction of robustness is its insistence that in a turbulent environment some features of a system, institution, organization, or individual must be changed for others to remain stable (Ansell et al., 2015). Hence, robustness is generally defined as the ability of a particular unit to continue to uphold some core functions, purposes, and values and/or maintain key structural or operational architectures in the face of disruptive perturbations by means of adaptation and innovation. While the change inherent to adaptation and innovation processes is necessary to preserve some key features of a system, institution, or organization, the change process is guided and controlled by the stable functions, goals, and values that it seeks to maintain (Carlson & Doyle, 2002).

The concept of robustness begs the question of what exactly is maintained and what is changed in a robust response to turbulence. Robustness theory asserts that a unit has several functions, goals, and values, which are constantly rearticulated. The inherent heterogeneity and volatility of

units tends to produce ambiguity and tension while also creating room for maneuver that can be exploited to respond robustly to the turbulence produced by multiple interconnected perturbations, which are either internal or external to a particular unit (Jen, 2005: 12-3). From this perspective, what to maintain and what to change are relatively open questions when responding robustly to turbulence. Based on a review of theories of robustness in different disciplines including the social sciences, Jen (2005: 113) distinguishes between two different ways that units can respond robustly to turbulence. *Mutational robustness* involves withstanding perturbations without changing the articulation of core functions. Here the functions, goals and values will remain the same, while how they are pursued is changed. *Phenotypical robustness* involves rearticulating different functions by reordering their relationships, reformulating their meaning, or introducing new ones without changing the structures, procedures, and modus operandi of the unit. In other words, robustness can be achieved either by continuing to pursue a given set of functions, goals, and values by means of reforming the architecture or by redefining the functions, goals, and values to fit the existing structures, procedures, and modus operandi of the unit.

A shared feature of these two forms of robustness is that they leave many options open for how to respond to turbulence, which is indeed the essence of robustness. The strategic openness enables a unit to respond to emerging turbulence without disintegrating or becoming irrelevant or obsolete. Indeed, the basic idea of robustness is to prevail in some form or another in the face of stress, pressure, and turmoil. Prevalence is not the same as stability, however, since the former tends to presuppose continuous change and cannot be ensured merely by maintaining the effective production of outcomes. At least in the realms of politics, economics, and social reproduction, prevalence tends to require legitimacy (Jen, 2005; Sørensen & Ansell, 2023).

3.2 Interdisciplinary literature review of robustness

Robustness is part of our everyday vocabulary. It is often used to indicate *strength* as in physical health, *vigorousness* as in praising the abundance and intensity of a city or a cup of coffee, or *sturdiness* as when something is constructed to withstand pressure. Scientific references to robustness seem to increase and diversify from the 1990s onward (see Jen, 2005) where we find discussions of robustness in the natural science disciplines of chemistry, biology, engineering, computer science, and statistics as well as the social science disciplines of social system theory, economics, environmental planning, disaster management, legal studies, policy design, and democratic theory. Let us consider both the similarities and variations in the discussion of robustness across the various disciplines.

Beginning with the natural sciences, robustness has been discussed in *chemistry* with a focus on robust modelling (Gaucher et al., 2009), robust mechanisms and processes (Song, 2004) and

robust substances (Zang et al., 2021). Deng and colleagues (2010) coin the notion of 'robust dynamics' to describe constructs where the repeated dynamic of one entity does not affect the integrity of any others linked to it and go on to explain that 'the implication of this concept for dynamic molecules, whose performance has the disadvantages of random motion, is to bring them to a standstill in three-dimensional extended structures and thus significantly enhance their order, and ultimately their coherence and performance' (Deng et al., 2010: 439). As such, robustness is about creating conditions for some form of stability in the face of random motion.

Robustness is also a central theme in *biology* where robustness is a long-recognized key property of living systems and it is analyzed both at the cellular level (Stelling et al., 2004) and at the level of complex biological systems (Krakauer, 2006). In developmental biology based on neo-Darwinian theories of natural selection, robustness typically refers to the ability of a developmental process to stay on track despite perturbations due to the ubiquity of buffering and compensatory mechanisms (Hermisson & Wagner, 2004; Lewontin and Goss, 2005). Robustness ensures that specific functions of a biological system are maintained despite external and internal perturbations. Alternative (or fail-safe) mechanisms, modularity, and decoupling are seen as the key underlying mechanisms that produce robustness (Kitano, 2004, 2007). These observations lead biologists to assert that ecosystems defined as biological communities of interacting organisms and their physical environment may be relatively robust vis-à-vis disturbances caused by invasive species or anthropogenic behavior (Walker et al., 2004; Webb and Levin, 2005; Cai and Liu, 2016).

In *engineering*, robustness is understood as the design of engineering systems that has a functional reliability in the presence of both probable and improbable failures (Taguchi, Chowdhury, & Taguchi, 2000; Carlson & Doyle, 2002). Deviations from the intended function are caused by contingent variations in various engineering processes, and robust designs must be developed to improve product quality and reliability in industrial engineering by means of achieving insensitivity to noise factors (Arvidsson & Gremyr, 2008). The efforts to ensure system robustness in engineering, for example through built-in redundancies, are often more expensive than the functional features themselves (Jen, 2005). Drawing on the work of Bettis and Hitt (1995), other researchers take a more managerial approach to ensuring robustness in engineering projects. Hence, Floricel and Miller (2001) argue that achieving high project performance in turbulent environments requires organizational strategies and institutional designs that are robust with respect to anticipated risks and disruptive events.

Robustness features prominently in *computer science*, where software and computer networks are designed to perform correctly in situations with expected user or data failure, as well as in more unforeseeable situations (Willinger & Doyle, 2005). Hence, a software program may work even if the user makes an error, or an operative system may graciously close down if power is

cut. Similarly, robust computer networks allow communication to continue despite the loss of networks and routers. Building robust computer network architectures that allow for stable connectivity in the presence of failures and disturbances is a key goal for designers (Peterson & Davie, 2007).

In *statistics*, robustness signifies insensitivity to small deviations from the assumptions about randomness, independence, and distributional patterns (Huber, 1981; Launer & Wilkinson, 2014). The use of robust statistical procedures ensures that small deviations from the model assumptions impair the performance only slightly and that somewhat larger deviations from the model will not cause a catastrophe. Hence, while classical statistical inference quantities (e.g., confidence intervals, t-statistics, p-values) are adversely influenced by outliers, robust versions of these inferences' quantities are only small influences by such outliers (Maronna et al., 2019).

Social scientists have become increasingly aware of how robustness may also be a key property of social behavior, processes, and systems based on experimentation, adaptation, and learning (Anderies, Janssen & Ostrom, 2004, 2007; Anderies & Janssen 2013; Padgett & Ansell, 1993; Leifer, 1991). Here, robustness is broadly conceived as the ability to be responsive, open, and adaptive in the face of emerging challenges and unanticipated conditions caused by social, spatial, and temporal variability.

In *economics*, Cowen argues that 'while robust statistics is designed to cope with measurement error, robust institutions are designed to cope with political actions that are not conducive to the public good' (Cowen, 2016: 422). This line of thinking is taken up by other economists who expanded the notion of Robust Political Economy (RPE), which is an approach to the comparative analysis of institutions with a specific emphasis on their ability to cope with knowledge and incentive problems (Boettke & Leeson, 2004; 2006). According to Pennington (2011), RPE provides a theoretical framework for defending classical liberalism against market-failure arguments and challenges from communitarianism and egalitarianism. Hence market economies can be shown to be robust in the sense of being able to withstand the stresses and strains wrought by human imperfections (Pennington, 2011: 8).

The field of *environmental planning* also makes frequent references to the robust strategies, plans and actions that are deployed in volatile social and biological environments. To illustrate, Simonovic and Arunkumar (2016) discuss robust reservoir management and draw on the notion of dynamic resilience, which they see as a tool for selecting proactive and reactive adaptive responses to disturbing events. Durden and colleagues (2017) argue that deep-sea mining projects must be supported by robust environmental management enabling the implementation of the precautionary approach in decision making through adaptive measures capable of ensuring fairness and uniformity in the application of environmental standards in the face of

uncertainty and reports about unforeseen developments. In their discussion of strategies for abating climate change, Lempert and Schlesinger (2000) note that uncertainty prevents us from predicting the future development of sustainable energy. Consequently, they recommend that we adopt strategies that are robust against a wide range of plausible climate-change futures and will perform well even if confronted with surprises or catastrophes. Finally, Tan, Huang, and Cai (2013) discuss robust environmental management as a question of ‘adaptive conservatism’. Environmental management is robust if it maintains optimal solutions by proactively adjusting them to input fluctuations.

In the field of *disaster management*, researchers aim to build robust disaster preparedness models that allows demand to be met in an effective and fair manner under any disaster scenario (Erbeyoğlu & Bilge, 2020; Kim, Park, & Ha, 2022). Since there is a risk that prepositioned disaster relief supplies is destroyed by the disaster, the robust optimization of disaster relief may be provided through a two-step model where the location and amount of prepositioned relief supplies are decided prior to the disaster and limited amounts of relief supplies are procured post-disaster (Velasquez, Mayorga & Özaltın, 2020). Similar robust optimization models for disaster relief and evacuation are offered (Bozorgi-Amiri, Jabalameli & Al-e-Hashem, 2013; Fereiduni & Shahanaghi, 2017).

While robustness is not a central theme in *legal studies*, a few contributions discuss how legal norms can be robust in the sense of continuing to be relevant and effective in times where they are contested by emergencies and rapid change (Brunnée & Toppe, 2019; McLean et al., 2021). The rule of law is supposed to protect citizens who are subjected to the law from arbitrary and unpredictable treatment. It comes under pressure when governments face emergencies or want to transform society, and the question becomes whether and how the rule of law will be upheld in some form or another in such situations (Sypnowich, 1999).

Recently, the field of *policy design* has been overflowing with research on robustness. An early contribution by Dryzek (1983) called for the abandonment of optimization as the guiding principle for policy design, arguing instead for a stronger focus on robust policy designs that have the capacity to perform tolerably well across the whole range of different contexts and scenarios. In a more recent article, Ferraro, Etzion, and Gehman (2015) discuss how organizations can tackle grand societal challenges that are multidimensional, uncertain, complex, and nonlinear. Citing Padgett and Powell (2012), they claim the proper response to be robust action aimed at keeping future lines of action open in strategic contexts where opponents are trying to narrow them. Robust policy action is said to combine flexibility and innovation. Capano and Woo compare the concepts of resilience and robustness and they praise the potential use of the latter that, citing Jen (2005) and Bankes (2010), they define as the ability to withstand or survive external shocks and thus to maintain a certain functionality despite

perturbations that radically change the conditions for policy execution (Capano & Woo, 2017). Robustness allows policies or institutions to persist by allowing them to adapt to unpredictable dynamics. From this observation it follows that robustness is not the same as stability. Two subsequent articles explore how policies can become more robust. The first claims that robustness requires policy makers to be more agile (Capano & Woo, 2018a) and the other shows that robust policy designs are characterized by diversity, modularity, and redundancy and argues robust policy design processes require the presence of polycentric decisional process, political capacity, and technical capacity (Capano & Woo, 2018b). In a discussion of the Italian response to the COVID-19 pandemic, Capano and Toth (2022) highlight the importance of improvisation and fast learning for the design of robust policy responses to unpredictable shocks.

Howlett, Capano and Ramesh (2018) continue this line of thinking taking an even closer look at the policy instruments needed for robust policy designs aiming to grapple with uncertainty and surprise. In a turbulent VUCA world characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (see Bennett & Lemoine, 2014) policy makers must design and adopt policies featuring some level of agility, improvisation, and flexibility in their components and processes. Altering and adapting policies on the fly require slack and redundancy, and policies should incorporate a mix of different substantive policy tools as well as processes that allow the involved actors to take stock of the situation and revise the policy mix. Building on this argument, Howlett (2019) argues that intentional sequencing of policy instruments is key to ensure robustness in turbulent times. To continue to operate effectively in the face of surprising contextual changes, policy mixes must be robust and either adapt the policy tools while the goals remain unchanged, or simultaneously adapt both tools and goals (Howlett & Ramesh, 2022).

In a study of government responses to the turbulence caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, Ansell, Sørensen, and Torfing (2021) call for robust governance solutions that are sufficiently adaptable, agile, and pragmatic to uphold a particular function, goal, or set of values in the face of continuous disruption. Different robustness strategies are presented and the consequences of the new focus on robust governance for public administration and leadership are fleshed out. In a previous work, Sørensen and Torfing (2019) discuss the robustness of the so-called Finger plan that has governed metropolitan planning in Copenhagen for more than 75 years. The robustness of the Finger Plan was achieved by successfully turning problems, conflicts, and demands into design assets while simultaneously using modularity to enhance the future adaptability and polyvalence of the designed solutions. Carstensen, Sørensen, and Torfing (2023) add another tool for achieving robustness. Hence, to build robust governance, public managers must engage in bricolage and become bricoleurs in order to flexibly combine elements from competing and co-existent public governance paradigms. Doing so necessitates the

construction of institutions characterized by a high degree of flexibility, inclusive deliberation, and a balance between centralization and distributed agency.

Finally, in a more conceptual paper, Sørensen and Ansell (2023) defines political robustness of a political system as a property of its institutions (polity), political processes (politics), and policy instruments (policy). Polity robustness is defined as the ability of political institutions to flexibly adapt and creatively innovate rules and norms. Robust politics is defined as political processes such as negotiations, coalition building, and dialogical representation that produce political agendas, views and ideas that accommodate and transform political conflict and tension. Robust policy is defined as policy designs that permit concerted collective action, while allowing, sustaining, and mobilizing political agency in a manner that enhances output legitimacy.

Democratic theory has explored how democracy can be robust. Referring to the work of Pennington (2010), Layman (2016) shows how robust deliberative democracy can strengthen democracy by turning citizens into co-authors of shared public norms by means of solving intractable knowledge and incentive problems. Gruidl and Hustedde (2015) define democracy as a means by which people act together to solve problems and pursue common goal and claim that the joint production of public solutions presupposes an ecosystem of civic actors and thus the development of local communities. Building a robust democracy that is well-anchored in civic communities is challenged by the decline in social capital and thus requires dedicated efforts of community developers with specialized skills and competences including cultural awareness, facilitation, and empowerment. Sørensen and Torfing (2019) show how democracy can robustly undertake its key functions of empowered inclusion, collective agenda-setting and the making of binding decisions by combining representative democracy with participatory and deliberative democracy. Finally, further pressing the issue of institutional robustness, Bednar (2021) argues that constitutional safeguards such as institutional fragmentation and overlaps serve to make the Madisonian democracy robust vis-à-vis the diversity of rivaling political and socioeconomic interests. Today, the rise of affective polarization tends to eliminate the diversity of interests, but democratic robustness may still be ensured in relation to the federalist system that allows for differences between national- and state-expressed interests.

3.3 Generic and operational definitions of robust governance, democracy, and legality

The interdisciplinary literature review reveals a notable family resemblance between the different definitions of robustness. Robustness enhances stability and order amidst dynamic disorder and allow processes to stay on track despite perturbations through the activation of fail-safe mechanisms. Robustness aims to achieve insensitivity to noise factors and seeks to continue operations despite failure. Robust measures tolerate deviations from standard assumptions and robust solutions cope with problems and challenges and succeed to withstand

stress, which allows effective performance even when confronted with surprise and uncertainty. Robust is a form of adaptive conservatism that maintains functionality despite shocks. These definitions all seem to have more or less the same form: some degree of stable functionality is achieved in the face of turbulence.

The definitions of turbulence differ in terms of whether they specify the mechanisms that help to produce a degree of stable functionality in turbulent environments as well as in terms of what mechanism they highlight. The mechanisms cited in the literature include redundancy, modularity, decoupling, improvisation, fast learning, experimentation, adaptation, proactive adjustment, agility, bricolage and mixing of tools, deliberation, and strategies that keep options open. While several robustness strategies are mentioned, they are not always well explained. In our view, a theory of societal robustness must provide a detailed account of the strategies and mechanisms ensuring robustness (see the next section).

It goes without saying that the different disciplines differ in terms of what unit that is regarded as being robust. Molecules, cells, ecosystems, political economies, social systems, institutions, actions, and policies can be robust. What also differs is whether robustness is a passive property of the unit in question, or whether it is a result of a proactive agency. In the remainder of this report, we shall focus on robustness resulting from social and political actors responding robustly to heightened turbulence.

Providing a generic definition of robustness that covers most of the definitions of robustness appearing in the literature review must conform with the implicit formula of 'maintaining X in the face of Y' where X is a desired outcome such as stability, functionality, etc. and Y is a troublemaker that creates a disruptive turbulence. A generic definition of robustness should also explain what it is that allows X to be maintained in the face of Y. Following these guidelines, *we shall define robustness generically as the ability to uphold a particular function, goal, or value in a turbulent environment by means of flexible adaptation and/or proactive innovation.* Adaptation is a response to adversity aiming to marginally modify what can be easily changed without transforming the basic forms of what is adapted. Innovation involves the creative development and implementation of solutions that disrupt common wisdom and/or established structures, institutions, and practices. Hence, while adaptation involves a contextual modification of something, innovation adds new features to the existing format.

Based on the generic definition of governance, we can now develop a series of radial definitions of robust governance, robust democracy, and robust legality. The definitions offered below are operational definitions in the sense that they add relevant details that tell researchers and practitioners what to look for when applying the concepts in empirical analysis.

Robust governance can be defined as the ability to ensure the formulation and implementation effective and legitimate public value solutions in response to heightened turbulence through the adaptation and innovation of public policy, regulation, and service production. Robust governance aims to maintain the ability to govern society and the economy in turbulent times by deploying adaptive and innovative strategies that help to effectively solve emerging problems and challenges while ensuring broad-based support to the changing solutions as well as to the overall system of governance.

Robust democracy can be defined as the ability to uphold basic democratic functions and norms in turbulent times where patterns of political participation, contestation, and allegiance are shifting thus calling for adaptation of existing forms of democracy and the invention and integration of new forms of democracy, thus creating an adaptable compound or hybrid democracy. Robust democracy may change existing democratic procedures and experiment with new channels for participation to accommodate political pressures for change that are fed by rising societal turbulence, but the new and changing forms of democracy must fulfill some basic democratic functions.

Robust legality is defined as the construction of an adaptive combination of strict legal constraints, enablement laws, conditional exceptions, and post hoc control and accountability mechanisms that enhances the ability to maintain the rule of law in times where crisis-induced turbulence puts pressure on, or tempts, governments to act swiftly and self-willed and use drastic and coercive measures. Neither overly strict nor overly loose legal demands will suffice to uphold the rule of law in turbulent times. Instead, what is needed a mix of legal tools that must be adapted to the context to upholding the law and protecting the citizens, while ensuring government a sufficient room of maneuverability.

The three concepts of robust governance, robust democracy and robust legality all refer to a particular set of functions, goals, and values that must be upheld through robust action in turbulent times. However, these functions, goals and values are not set in stone, but are subject to gradual transformation and re-articulation over time. There might even be examples of the key functions of public governance, democracy, and legality being reinterpreted as a part of the attempt to adapt and innovate the tools by which a particular set of functions are upheld.

3.4 Robustness strategies

Through the interdisciplinary literature reviews, we have been able to identify eight ideal-typical strategies for achieving robustness in the face of mounting turbulence and crisis. In practical situations, these strategies will most likely show up in combinations depending on the context and circumstances within which decision-makers seek to ensure robust crisis governance.

a) *Redundancy, slack and buffering: 'Keep something in your back pocket'*

A standard argument for dealing with potential failure that results from disturbances, shocks or failures is to increase redundancy. Challenging the classical emphasis on enhancing organizational efficiency by reducing program overlap and duplication, Martin Landau (1969) argued that 'redundancy' that includes extra components that are not strictly necessary to the functioning of a program is an important feature of error reduction. He pointed out that the conventional wisdom at the time was that the reliability of an organization depended on the reliability of individual components and their links to other components. From this point of view, the strategy for increasing reliability is to perfect individual components, but Landau argued that all components have a risk of failure and suggested that redundancy allows systems to be more reliable by providing backup components. Overlap and duplication may reduce efficiency, but they may also reduce the likelihood of system failure.

In his research on 'normal accidents,' Charles Perrow (1999) argued that 'tightly coupled' technological systems are prone to normal accidents because they have fixed connections and processes. Such systems must intentionally *design in* redundancy by adding backup capacity. In a similar spirit, Capano and Woo (2018) argue that designing redundancy into policy is an important strategy for fostering policy robustness. Roberts (1990), however, argued that the liabilities of tight technological coupling can be mitigated by more loosely-coupled organization that mobilizes redundancy from *within* the system by redeploying or repurposing components. With respect to public policy, Howlett and Ramesh (2022: 7-8) similarly suggest the importance of going 'beyond redundancy' by allowing high-level goals, program level objectives and on-the-ground specifications to adapt to one another over time to meet new challenges.

Classic organization theory asserted that organizational slack and buffering also helps organizations manage challenging circumstances and external disruptions (March and Simon, 1958; Thompson, 1967). Slack refers to resources held (intentionally or not) in excess of those required to operate in normal or average situations. Howlett, Capano and Ramesh (2018) have recently extended this perspective to public policy, arguing that robust policies must be constructed with a certain degree of slack to be robust. Like slack, buffering refers to mechanisms that dampen or mediate external demands. Arguing that public managers can act as 'disturbance handlers,' O'Toole and Meier (2010) find support for the argument that slack managerial capacity can help public organizations mitigate the negative effects of external shocks on performance. Boundary-spanners—i.e., people who help organizations interact and negotiate with their environments—are a form of buffering that can smooth disturbances that might disrupt core production processes (Thompson, 1967).

Some research raises the question of whether slack and buffering help or hinder organizations from effectively adapting (Lynn 2005). Rather than aiding an organization to get over a rough patch, for example, it is also possible that buffering can forestall painful but necessary adjustments to new and demanding situations. Lynn (2005) argues that this depends on the nature of uncertainty and change: if conditions fluctuate in ways that can be anticipated, then there is less need for buffering; where change is discontinuous and uncertain, then buffering is more valuable.

Although redundancy, slack and buffering tend to emphasize stabilization and recovery in the face of turbulence, they also create latitude within an organization for reflection, innovation and adaptive repurposing of governance resources and tools. The lesson for public leaders is to avoid creating an overly specialized division labor and to allow some degree of overlap or cross-training between individuals and units. They should also push back against the drive for greater and greater efficiency, which can eliminate adaptive resources. Finally, investing in external networking can pay dividends by helping to buffer disturbances and by giving access to the resources and support needed in exceptional circumstances.

b) Multivocality and ambidexterity: 'Keep your options open'

Analyzing differences between amateur and expert chess players, Eric Leifer (1983) found that experts were particularly adroit at keeping their options open so that they can respond to surprise moves by the opponent. Building on this work, Eccles and Nohria (1992, 11) define robust action as 'action that accomplishes short-term objectives while preserving long-term flexibility.' Padgett and Ansell (1993) explored the robust action of the Medici family in the face of the cultural, economic and political divisions of Renaissance Florence. Their 'sphinxlike' or 'multivocal' capacity to avoid being locked into any particular role by either supporters or opponents depended on their positioning in social networks. Later, Ferraro, Etzion and Gehman (2015) picked up on the idea of multivocality as a robust strategy for dealing with grand challenges. They describe multivocality as a '[d]iscursive and material activity that sustains different interpretations among various audiences with different evaluative criteria, in a manner that promotes coordination without requiring explicit consensus' (2015: 373). Multivocality expands the room of maneuver for public governors by avoiding lock-ins and allowing for flexible adjustment.

Research on robust decision making also stresses the value of keeping your options open. This research emphasizes the value of considering alternative plausible futures and adopting strategies that can do well across these different futures (Lempert 2019, 30). Taking his cue from research on complex systems, Beinhocker (1999) has argued that strategies should place less emphasis on making accurate predictions about a single optimal strategy—since those are

inherently hard to get right—and should instead adopt an evolutionary approach that pursues multiple, shifting and combined strategies. Doing this, he argues, requires ‘parallel’ as opposed to ‘single’ searches, which in turn implies the importance of conducting experiments with a portfolio of strategies. Finding superior strategies requires a combination of local ‘adaptive walks’ (pursuit of advantage through incremental improvement or ‘exploitation’) and ‘medium or long jumps’ (more radical adaptations or ‘exploration’).

A related argument is that turbulence accentuates the need for organizations to be ‘ambidextrous’—that is, capable of both exploitation and exploration (Folger, Brosi and Stumpf-Wollersheim, 2022). Exploitation is the ability to take a given set of goals and technologies and to improve a product or process through stable procedures and continuous learning. While exploitation can lead to greater efficiency and effectiveness for achieving a certain purpose, it is often a liability if the organization is operating in a rapidly changing environment. Exploration of new and innovative goals and technologies must complement exploitation in order for the organization to seize on new opportunities and deal with unwelcome surprises. Ambidexterity can thus be seen as a strategy for combining stable exploitation with adaptable and innovative exploration.

Public governors can keep their options open by becoming conscious of the way that univocal communication or single-purpose tools and institutions can be self-limiting and close off future opportunities. When faced with a high degree of uncertainty and unpredictability, they should imagine multiple possible futures and avoid committing to or overinvesting in any particular strategy or scenario. While they should continue to do what they are good at, they should remain attuned to shifting conditions and new opportunities.

c) *Vigilance: ‘Prepare to be surprised’*

High-reliability theory stresses the importance of preparing to be surprised (LaPorte, 2007) and argues that the name of the game in managing complex technologies is ‘reacting to unexpected sequences of events’ (Roberts, 1990: 184). To be reliable, organizations must try to anticipate and prevent sources of error, with a focus on detecting and correcting ‘precursor events’ that hint at imminent problems (Schulman, 2022). Strategies for building reliability include constant training that deepens understanding of technological complexities, greater redundancy, and the giving of responsibility to skilled operators who are often low in the hierarchy.

Building on lessons from RAND Corporation research, Light (2005: xv) argues that robust organizations ‘think in futures’ and prepare to be surprised by maintaining a high level of alertness. Similarly, a characteristic of private firms that do well in turbulent environments is ‘vigilance’ (Day and Schoemaker, 2019: 1). Vigilant organizations invest in both foresight

capacities and in the dynamic capacities that allow them to respond quickly to incoming information. They balance the need for both focus and breadth in their search for information. In other words, they look for the infamous ‘needle in a haystack’ and are prepared to act when they find it.

One related argument about preparing for surprise is to attend carefully to ‘weak signals’ (Ansoff, 1975). Building on this idea, Mendonça et al. (2004: 203) suggest that weak signal analysis should be geared to the detection of ‘wild cards’—that is, low probability, high consequence events. In *Managing the Unexpected*, Weick and Sutcliffe (2015) call for ‘mindful organizing’ or ‘heedful interrelating’ as strategies for maintaining attentiveness to weak signals. These strategies depend on constant scanning for potential dangers.

Both military and disaster management communities have explicitly considered the issue of surprise. They distinguish between *situational surprise*, where an event falls outside normal expectations but remains understandable from the perspective of extant beliefs, and *fundamental surprise*, which is an event that rocks our basic beliefs (Alderson et al., 2022). In the sensemaking literature, Weick (1993) referred to the latter as ‘cosmology episodes,’ because they shake your basic perception of how the world is ordered. Such fundamental surprises pose a particularly tricky problem because responders lack the experience base to know how to respond to them. However, Alderson et al. (2022) argue that techniques like scenario exercises still provide some opportunity to train people to respond to surprising events. Scenarios are a powerful tool of exploration but should be thought of as recipes for action.

Planning is a highly problematic strategy in turbulent environments because it is difficult to establish fixed planning parameters and assumptions. However, Ramírez and Selsky (2016) argue that scenario planning is an appropriate planning approach in turbulent environments. Scenario planning can help organizations to spot turbulence as it emerges, to anticipate responses to this turbulence, to prepare experiments and prototypes for adapting to turbulence and to identify possibilities for collaboration.

In a study of U.S. transit agencies facing turbulent environments, Pasha and Poister (2017: 510-511) found that these agencies supplement strategic planning with ‘logical incrementalism,’ which refers to a strategy that is ‘continually revised based on learning, experimentation, stakeholder negotiations, political relationships, and adaptation to environmental changes within a general framework of organizational purposes.’ Subsequent research finds that organizational performance is enhanced during turbulence when formal strategic planning and logical incrementalism are used in concert, but not when they are used independently (Pasha and Poister, 2019). A recent study of Norwegian public organizations found that strategic

planning is still perceived to be useful under turbulent conditions, but primarily when it is complemented by logical incrementalism (Johnsen, 2022).

Sometimes surprise arises from *within* the response system. For example, Daupras et al. (2015) contrast a vulnerability and a robustness approach to flood warning systems. A classic vulnerability approach, they write, assumes top-down communication, technocratic guidelines for how citizens should respond to warnings, and a focus on identifying sources of vulnerability. This approach runs into trouble, however, when stakeholders do not behave as expected (i.e., in a way responsive to the top-down technocratic communication of risk). In order to enhance the robustness of a warning system, they argue, it is necessary to consider how stakeholders will respond and why. To better understand their actions and reactions, a robust warning system must engage in collaboration with relevant and affected actors before, during and after disasters.

In sum, to prepare for surprise, public leaders should promote continuous real-time investigation of possible futures. Probing these futures requires attending closely to weak signals that may signify fundamentally shifting conditions and prompts investment in the capacity to formulate multiple scenarios. Planning remains valuable but it takes a different form: it avoids placing firm bets on future conditions and instead stresses the need to observe and respond to changing circumstances. To stay vigilant in the face of turbulence, public leaders need to mobilize and activate a distributed network of internal and external actors who can help gather and interpret relevant intelligence.

d) Flexible adaptation: 'Stay ready to adapt'

By generating interactive variability, short response times and unpredictability, turbulence places a premium on the ability to remain flexible and adaptable. In their study of the management of the California electrical system, Roe and Schulman (2008) stress the importance of 'reliability professionals' who develop specialized skills and knowledge about how to manage complex technical systems. These professionals are adept at moving between different performance modes depending on the conditions they face. These performance modes vary along two dimensions—the volatility of the system (which is similar to our definition of turbulence) and the range of resources they can mobilize at a given moment ('network option variety'). Of special interest here is 'just-in-time performance,' where both system volatility and network option variety are high. This condition places a premium on 'real-time flexibility' that leads to what they call 'adaptive equifinality,' which means that professionals have a variety of ways they can meet the challenges they encounter. They also discuss what happens as options become more constrained, which they call 'just-for-now' management. This is not a desirable situation for

reliability professionals because it throws them into a coping or 'firefighting' mode of response where small events can threaten reliability.

Several research contributions stress the value of flexibility and adaptability. For example, Howlett, Capano and Ramesh (2018) argue that in the face of uncertainty and unpredictability, public policies designed to be flexible and adaptable will be more robust. A significant strand of the crisis management literature sees rigidity as a common and unfortunate organizational response to crisis and sees proactive flexibility as a necessary antidote (Deverell, 2010). LaPorte (2007: 62) points to the value of preemptively establishing 'rules of exception' that allow standard operating procedures to be revised during exceptional events. In much the same way, Light (2005) finds that robust organizations organize to enhance their flexibility and agility. While there is a lot of agreement that flexibility is a desirable quality for dealing with turbulence, it is also important to keep in mind that flexibility is enabled by stable organizational conditions such as well-integrated teams with shared knowledge and certain repertoires of action (Boyne and Meier, 2009).

Agility is often used as a synonym for flexibility in describing adaptive ability. Moon (2020), for example, attributes South Korea's effective response to COVID-19 to their 'agility-adaptability.' Studies of the private sector have found that both agility and resilience are necessary for effectively responding to turbulence (McCann, Selsky and Lee, 2009). Similarly, Harrald (2006: 268) argues that both agility and discipline are needed for effective disaster response, which can be produced by combining a 'creative culture' with a 'well-structured, well-defined process.' Recent research on agile government extends lessons from effective software development to the public sector (Mergel, Ganapati and Whitford, 2021).

It is useful to think of flexibility (or agility) as having different dimensions. One dimension is strategic or decisionmaking flexibility, which captures whether people and organizations can shift their strategy or adapt their decisions as new conditions arise (Vecchiato, 2015: 268; Eckhard et al., 2021). Another dimension might be termed 'cognitive flexibility' because it refers to the ability to take in new information, break from existing routines, and reflect critically on existing practices (Deverell, 2010). A third type might be termed 'structural flexibility,' which means that organizational structures can be easily shifted in response to changing circumstances. A fourth dimension is operational flexibility, which refers to the ability to change procedures and processes and to reallocate resources and personnel as new challenges arise (Eckhard et al., 2021).

Some scholars also argue that hybridity—the combination of different organizing principles—increases the structural flexibility that allows public organizations to respond robustly to turbulence (Trondal, Haslerud and Kühn, 2021). Eckhard et al. (2021: 419) explore the role of

organizational hybridity—which they define as cross-sector ‘fit-for-purpose entities’—in crisis management. Their research on the German refugee crisis finds that hybridization contributes to perceptions of more effective crisis response. Similarly, high reliability organizations and rapid response organizations are able to effectively shift across different modes of organization as operational tempo increases (LaPorte and Consolini, 1991).

Flexibility is not the only way to think about adapting to variability and uncertainty of the environment. Imagine a system where for each distinctive state of the world, the system could reorganize itself to respond to that particular state. If such a state of the world comes about rapidly or unexpectedly, the system property that allows it to respond to these changes through time would be *flexibility* that enables the system to easily and rapidly adjust itself to each new condition. However, consider a second circumstance where the world does not merely change from one state to another, but simultaneously contains different states. In such a world, an organization may wish to maintain the ability to respond simultaneously to multiple conditions, a situation that system theorists refer to as ‘requisite variety’—the idea that the system should be as diverse as the environment it operates in.

These ideas of diversity and flexibility are often fudged together and are rarely distinct in practice but are useful to keep analytically distinct because they highlight different robustness strategies. They also point to some of the tensions and tradeoffs that may be inherent in developing such strategies. On the one hand, following Beinhocker (1999), robustness may be enhanced through an evolutionary approach of developing a ‘population’ of strategies (experiments) operating simultaneously. Keeping a portfolio of projects going, however, is likely to be in tension with focusing your resources and investments on a particular project of high potential. The less certain we are about which project will pan out, the more the portfolio approach will become attractive. On the other hand, flexibility—understood as the ability to easily adapt to a specific situation—is likely to be especially useful when conditions are changing rapidly and unexpectedly. Fostering flexibility often comes at the cost of building and maintaining more dedicated and specialized capabilities but becomes more attractive as fluctuating conditions call for redirection of investment and capabilities. Similar ideas have been explored in developing the contrast between ‘serial’ and ‘parallel’ experimentation (Ellerman, 2004).

In order to respond robustly to turbulence, public leaders must pursue strategic, structural, cognitive and operational flexibility. This advice does not imply that everything is up for change all the time. In fact, flexibility is often nurtured by supporting conditions that are stable. However, large bureaucratic organizations based on centralized command and compliance tend to become ossified, thus preventing flexible response. One important way to overcome this problem is to develop hybrid organizations that combine bureaucratic hierarchy with elements

of networking and market competition. Another is to ensure that those who need to flexibly adapt have the authority and resources to experiment and make exceptions.

e) *Scaling and scalability: 'Get ready to plug-and-play'*

Turbulence often presents itself as a challenge of rapidly producing certain decisions, goods, or services to meet a particular scale of demand or need. The ability of institutions and governments to scale their operations to the appropriate level is a significant challenge that builds on many of the strategies discussed here.

The concept of scaling is typically viewed as a matter of taking something—a product, an operation or a body of knowledge—that has been successfully developed on a small scale and then making adjustments to successfully produce, transfer, replicate or apply it on a larger scale. While this idea of scaling-up is important, turbulence can also produce conditions where governance must quickly scale-down. For example, a crisis management capacity organized at a national or international level often has to be quickly deployed locally. In addition, environmental governance research stresses the importance of 'cross-scale' governance, which is often facilitated by 'bridging organizations' (Cash et al., 2006). Thus, robust governance requires not only the ability to scale-up, but also the ability to flexibly adapt governance to multiple scales (Ansell and Torfing, 2015).

A key point here is that robust governance not only requires a certain scale of operations or production, but a capacity for *scaling* to meet volatile demands. Thus, robustness will depend on understanding the conditions that enable governments or organizations to easily shift scales in an adaptive fashion. For example, a study of emergency management in Denmark and Norway finds that incorporation of volunteers is critical for scaling-up response operations (Krogh and Lo, 2022). Professional emergency managers and volunteers, however, do not necessarily enjoy the interpersonal trust that can facilitate this scaling. Nevertheless, the study found that institutional trust fostered by volunteer training and certification partially substitutes for interpersonal trust, permitting the effective incorporation of volunteers into emergency operations.

The idea that organizations must be dynamically *scalable* is commonly voiced in research on incident management, workforce development and agility and some basic strategies enabling scalability, such as employee cross-training, are already commonly practiced. With their modular architectures, incident command systems are specifically designed to be scalable, quickly adding or shedding modules as necessary to respond to shifting needs. Rapid scalability in these systems is enhanced by the capacity to 'plug-and-play'—that is, the ability to easily combine and

align tasks, roles, and units so they are immediately functional (Faraj and Xiao, 2006). This process can be enhanced through both standardization and dialogue.

f) Modularity and bricolage: 'Recombine, reuse and repurpose available tools'

One of the few bright spots in the U.S. government's response to Hurricane Katrina was the U.S. Coast Guard's search and rescue missions. While confronting the same turbulent events and extreme conditions that crippled other response organizations, the Coast Guard was responsible for over half of the rescues from rooftops and flooded homes. The General Accountability Office (2006) attributed the agency's success to a powerful combination of standardization and flexibility, operational principles often seen as contradictory. By standardizing its training and technology across its different locations while giving local teams a high degree of discretion and deploying resources to where they were most needed, the Coast Guard missions rapidly accessed relevant resources and deployed response teams equipped with a repertoire of relevant tools. In essence, the Coast Guard used a modular strategy to rapidly assemble customized search and rescue missions.

A key aspect of modularity is that it allows for the flexible recombination of modular units. In developing a general systems theory approach to modularity, Schilling (2000, 315) writes that '[t]he primary action of increasing modularity is to enable heterogeneous inputs to be recombined into a variety of heterogeneous configurations.' As she points out, modularity is not always an advantage because value often arises from specialized and dedicated relationships between components, which she calls 'synergistic specificity.' The key point here is that modularity becomes more desirable as the value of recombining people and resources outweighs the advantages of specialized and dedicated connections. Increasing turbulence is likely to enhance the value of recombination, since it becomes impossible to plan for every eventuality.

Scholars have begun to argue that modularity can be an important feature of policy design (Law et al., 2012; Capano and Woo, 2018), which they think about in terms of customized 'mixes' of different policy instruments, such as regulation, funding, and voluntary standards. They have also speculated that modularity may facilitate the robustness of policy processes—that is, their ability to adaptively respond to challenging circumstances in ways that allow them to fulfill their missions (Anderies and Janssen 2013; Bednar, 2016; Capano and Woo, 2018; Ansell, Sørensen and Torfing, 2020; Sørensen and Ansell, 2021). Sørensen and Torfing (2019), for example, argue that the robust adaptability of the Copenhagen regional plan, known as the 'finger plan,' builds in part on its modularity, which has allowed different components of the regional plan to be combined in different ways in response to the dynamic and unpredictable expansion of the metropolitan area.

The concept of bricolage shares many features with modularity but tends to stress the reuse and repurposing of existing resources. Carstensen, Sørensen and Torfing (2022: 7) conceive of bricolage as drawing creatively and situationally on a 'heterogeneous repertoire of existing resources assembled over time and perhaps used in previous situations and projects, then discarded or forgotten, and ultimately rediscovered and reinvented.' They argue that bricolage can be understood as a strategy for achieving robustness and stress that public sector leaders become more robust if they can draw on the heterogeneous resources of different governance paradigms, such as Traditional Public Administration, New Public Management and New Public Governance. Bricolage that makes do with what is at hand has been found to be valuable for resource-constrained entrepreneurs facing stress and turmoil (Baker and Nelson, 2005). Howlett, Capano and Ramesh (2018) also emphasize the importance of brokerage as a mechanism for robust policies to adapt. Brokerage involves channeling improvisation according to the planned design in order to facilitate agility. As such, it comes close to the notion of bricolage.

Baker and Nelson (2005) distinguish between parallel and selective bricolage by entrepreneurial firms. Parallel bricolage develops multiple projects, ignores local institutional constraints and develops broad and diverse but amateur skill sets. They describe this strategy as producing a distinctive and robust organizational form, but one that discourages growth and isolates these organizations from richer markets (2005: 348-9). By contrast, selective bricolage is used in a more targeted and less thoroughgoing fashion. An advantage of this target-driven bricolage strategy is that firms are not 'locked into a pattern of parallel bricolage' that can be very costly (2005: 351). Selective bricolage strategies may be useful when public organizations face turbulent situations and must design robust solutions based on available ideas, tools and resources that when recombined, re-used and re-purposed may offer a tailor-made response.

g) Proactive real-time innovation: 'Be ready to improvise, probe and learn'

Responding to variable, shifting and surprising conditions often requires creativity and innovation. In a study of 'robust innovation,' Hargadon and Douglas (2001) develop an analysis of innovation that is similar in some respects to bricolage. Analyzing Thomas Edison's successful introduction of electric lighting, they find that his innovation was robust because it purposefully harnessed 'preexisting schemas and scripts' (gas lighting) to smooth the recognition and acceptance of his innovation (2001: 498). However, whereas the introduction of electric lighting unfolded over several years, turbulence typically introduces significant time pressures on would-be innovators, requiring them to innovate proactively or in real-time.

One way to talk about proactive and real-time innovation is in terms of improvisation. In their study of robust governance of the Italian COVID response, Capano and Toth (2022: 4) describe the importance of thinking outside the box, improvising and promoting fast learning. Thinking outside the box, they write, is about challenging dominant interpretations, whereas improvisation occurs where 'the rules are vague or incomplete' or where 'the official tools provided by the plans are not available' (2022: 7). Improvisation is similar to bricolage in that it also implies the ability to use repurpose and recombine available resources and tools, but it also emphasizes creativity and innovation in the moment. Both thinking outside the box and improvisation are enhanced by 'coordinated autonomy,' which grants discretion to responsible actors but also facilitates coordination among them. Another critical factor is fast learning, which allows quick assessment of whether a strategy is working. The development and experimental testing of prototypes may facilitate fast learning.

Mendonça et al. (2004) argue that facilitating improvisation requires creating 'safe environments' that do not punish experimentation and failure. Improvisation is associated with achieving creativity within and through the medium of established rules and norms, but since it takes place on the spot and without rehearsal or chance to work out the ideas in advance, it may fall short of the existing needs and expectations. Still, improvisation is necessary in turbulent situations where no script is available but there is pressure to act swiftly. To facilitate improvisation in such situations it is necessary to create an environment where failure is tolerated as long as people fail fast and without excessive costs and learn from their failure. Collective learning can be difficult even in relatively stable conditions, not to mention where individuals and organizations must grapple with time pressure, incessant change and uncertainty. Ansell and Bartenberger (2016) outline a 'probe and learn' strategy for dealing with unruly problems. Such problems are not well understood as they unfold and often exhibit interactive change (x changes y, which feeds back to change x). Probes are measured actions or investigations that seek to develop a real-time understanding of an evolving system. For example, as a public health emergency develops, there need be ways to quickly assess demands and capacities to ensure that resources are available when and where they are needed. Such probes should be rapid, exploratory, adaptive, distributed and small.

Research on fast-moving markets has suggested that innovative firms need 'dynamic capabilities'—that is, the capacity to sense, shape and act upon opportunities and threats and to enhance, protect, combine and reconfigure organizational assets (Teece, 2007). Eisenhardt and Martin (2000: 1107) describe dynamic capabilities as '...the antecedent organizational and strategic routines by which managers alter their resource base to acquire and shed resources, integrate them together, and recombine them to generate new value-creating strategies.' Dynamic capabilities can be understood as capabilities to reorganize more basic operations and broadly include capabilities for sensing, learning, integration and coordination (Pavlou and El

Sawy, 2011). The research on dynamic capabilities has primarily been focused on firms operating in turbulent or 'high velocity' market environments, but these ideas are also relevant to public governance (Piening, 2013).

Turbulence places public governance in novel situations where standard-operating procedures are of limited use and perhaps even restrictive. Instead of panicking, public leaders must rely on improvisation that seeks to innovate in real-time and on the spot. This type of creative improvisation requires acceptance of the possibility of failure, the development of dynamic capabilities to adapt structures and operations, and the ability to probe system conditions.

h) Coordination and collaboration: 'Rapidly convene actors and build trust'

Coordination and collaboration are often more essential as turbulence increases because the relevant knowledge, ideas and resources must be harnessed. At the same time, coordination and collaboration are often harder to achieve when the situation is urgent and time pressured. The crisis management literature has been interested in this challenge for quite a while because coordination failures are common during crises (Boin and Bynander, 2015). One suggestion is that crisis responders can quickly achieve coordination and collaboration by combining the complementary strengths of networks and hierarchies in hybrid structures (Moynihan, 2008; Hu et al., 2020). Information is also a key resource for generating rapid coordination and research suggests that it can be more efficiently transmitted through central network hubs (Comfort, Ko and Zagorecki, 2004; Comfort, 2007).

Emergent forms of coordination during crisis often lack the mutual trust regarded as important for collaborative governance. However, 'swift trust' can to some degree compensate for the lack of more developed forms of trust (Boin and Bynander, 2015). Research on 'the development of swift trust in temporary organizations and project teams finds that targeted selection of team members and clear role definitions enhance the development of swift trust (Kroeger, Racko and Burchell, 2021). Research on interagency coordination among Australian emergency responders has found that role clarity is an essential contributor to the development of swift trust (Curnin et al., 2015). The development of swift trust is also enabled if members recognize their interdependence and are highly engaged and committed.

Studies of medical organization that operate in highly dynamic environments also provide insights into rapid coordination and collaboration. In a study of a medical trauma center, Faraj and Xiao (2006) find that 'plug and play teaming' (modularity) that builds on recognized roles can facilitate the coordination of ad hoc response teams. As tempo and uncertainty increase, they also find that teams move to a form of 'dialogic coordination' that is less focused on rules and structures and instead characterized by relational coordination that includes on-going

contestation and negotiation, joint sensemaking, and interventions to check or prompt the behavior of others. Ongoing contestation under turbulent conditions will also place a premium on a 'robust politics' that can rapidly facilitate conflict mediation in ways that promote inclusion (Sørensen and Ansell, 2021).

While public leaders facing turbulence may initially make rapid decisions in small groups, they eventually recognize the need to rapidly convene relevant and affected actors. To do so in time pressured circumstances requires understanding the possibilities for achieving rapid mobilization and swift trust, which can be facilitated by organizational forms that combine hierarchy and networks, through targeted mobilization of actors and via clear prior specification of necessary roles.

4 Proof of concept

When new concepts are developed, it is a good idea to provide proof of concept before a prototype is developed and tested. Proof of concept is provided by demonstrating the relevance and feasibility of a new construct. In our case, there could be no better way of providing proof of concept in relation to our new idea about turbulence and robust governance than: 1) exploring the value added of our conceptual doublet 'turbulence-robustness' vis-à-vis extant studies of recent crisis that are often viewed through the lens of 'crisis-crisis management'; and 2) engaging in dialogue with practitioners who have first or second hand experience with crisis-induced turbulence to see what they think of the new concepts that we bring to the table. Let us take a brief look at our two strategies for providing proof of concept in relation to 'turbulence' and 'robustness'.

4.1 Analyzing three recent societal crises through the lens of turbulence and robustness

This section demonstrates the usefulness of the robust governance framework as compared with slightly more traditional frameworks drawn upon of leading ex-post evaluations of the 2008 financial crisis, the 2015 refugee crisis, and the recent COVID-19 pandemic. The question we pose in this section is: Are there demonstrable conceptual problems in existing frameworks and approaches to which the robust governance framework provides solutions?

We approach this question with a light touch and with a view to highlighting the contributions of our new conceptual framework. Through targeted literature searches in Google Scholar and Scopus, we identify the three most cited peer-reviewed ex-post evaluations of each of the three crises for a total of nine articles. We study these articles to identify how they conceptualize the processes of crises and public sector responses to them. For each set of three articles, we discuss the potential value that the robust governance framework could have brought to the articles in question. Finally, we draw out cross-cutting tendencies from the articles in the forms of conceptual problems that the robust governance framework seems to provide solutions for.

Importantly, this exercise is in no way a stand-in for the in-depth literature review conducted to produce this report. Instead, the idea here is to test in an illustrative manner how the robust governance framework relates to works with significant academic purchase, thereby helping to identify the "market" for the framework as well as potential selling points.

The targeted searches we performed narrow the scope of articles in third ways. Firstly, by combining keywords that target the crisis in question (e.g., "COVID-19") and the governance dimension (e.g., "governance" AND "lessons"). Secondly, we narrow the literature searched by disciplines to "social sciences", "decision sciences", and "economics". Third, we manually filter out

articles where the scope is too narrowly on one national or subnational case and without apparent general applicability. We conducted several rounds of searches to refine the keywords for each crisis.

We shall conduct the re-analysis of the three batches of top-cited articles in the following marching order: the financial crisis, the refugee crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Top-cited articles about the financial crisis:¹

- 1) Bermeo, N. & Pontusson, J. (Eds.). (2012). *Coping with Crisis: Government Reactions to the Great Recession*. Russell Sage Foundation. (91 citations)

- 2) Goodhart, C. A. (2008). The Regulatory Response to the Financial Crisis. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 4(4), 351-358. (66 citations)

- 3) Demirgüç-Kunt, A. & Servén, L (2010). Are all the Sacred Cows Dead? Implications of the Financial Crisis for Macro-and Financial Policies. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 25(1), 91-124. (35 citations)

a) Turbulence:

How close do these articles come to conceptualizing turbulence in the way we do? On the one hand, each of the articles make use of the term “turmoil” to describe the financial movements that take place during the crisis. The turmoil, however, is inside the financial movements and caused by the crisis, not the other way around. On the other hand, two of the articles (nr. 2 and 3) both point to “volatility” in asset prices and the movements of the “business cycle” as drivers of the crisis. As such, these articles conceptualize movement on either side of the onset of the crisis, but these movements are not conceptualized as being of the same nature. After the onset of the crisis, “turmoil” ensues, applying chaotic and unpredictable movements. For article, turmoil is worsened by the “speed” of decision-making. All articles share the idea that knowledge of the nature of crisis, which they see as recurring and linked to the nature of the capitalist system, and preparedness developed in times of normalcy, can help decisionmakers to weather crises prudently.

There is a vocabulary here, which could help to name the laminar flows that come before turbulence. Surely there are cyclical movements in the environments around public sector systems, knowledge of which would take some of the guesswork out of understanding some crises (like the financial crisis). The current definition (by WP2) of the link between crisis and

¹ Brief summaries of all the top-cited articles are provided in Appendix A

turbulence allows for the idea that sometimes crises are not caused by increases in turbulence. The idea that crises occur at certain points in the business cycle (when asset prices and lending increase at an increased rate) provides one example of how this may occur.

However, it seems that the articles could benefit from the concept of turbulence as an alternative cause for crises. In their current conception, the movements occurring before the crisis, which end up causing it, are in principle predictable and in any case regular. The business cycle is – although not easily predictable – a kind of law of the market, just as the volatility of asset prices is a result of (in principle) rational behavior by market actors. Despite treating a phenomenon that contains chaotic elements, the articles thus share a universe of quasi-mechanistic flows. There is no openness to the idea that other types of flows may impact on markets and cause unpredictable movements. This rules out exogeneous explanations, such as the idea that the 2007-08 Peak Oil supply crisis might in fact have impacted poor mortgage owners' economy and caused the sudden spike in defaults that triggered the financial crisis (Hamilton, 2011).

b) Robust governance:

All three articles see a deficit of policy innovation during the crisis responses, although they characterize this deficit differently. The first two articles criticize decisionmakers for not having moved far enough away from the pro-cyclical regulatory structures that helped facilitate the crisis towards a new mode of counter-cyclical regulation. The last article, on the contrary, lambasts Western governments for having failed to prepare for well-known crisis phenomena with well-designed crisis management tools. The net result is the same: decisionmakers are criticized for not moving away from the monetarist, pro-finance stance that dominated the 00s.

The articles do not explicitly make use of “resilience” as a recommendation for how to improve governance in the future, but they lean in that direction with their emphasis on improved capital requirements in the banking sector and improved risk management. However, there is an interesting twist here between what the articles recommend and how WP2 represents the resilience paradigm. The articles do seek to recreate greater stability through public governance, but not in order to “bounce back” to the state before the crisis. Rather, what they all aim to do is to bring governance of the financial sector back to a time before the deregulatory movement that they each believe caused the crisis. They see the crisis as a reason to rebalance sectoral self-governance with greater public governance, thereby achieving a healthier and more stable form of growth than the unsustainable model that dominated before the crisis (i.e., asset-price driven growth). Granted, an important element of this rebalancing is to create more resilient individual banks. But more fundamentally, it is about creating more transparency and accountability in the governance dynamics between public and private actors and to re-install counter-cyclical mechanisms in the system to avoid system-level impacts of individual risk-taking.

In this way, the high-level recommendations of the articles seem to be quite well aligned with the idea of “building back better”, i.e., robust governance.

c) Drivers of robust governance:

The three independent variables in our framework are each reflected as relevant dimensions for crisis governance in the three articles.

There are implicit and explicit calls for improvement the multi-level governance exerted through the IMF and the EU, i.e., by broadening the palette of available policy options for future crises (implicit, FIN-2-1) and for enhancing burden-sharing facilities (explicit, FIN-2-2). There is, however, no explicit focus on the interactivity in multi-level governance venues. One can imagine that the authors of especially the first article, which criticizes the dominance of a single mindset would welcome the idea that greater and broader interactivity in multi-level governance would have helped to also broaden the available policy palette.

The reform recommendations all circle around the notion that the current pro-cyclical regulatory regime should be re-balanced by hybridizing existing regulatory instruments with a counter-cyclical logic, e.g., by tying capital requirements to the rate of increase or decrease of asset prices and lending in the sector broadly (rather than to the features of individual banks). It is possible that the authors would have been helped in clarifying their overall argument by presenting it as a call for hybridizing neoliberal with Keynesian economic policy, although their choice not to do so may have been very conscious.

The articles present different accounts by which the financial crisis was a result of societal intelligence failures, namely: the dominance of anti-state sentiment among powerful elites; the failure to monitor and regulate systemic rather than individual risk; or the lack of prudent crisis planning and market monitoring among key decisionmakers. The notion of societal intelligence is almost implicit in these accounts, but the explication of combining different forms of knowledge might have helped clarify the argument.

Top-cited articles about the 2015 refugee crisis:

1) Moreno-Lax, V. (2018). The EU Humanitarian Border and the Securitization of Human Rights: The ‘Rescue-Through-Interdiction/Rescue-Without-Protection’ Paradigm. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 56(1), pp. 119–140. (87 citations)

2) Biermann, F., Guérin, N., Jagdhuber, S., Rittberger, B., & Weiss, M. (2019). Political (Non-) Reform in the Euro Crisis and the Refugee Crisis: a Liberal Intergovernmentalist Explanation. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(2), 246-266. (66 citations)

3) Morsut, C. & Kruke, B.I. (2018). Crisis Governance of the Refugee and Migrant Influx into Europe in 2015: A Tale of Disintegration. *Journal of European Integration*, 40(2), pp. 145–159. (28 citations)

a) Turbulence:

The second article and three each make use of the traditional connection between “external events” and “crisis”, the latter defined as “periods of upheaval and collective stress, disturbing everyday patterns and threatening core values and structures of a social system in unexpected, often unconceivable ways” (Rosenthal, Boin, & Comfort 2001, 6). This conception of crisis as something that suddenly erupts guides the articles to focus narrowly on the events that unfold at the point where refugee inflows, counted in real numbers, become unmanageable with existing organizational capacities and institutional structures. This focus leads to an implicit assumption that it is the suddenness itself that overpowers the system.

However, the first article, which is the most empirically grounded of the articles, instead views the sudden spike in refugee inflow in 2015 against the background of a long-term upward tendency in pressures on the EU’s outer borders and analyses and already existing failures to deal with this upward tendency in a way that conforms with the fundamental values to which the EU subscribes. This longer-term perspective is helpful in pinpointing the sources of failure during the crisis (namely, institutional drift towards an untenable rescue-through-interdiction paradigm). But as the article establishes a strict contradiction between this paradigm and the international legal obligations of the EU and its member states, the article rules out from the beginning that this framework could somehow itself be a source of adaptation and innovation of refugee policy.

The concept of turbulence and its connections with crisis as developed within WP2 would be of great value in connection the long-term and short-term perspectives on the crisis. With this concept, we can explain the pre-crisis increases in boat refugees as a steadily accelerating laminar flow of migration to the EU, flowing within a highly vulnerable institutional and organizational container. As the velocity of these flows increase, the stability of the existing system becomes increasingly precarious, and any unpredicted flows are ever more likely to produce suddenly heightened turbulence and to break the system containing those flows.

b) Robust governance:

The rescue-through-interdiction paradigm, which itself arises based on an already dysfunctional Schengen/Dublin system of border control and burden distribution, was already unable to scale to the slowly growing pressures occurring before the crisis. Little surprise that such a brittle system would breaker under suddenly increasing demands.

The question then is whether any alternative governance response could have produced better and more sustainable outcomes? The third article argues that a mixed mode of governance where member states had been able to engage autonomously in co-governance, with the Commission only imposing hierarchical governance on some aspects of the crisis management, would have been more likely to achieve buy-in to a proper burden sharing arrangement that would help save the Schengen system. However, article two argues that the interests of each member states as already expressed in the existing system, and as revealed during the crisis, rule such co-governance out. The uneven distribution of refugee inflows and costs of system failure mean that some countries have no incentives to engage in co-governance but will rationally be driven to adopt self-governance strategies.

The robust governance concept from WP2 can help to change the framing of the investigation. Given that the Schengen/Dublin-system was already dysfunctional before the crisis, what is the good reason to limit the spectrum of available solutions to once that are compatible with that system? What the second article importantly points out is that the system is in fact based on two different sets of fundamental values. On the one hand, the Schengen system allows for a Europe without borders and the freedom of movement within it. This is one set of fundamental EU values, which all member states have an active interest in realizing together. The Dublin system, on the other hand, seeks to create a solid external border around the EU while allowing for the inflow of refugees and migrants with legal claims to stay within EU countries. This inflow of migrants is highly uneven across the continent. Thus, while all member states are committed legally to the fundamental values of human rights, they do not share equally in the governance challenge to those rights. There are frontline countries where many refugees arrive, and there are preferred destination countries where many migrants end up. And then there are countries that are affected by neither. This was a well-known weakness in the Schengen/Dublin system before the crisis: the system sought to manage two governance challenges together that not all parties were equally committed to. We must therefore ask: Is it really a bad outcome that the system splits up, and that those countries most affected by migration find solutions in solidarity while other countries are left out of the equation? Perhaps this is a case where a robust solution is ultimately found by actors within the broken system despite efforts by decisionmakers to maintain it.

c) Drivers of robust governance:

Multi-level governance is a key variable here, and not simply one in which “more” multi-level governance is “better”. The third article points out that adopting a hierarchical form of multi-level governance (mode 1) did not work and argues instead for a broader base of power sharing (mode 2). But even this might not have done the trick. Because EU multi-governance in this area proved to be bound by a previously decided system that did not fit the situation. As such, multi-

level governance must also embrace innovation and adaptation strategies before it would have been able to work.

Hybridity plays an important role also, and likewise in a way where “more” hybridity is not necessarily “better”. The Schengen/Dublin system was already a hybridization of internal border freedom to realize freedom of movement and external border system to realize security and human rights. On the external border side of the equation, this hybridization had over time mutated into an unsustainable paradigm of interdiction through humanitarianism. What occurred during the crisis was thus a de-hybridization of those two governance missions and potentially a re-hybridization of the EU collaboration, i.e., a step towards an EU integrating at different speeds. Just as some member states are in the Eurozone and some are not, a picture is emerging of some members being in a shared migration zone while others are not. The compatibility with this emerging new system with Schengen is yet another question of hybridization.

Finally, societal intelligence is also key. Here, it does seem that “more” would have been “better”. Rising pressures on the border were well-known before the crisis, as were the deficiencies of the existing system. Rather than insisting on ramming through a defunct and badly designed system, EU decisionmakers could have spent time debating alternative systems and ways of working together – inside and outside the EU rules.

Top-cited articles about COVID-19:

1) Janssen, M., & van der Voort, H. (2020). Agile and Adaptive Governance in Crisis Response: Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Information Management*, 55, 102180. (151 citations)

2) Fakhruddin, B.S., Blanchard, K., & Ragupathy, D. (2020). Are We There Yet? The Transition from Response to Recovery for the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 7, 100102. (66 citations)

2) Collins, A., Florin, M.-V., & Renn, O. (2020). COVID-19 Risk Governance: Drivers, Responses and Lessons to be Learned. *Journal of Risk Research*, 23(7-8), pp. 1073–1082. (52 citations)

a) Turbulence:

All three articles revolve around the insight that while the COVID-19 pandemic crisis was exceptional in comparison with previous crisis, this kind of exceptionality is to be expected in the future. However, none of them find a unified concept for naming this “new normal”. Instead, each of them engages in some degree of conceptual stretching as they extend the need for crisis

management into the periods between crises. The second article, for example, understands pandemics that as somehow cyclical and continuous and correspondingly calls for a kind of continuous crisis management. Third article crystalizes this analysis and comes closest to an analysis like the one that underpins the concept of turbulence developed in WP2. It describes the structural drivers of the COVID-19 crisis in a way that is akin to the turbulence concept. One kind of flow – the transmission of zoonotic diseases to humans – interacts with another kind of flow – globalized air traffic – to produce a sudden pandemic spread of a new virus. The description, however, remains tied to the nexus of zoonotic diseases impacting globalization and thereby does not capture the more generalized change in global risks that the concept of turbulence seeks to capture. This means that the article – despite its important emphasis on the cross-sectoral nature of the pandemic crisis – risks being read as a “health crisis” article, which would undermine its main messages.

The more generalized concept of turbulence would help in two ways. Firstly, it helps to name the continuous nature of the threats that arise with human encroachment on animal territories, increasing interconnectedness, and global warming, without stretching the concept of crisis to fill the gaps between actual moments of crisis. Secondly, the turbulence generalization of the turbulence concept into one that challenges all sectors can help to identify a general feature of the globalized and interconnected world and thus shift the perspective from crisis management in specific sectors to a more broadly crisis-prepared form of governance in all sectors.

b) Robust governance:

There are three competing perspectives on governance at play in the articles: a Western-centric one where a general level of state capacity is assumed (article 1), a global one in which some countries suffer because their lack of such capacities (articles 2 and 3), and an international one focusing on interstate collaboration (article 3). The robust governance concept seems to offer something different to each of these perspectives.

In the Western-centric perspective, the governance challenges presented by COVID-19 were first and foremost ones of agility and adaptiveness. Some crisis phenomena call for methods that allow for small adjustment to routinized systems delivering services under swiftly changing conditions (agility) while other phenomena demand system level readjustment achieved through multi-actor dialogue, coordination, and learning (adaptivity). For both types of phenomena, swift changes come with the challenge that important societal values may be impacted negatively because of the changes. This, of course, is precisely the challenge that the robust governance concept aims to address. By combining agility through adaptation and innovation with resilience, the concept aims at a type of “dynamic conservatism” where changes are made precisely with a view to protecting underlying values.

In the global perspective, the lack of health and state capacity, which in some countries led to deficient responses, led the authors of article 2 and 3 to call for increasing capacities for crisis preparedness and crisis management. However, these recommendations fail to address the underlying causes of lacking capacities and make the risky assumption that governments in those countries will be able to marshal resources for crisis management outside of the policy window that crises uniquely provide. Here, the robust governance has the advantage of taking for granted the level of health and state capacity that exists at the moment the crisis strikes. The robust governance approach takes for granted that – even if countries do seek to build up early warning systems – some crises will eventually arrive as thieves in the night. It is these moments of governance during unforeseen moments of crisis that must be made manageable. The strategies and mindsets developed in WP2 may thus provide value above and beyond calls for greater crisis preparedness.

In the international perspective, article 3 calls for increasing preparedness, specifically around emergency mechanisms for temporary shutdowns of key nodes in the system of global interconnectedness (e.g., air traffic). Again, this assumes the ability to build up capacities and for mobilizing joint resources outside of the pressures of an ongoing crisis, just as it ignores the risk that the next crisis may come from a sector not considered. The robust governance concept, a mindset of changing existing systems to protect the values they embody, provides a way of addressing precisely those types of crises that may occur where society has not prepared for them. And there, the focus on innovation and adaptation for the protection of shared values may be central. Interconnectedness exists because it provides shared values to countries across the globe. Protecting interconnectedness by changing the way it is achieved may be a better way of framing shared challenges during a crisis than the less politically interesting concepts of crisis management.

c) Drivers of robust governance:

The first article confirms that multi-level dynamics are important for achieving agility and adaptability as well as in determining, which values should be protected through swift changes of practice.

The first and second article both confirm that hybridization of public/private service provision (article 1) and different governance frameworks (article 2) is important to allow for the changes needed to respond swiftly to crises. All three articles document extensively the need for societal intelligence through science-policy communications, sharing of data across public and private sectors, and from governments to citizens.

4.2 Lessons learned from literature studies

Looking across the re-analysis of three batches of literature, we do detect some conceptual problems and challenges for our new robust governance framework. We shall here highlight some of the key conceptual problems and the solutions that our robust governance framework may provide.

a) Problem one: Society cannot increase preparedness in all directions at once

All three crises become crisis because long-term structural trends that increasingly stress public sector systems (the business cycle, increasing migration, increased pandemic risk) are not taken up and prepared for. The traditional crisis management response is to call for increased preparedness planning and for the build-up of crisis response capacities. These calls, however, are generally tied to the specific crises under analysis and the capacities called for would be tailored to a similar crisis in the same sector. These calls, therefore, fail to address the cross-sectoral experience of increasing turbulence that stem from a multitude of structurally increasing stressors. *With limited political and economic capital to invest, surely the answer to crises becoming increasingly common cannot be to prepare for all types of crises through dedicated capacity-building?* The turbulence approach provides a way out of this dead end. It focuses not on the individual structural stressors rising, which may or may not be manageable within each sector, but rather on the compound effect, which is a generalized rise in turbulence. Because many forms of stress on societal systems are increasing at once, and because societal flows are increasingly mixed in cross-boundary and cross-sectoral patterns, the net result is an increasing likelihood of turbulent problems. This creates an important task in addition to traditional preparedness planning, namely, to prepare for turbulence arising where we least expect it.

b) Problem two: Preparing for the unforeseen takes a different mindset than planned preparedness

The robust governance approach, to be sure, does not recommend against crisis preparedness in areas with well-known risks. But it takes for granted that there will always be *some* areas of societal activity where well-known risks fall between the cracks of expert analysis and policy-making capacity, simply because no system can focus on all aspects of its environment at once. Rather than lamenting this fact, it takes up the tasks of preparing for that which *for some parts of the system* remains unforeseen – in some cases because of real epistemic lacks, in other cases because of a lack of political bandwidth. The central tenet of the approach – that robustness is achieved through adaptation and innovation – is designed to provide guidance in precisely such moments. If decisionmakers find themselves facing a moment of sudden turbulence, rather than seeking to pass the buck to someone “in charge”, lamenting the lack of planning for this particular problem, they should feel confident in engaging with the challenge by adapting already existing tools and plan or, where none exist, innovating new approaches with inspiration from entirely different sectors, countries, or time periods.

c) Problem three: Multi-level crisis preparedness assumes a collaborative spirit in times of normalcy
Several of the articles reviewed here call for the development of multi-level capacities for crisis mitigation and call for enhanced solidarity mechanisms to prevent beggar-thy-neighbor policies during future crises. These recommendations assume a more rational process of multi-level governance development than can be expected based on previous experiences. Rather, as European experiences show, multi-level governance tends to evolve by “failing forward” – a mode of policy development that the robust governance framework turns into a virtue. Without fully embracing the cynical dictum of “never letting a good crisis go to waste”, it is to be expected that some policy window is needed for multi-level governance actors to agree on new modes of collaboration and solidarity. The robust governance framework assumes that *enhancing interactivity* in multi-level governance, especially in moments of crisis, may help governance actors not only to manage crisis but to achieve necessary governance reforms.

d) Problem four: Hybridizing crisis management tools demands a state-of-exception mindset
Several of the articles reviewed call for reforms that hybridize different crisis governance tools to draw on the strength of different modes of governance, and examples of hybridization are documented for each of the three crises. The adoption and spread of hybrid forms of governance, however, may slow down once the immediate pressure of the crisis subsides. We cannot expect that expert communities around crisis management alone can drive the spread of new hybrid forms outside of the state-of-exception that occurs during moments of crisis. Developing a robustness mindset, however, may help decisionmakers to take notice of such hybridizations and to draw on such inspirations more easily in future moments of crisis, where bricolage is once again necessary.

e) Problem five: Rationalizing knowledge-sharing in “peace time” goes counter to institutional incentives

The literature reviewed here amply documents the link between the eruption of crises and failures of societal intelligence. And there are certainly “low hanging fruits” of information sharing practices and digital capacities in many countries. But again, once the immediate pressure of a crisis subsides, it may not be realistic to bank on a generalized crisis awareness driving large-scale changes to information practices and major investments in IT infrastructure (at least not in all countries and in all sectors). A robustness mindset would consist in an increased insight into the importance of different forms of interaction between experts, policymakers, and citizens as well as the agile adaption of the use of existence systems as drivers for robustness during future crises.

4.3 Interaction with practitioners

To solicit responses from practitioners in the field of crisis management, we organized two online seminars on the 17th of May, 2023. The first seminar brought together a group of Danish practitioners and took place 10-12 CET, and the second seminar assembled a group of European and global analysts and practitioners in the field of crisis management and took place 15-17 CET.

The title of the two identical seminars was: “A new framework for robust crisis governance in turbulent times”. The participants were informed that the EU-funded ROBUST project would present a new conceptual framework for understanding the conditions that makes the public sector able to respond robustly to unforeseen crises and heightened societal turbulence. The central idea would be that new turbulent problems call for robust governance that combines adaptation and innovation on the fly. The participants were invited to critically reflect on the usefulness of the new framework from their professional vantage point and give feedback to help strengthen the project’s conceptual development and empirical research. Finally, the participants were encouraged to nominate cases for further investigation and were invited to join the ROBUST Learning Hub.

The program of the seminar was:

- 15.00 Introduction – Rasmus Øjvind Nielsen, Deputy Coordinator, ROBUST. Roskilde University
- 15.10 Turbulence and Robustness – Prof. Jacob Torfing, Lead Researcher, Roskilde University
- 15.40 Conditions of robust crisis governance – Prof. Eva Sørensen, Coordinator, Roskilde University
- 16.00 Peer reflections – Does the framework help clarify your experiences during recent crises?
- 16.30 Plenary debate – Potentials and pitfalls for the ROBUST framework
- 16.55 Wrap-up and next steps.

The participants in the first Danish-language seminar were: Alexander Høgsberg Tetzlaff, Department of Political Science, Copenhagen University; Andreas Hagedorn Krogh, Center for Societal Security, The Danish Defense Academy; Kamilla Kaae Høier, The Danish Crisis Management Agency, Susanne Klint Poulsen, The Danish Crisis Management Agency; Thomas Rudbeck, Danish National Police; Mikkel Nedergaard Emergency and Risk Management, University College Copenhagen; and Svante Aasbjerg Thygesen, Management and Organization, The Danish Defense Academy.

The participants in the second English-speaking seminar were: Rasa Bortkevičiūtė, Institute of international Relations, Vilnius University; Jeong Hyup, Department of Urban Administration, University of Seoul; Fraser Quin, British Society of Lifestyle Medicine; Ronald Christiaans, Resilience Advisors Network; Corinne Hinlopen, WEMOS; Joelle Beckers, REZONWAL; Egzon Krasniqi, HVL; Feras Naser, Co-creation 17; and Natalia Oprea, Bocconi School of Management.

4.4 Practitioners' responses

Let us first consider the responses from the participants in the Danish-language seminar. Here there were a lengthy discussion of the eight robustness strategies outlined by Eva Sørensen. Some of the participants found that these strategies were more closely related to agility than to resilience. In response, it was clarified that this is because the robustness strategies focus on what must be changed to uphold core functions, goals, and values. In continuation with this, the need to put a limit to agility was discussed. One participant asked we can create safeguards against too much/too swift innovation in the face of turbulence. The Danish Mink scandal was cited as a case in point. Overnight, the government closed the whole mink breeding industry and started to kill all of the minks that were seen as a potential health threat as they could be a breeding ground for new COVID mutations. A part of this discussion focused on how to avoid both over and under-reaction to crisis-induced turbulence.

Robust governance was discussed as an instance of 'dynamic conservatism' implying that that something needs to change in order that something else to stay the same. It was pointed out that decisions about change and stability are ultimately settled locally and among citizens who discuss what to keep and what to change. This raises the question of how citizens can join the conversation about robust governance. In the ensuing discussions about "societal security", the concept of turbulence and its differentiation from crisis were deemed to be highly relevant. People use the notion of crisis for everything big and small where often they should perhaps instead talk about turbulence.

The idea about robust turbulence-based adaptation and innovation that change to preserve was also deemed relevant since we are seldom facing a crisis that can be fixed by a definitive crisis management package, but require iterative rounds of tentative solutions, learning, and revision. This insight led to a discussion of how societal learning can be integrated in the conceptual framework. How can robustness increase from one crisis to the next as a result of learning? A possible answer is that we should focus on societal intelligence and that actors should deploy a developmental evaluation perspective.

Turning next to the English-language seminar, the use of different robustness strategies had an immediate resonance with the participants. Several examples were shared in the group. One example was how scaling was achieved by letting the military to provide backup to other public service systems. Another example was how, during COVID, Seoul City adopted a very collaborative approach to managing challenges, which may be described as robust. Working with the city, college campuses agreed to provide sick beds for COVID patients. A final example was how industrial producers were convinced to retool to produce masks.

It was well taken that robust governance combines adaptation and innovation, but if rapid innovation is a prerequisite for robust crisis responses, the question becomes how one overcome implementation resistance? Perhaps a collaborative innovation strategy may help to build joint ownership to new solutions. Otherwise, one must rely on the urgency created by crisis and turbulence to remove obstacles.

Some questions related to global interconnectedness and international solidarity. During the COVID pandemic, the ability of countries to roll out vaccines was for the most part dependent on their access to health innovations created by the US pharmaceutical industry, especially for countries that do not themselves have healthy pharma industries. How do the robustness strategies mentioned help to strengthen such access or deal with the lack of access?

One participant found the boundary between the crisis and turbulence very blurry. For example, was the COVID pandemic crisis or spell of turbulence, or perhaps crisis that turned into turbulence?

The newness of robust governance was questioned. Hence, it was asked how robustness relates to the concept of “transformative resilience”. Here we need further exploration.

A related question concerned the relation between what is changed and what remains stable in robust governance. The resilience literature often asks: resilient for what? So perhaps we should also ask: robustness in relation to what?

4.5 Lessons learned from our engagement with practitioners

From the responses from the participants in the two seminars we learned that our concepts of turbulence and robustness makes good sense to practitioners, although the new concepts also raised questions and generated need for further clarification. Still, we were surprised how easily the participants caught the main argument and could ask relevant questions about definition, usage, and impact of turbulence and robustness. Most participants were able to find relevant examples of robust governance in the face of turbulence. Some participants have contacted us after the seminar asking for more information and one-on-one meetings.

The seminars have generated some new questions for us to ponder as a part of the ROBUST project. One question is how to ensure implementation of innovative solutions that break with common wisdom and established practices and thus tend to generate resistance. Another question is how in practice to determine whether an irregularity is a crisis or an instance of turbulence. Finally, we should further explore the notion of transformative resilience to see whether it approximates our notion of robustness.

5 Conclusion: summarizing key findings

After the deep socioeconomic crisis in the 1930s and the devastating Second World War that established a new world order, the Western European countries entered a long period of societal reconstruction based on social engineering of welfare state policies combining economic fine tuning with social services and benefits. Public governance was based on a predict and provide paradigm and thus used demographic analysis to ascertain the needs of the growing and increasingly affluent population and comprehensive planning and bureaucratic implementation to enhance the provision of infrastructures, public services, and social assistance. The expansion of the public sector was spearheaded by leading politicians, expert administrators, and public professionals.

In the 1970s, the economic stagflation crisis halted the long post-war period of growth and prosperity and the level of societal conflict increased. While policy makers gradually transformed the Keynesian welfare state into a neo-Schumpeterian workfare state (see Jessop, 2002), social science researchers discovered the limits of the bureaucratic planning paradigm that became apparent in the face of the pervasiveness of wicked problems (Rittel & Webber, 1973). The cognitive and political complexities could not be untangled by means of the standard linear problem-solving models. Increasingly, relevant and affected actors were invited to collaborate in defining problem and developing agreed upon governance solutions.

The last decades, researchers have talked about the growing number of complex problems but looking at the current poly-crisis that facing policymakers through Europe, it seems clear that problems are not only complex in a cognitive and political sense, but also surprising and mutable. Hence, public governors are aiming to hit a moving target. The new research on turbulence seeks to understand this new predicament in order to enable the development of a new problem-solving strategy.

There is an urgent need for developing new governance strategies in the face of societal turbulence since the rising citizen expectations to public service provision and the growing policy ambitions of public leaders have already strained the public sector. Hence, policy makers are straddling a widening gap between the effort to improve public governance and the attempt to deal with a heightened societal turbulence.

Turbulence became a scientific concept in fluid mechanics at the beginning of the 20th Century but has recently entered the vocabulary of a broad range of scientific disciplines including the social sciences.

A generic concept of turbulence covering most scientific disciplines and subdisciplines defines turbulence as a more or less enduring situation characterized by unpredictable and unsteady dynamics arising from the interaction between highly variable, inconsistent, and unexpected flows. As such, turbulence arises when separate flows that themselves change in irregular ways interact and produce a disorderly, unpredictable, and mutable dynamic.

In a social science context, we can define societal turbulence as a situation where cascading and interrelated social, natural, economic, and political events, demands and developments unexpectedly create unpredictable temporal dynamics that jeopardize the preservation of core functions, goals, and values of society and/or particular sectors of society. Hence, what the concept of turbulence adds to the notion of wicked problems is a temporal dimension of variability and unpredictability that raise the stakes for public governors who must deal with societal turmoil in a situation with short response times and a high degree of uncertainty.

While the concepts of turbulence and crisis do much of the same conceptual work by emphasizing the governance challenge of irregularity, turmoil, and disruption, the two concepts are different, although contingently related. While turbulence is often enduring, resulting from a distributed interaction of events and developments and something that organizations must learn to live with, crises are relatively short-lived, triggered by particular events, and constituting a threat to systemic reproduction. The accumulation of turbulence fueled by maladaptive responses may trigger a crisis, and an uncontained crisis that continues to spill over into new areas may spur turbulence. However, both turbulence and crisis may exist independently of one another.

There are many examples of crisis-induced turbulence. To illustrate, the COVID-19 pandemic began as a health crisis when a growing number of people were infected by a potentially lethal disease, but after the initial shock and efforts to further spread of the infectious disease, waves of turbulences began to spread through society as patients with other illness could not receive adequate treatment and lockdowns created economic, social, and personal problems for still wider segments of the population. Many similar examples can be thought of and demonstrate the need for appropriate governance responses.

Two governance strategies for responding to turbulences are in play: resilience and agility. While resilience strategies aim to overcome turbulence and restore the original equilibrium as far as possible, agility strategies seek to embrace turbulence as use the disturbance to pursue innovation and venturing into unknown territory. Thus, whereas resilience aims for stability with as little change as possible, agility strives for unfettered change. Both strategies are self-defeating as resilience is too conservative in its attempt to restore the status quo ex ante that may neither be possible nor desirable and agility is too progressive and risks throwing the baby

out with the bathing water by sacrificing functionality to restless experimentation with new innovative solutions.

Robustness provides an alternative to both resilience and agility by stressing the need to maintain some degree of stability through change. The concept of robustness has a wide application across the natural, technical, and social sciences disciplines where it is seen to enhance stability and order amidst dynamic disorder and allow processes to stay on track despite perturbations through activation of various fail-safe mechanisms. As such, robustness can be defined generically as the ability to uphold a particular function, goal, or value in a turbulent environment by means of flexible adaptation and/or proactive innovation. Based on this general definition, we have provided radial definitions of robustness great relevance to public governance. The definitions of governance robustness are presented below.

Robust governance is defined as the ability to ensure the formulation and implementation of effective and legitimate public value solutions in response to heightened turbulence through the adaptation and innovation of public policy, regulation, and service production.

Robust democracy is defined as the ability to uphold basic democratic functions and norms in turbulent times where patterns of political participation, contestation, and allegiance are shifting thus calling for adaptation of existing forms of democracy and the invention and integration of new forms of democracy, thus creating an adaptable compound or hybrid democracy.

Robust legality is defined as the construction of an adaptive combination of strict legal constrains, enablement laws, conditional exceptions and post hoc control, and accountability mechanisms that enhances the ability to maintain the rule of law in times where crisis-induced turbulence puts pressure on, or tempts, governments to act swiftly and self-willed and use drastic and coercive measures.

Our actor-centric perspective focusses on how relevant actors apply one or more robustness strategies when dealing with societal turbulence. Based on a study of relevant literature in public governance and administration, organization theory, and crisis management, we have identified eight robustness strategies, which are listed in the table below.

- a) *Redundancy, slack, and buffering: 'Keep something in your back pocket'*
- b) *Multivocality and ambidexterity: 'Keep your options open'*
- c) *Vigilance: 'Prepare to be surprised'*
- d) *Flexible adaptation: 'Stay ready to adapt'*
- e) *Scaling and scalability: 'Get ready to plug-and-play'*
- f) *Modularity and bricolage: 'Recombine, reuse, and repurpose available tools'*
- g) *Proactive real-time innovation: 'Be ready to improvise, probe and learn'*
- h) *Coordination and collaboration: 'Rapidly convene actors and build trust'*

The robustness strategies can be combined in different ways based on a situational analysis of what is required in a turbulent situation in order to uphold basic functions, goals, and values. The choice and successful application of one or more robustness strategies depends on whether public governors have a robust mindset and is conditioned by a range of institutional and societal factors that can only be transformed in the medium to long run.

It should be clear from the argument presented above that we see turbulence and robustness as intrinsically linked concepts that may help both researchers and practitioners to understand and act in a world where unpredictable dynamics have gone from an exceptional to a normal state of affairs. The concept of turbulence helps us to understand the current and highly disruptive challenges to public governance and the concept of robustness provides a response that stresses the need to adapt and innovate the modus operandi of the public sector in order to maintain some of its core public functions, goals, and values, thus embracing the idea that some forms of change are often necessary to preserve a measure of stability.

Applying the conceptual doublet of turbulence-robustness in a secondary re-analysis of the financial crisis, the refugee crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic shows that there are notable conceptual gains from adopting our robust governance framework, but also problems and challenges that call for further scrutiny.

Finally, interaction with a selected group of relevant practitioners shows that our concepts of turbulence and robust governance have an immediate resonance with the experiences of practitioners, although there is some way to go when it comes to explaining the practical implications.

References

- Achrol, R. S. (1991). Evolution of the Marketing Organization: New Forms for Turbulent Environments. *Journal of Marketing*, 55(4), 77-93.
- Aksin-Sivrikaya, S. & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2017). Where Digitalization Meets Sustainability: Opportunities and Challenges. In Osburg, T. & Lohrmann, C. (Eds.), *Sustainability in a Digital World: New Opportunities Through New Technologies* (37-49). Cham: Springer.
- Alford, J. & Head, B. W. (2017). Wicked and Less Wicked Problems: A Typology and a Contingency Framework. *Policy and Society*, 36(3), 397-413.
- Aliber, R. Z. (2011). Monetary Turbulence and the Icelandic Economy. In Aliber, R. Z. & Zoega, G. (Eds.), *Preludes to the Icelandic Financial Crisis* (302-326). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Allen, C. R., Fontaine, J. J., Pope, K. L., & Garmestani, A. S. (2011). Adaptive Management for a Turbulent Future. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(5), 1339-1345.
- Almond, G. A. & Genco, S. J. (1977). Clouds, Clocks, and the Study of Politics. *World Politics*, 29(4), 489-522.
- Anderies, J. M. & Janssen, M. A. (2013). Robustness of Social-Ecological Systems: Implications for Public Policy. *Policy Studies Journal*, 41(3), 513-536.
- Anderies, J. M., Janssen, M. A., & Ostrom, E. (2004). A Framework to Analyze the Robustness of Social-Ecological Systems from an Institutional Perspective. *Ecology and Society*, 9(1), 18.
- Janssen, M. A., Anderies, J. M., & Ostrom, E. (2007). Robustness of Social-Ecological Systems to Spatial and Temporal Variability. *Society and Natural Resources*, 20(4), 307-322.
- Ansell, C., Boin, A., & Farjoun, M. (2015). Dynamic Conservatism: How Institutions Change to Remain the Same. In Kraatz, M. S. (Ed.), *Institutions and Ideals: Philip Selznick's Legacy for Organizational Studies* (Vol. 44, 89-119). Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Ansell, C., Sørensen, E., & Torfing, J. (2021). The COVID-19 Pandemic as a Game Changer for Public Administration and Leadership? The Need for Robust Governance Responses to Turbulent Problems. *Public Management Review*, 23(7), 949-960.
- Ansell, C., Sørensen, E., & Torfing, J. (2022). Public Administration and Politics Meet Turbulence: The Search for Robust Governance Responses. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 3-22.
- Ansell, C., Sørensen, E., & Torfing, J. (2023). Public Administration and Politics Meet Turbulence: The Search for Robust Governance Responses. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 3-22.

- Ansell, C. & Trondal, J. (2017). Coping with Turbulence. In Ansell, C. K., Trondal, J. & Øgård, M. (Eds.), *Governance in Turbulent Times* (285-302). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ansell, C. & Trondal, J. (2018). Governing Turbulence: An Organizational-Institutional Agenda. *Perspectives On Public Management And Governance*, 1(1), 43-57.
- Ansell, C. K., Trondal, J. & Øgård, M. (Eds.), *Governance in Turbulent Times*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Antonakaki, D., Spiliotopoulos, D., V. Samaras, C., Pratikakis, P., Ioannidis, S., & Fragopoulou, P. (2017). Social Media Analysis During Political Turbulence. *PloS one*, 12(10), e0186836.
- Arellano, C., Bai, Y., & Kehoe, P. J. (2019). Financial Frictions and Fluctuations in Volatility. *Journal of Political Economy*, 127(5), 2049-2103.
- Arias, A., Hansen, G. D., & Ohanian, L. E. (2007). Why Have Business Cycle Fluctuations Become Less Volatile? *Economic Theory*, 32(1), 43-58.
- Arvidsson, M. & Gremyr, I. (2008). Principles of Robust Design Methodology. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, 24(1), 23-35.
- Arvidsson, N. (2014). A Study of Turbulence in the Swedish Payment System—Is There a Way Forward?. *Foresight*, 16(5), 462-482.
- Ashworth, J. & Heyndels, B. (2002). Tax Structure Turbulence in OECD Countries. *Public Choice*, 111(3/4), 347-376.
- Attar, M. & Abdul-Kareem, A. (2020). The Role of Agile Leadership in Organisational Agility. In Akkaya, B. (Ed.), *Agile Business Leadership Methods for Industry 4.0* (171-191). Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Auld, G., Bernstein, S., Cashore, B., & Levin, K. (2021). Managing Pandemics as Super Wicked Problems: Lessons from, and for, COVID-19 and the Climate Crisis. *Policy Sciences*, 54, 707-728.
- Bailly, C. & Comte-Bellot, G. (2015). *Turbulence*. Cham: Springer.
- Bankes, S. C. (2010). *Robustness, Adaptivity, and Resiliency Analysis*. Papers from the 2010 AAAI Fall Symposium Series.
- Bartlett, F. M. (2020). Turbulent Climate Discourses in Northern Sweden. *Anthropology Matters*, 20(1), 10-42.

- Beck, U. (1992). From Industrial Society to the Risk Society: Questions of Survival, Social Structure and Ecological Enlightenment. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 9(1), 97-123.
- Bednar, J. (2021). Polarization, Diversity, and Democratic Robustness. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(50), e2113843118.
- Belotserkovskii, O. M., Oparin, A. M., & Chechetkin, V. M. (2005). *Turbulence: New Approaches*. Cambridge: Cambridge International Science Publishing.
- Bennett, N. & Lemoine, G. J. (2014). What a Difference a Word Makes: Understanding Threats to Performance in a VUCA World. *Business Horizons*, 57(3), 311-317.
- Bettis, R. A. & Hitt, M. A. (1995). The New Competitive Landscape. *Strategic Management Journal*, 16(S1), 7-19.
- Bodlaj, M. & Čater, B. (2019). The Impact of Environmental Turbulence on the Perceived Importance of Innovation and Innovativeness in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(sup2), 417-435.
- Boettke, P. J. & Leeson, P. T. (2004). Liberalism, Socialism, and Robust Political Economy. *Journal of Markets and Morality*, 7(1), 99-111.
- Boettke, P. & Leeson, P. (Eds.) (2006). *The Legacy of Ludwig Von Mises*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Boin, A. & Lodge, M. (2016). Designing Resilient Institutions for Transboundary Crisis Management: A Time for Public Administration. *Public Administration*, 94(2), 289-298.
- Boin, A., Ekengren, M., & Rhinard, M. (2020). Hiding in Plain Sight: Conceptualizing the Creeping Crisis. *Risk, Hazards & Crisis in Public Policy*, 11(2), 116-138.
- Bosma, N. & Nieuwenhuijsen, H. R. (2000). *Turbulence and Productivity in the Netherlands*. Research Report 9909/E, EIM Business and Policy Research.
- Boyne, G. A. & Meier, K. J. (2009). Environmental Turbulence, Organizational Stability, and Public Service Performance. *Administration & Society*, 40(8), 799-824.
- Bozorgi-Amiri, A., Jabalameli, M. S., & Al-e-Hashem, S. M. J. M. (2013). A Multi-Objective Robust Stochastic Programming Model for Disaster Relief Logistics Under Uncertainty. *OR Spectrum*, 35, 905-933.
- Bradshaw, P. (2013). *An Introduction to Turbulence and Its Measurement: Thermodynamics and Fluid Mechanics Series*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.

- Brown, C., Haltiwanger, J., & Lane, J. (2008). *Economic Turbulence: Is a Volatile Economy Good for America?* Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Brunnée, J. & Toope, S. J. (2019). Norm Robustness and Contestation in International Law: Self-Defense Against Non-State Actors. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2985655.
- Buganza, T., Dell'Era, C., & Verganti, R. (2009). Exploring the Relationships Between Product Development and Environmental Turbulence: The Case of Mobile TLC Services. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 26(3), 308-321.
- Busumtwi-Sam, J. & Dobuzinskis, L. (Eds.) (2002). *Turbulence and New Directions in Global Political Economy*. Basingstoke: Springer.
- Cai, Q. & Liu, J. (2016). The Robustness of Ecosystems to the Species Loss of Community. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 1-8.
- Calantone, R., Garcia, R., & Dröge, C. (2003). The Effects of Environmental Turbulence on New Product Development Strategy Planning. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 20(2), 90-103.
- Capano, G. & Toth, F. (2022). Thinking Outside the Box, Improvisation, and Fast Learning: Designing Policy Robustness to Deal with What Cannot Be Foreseen. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 90-105.
- Capano, G. & Woo, J. J. (2017). Resilience and Robustness in Policy Design: A Critical Appraisal. *Policy Sciences*, 50(3), 399-426.
- Capano, G. & Woo, J. J. (2018a). Agility and Robustness as Design Criteria. In Howlett, M. & Mukherjee, I. (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook of Policy Design* (420-434). New York: Routledge.
- Capano, G. & Woo, J. J. (2018b). Designing Policy Robustness: Outputs and Processes. *Policy and Society*, 37(4), 422-440.
- Carlson, J. M. & Doyle, J. (2002). Complexity and Robustness. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 99(suppl_1), 2538-2545.
- Carstensen, M. B., Sørensen, E., & Torfing, J. (2023). Why We Need Bricoleurs to Foster Robust Governance Solutions in Turbulent Times. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 36-52.
- Carty, R. K. (2006). Political Turbulence in a Dominant Party System. *PS: Political Science & Politics*, 39(4), 825-827.

- Cashman, K. (2017). *Leadership from the Inside Out: Becoming a Leader for Life*. Oakland: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Chaisty, P. & Whitefield, S. (2017). Citizens' Attitudes Towards Institutional Change in Contexts of Political Turbulence: Support for Regional Decentralization in Ukraine. *Political Studies*, 65(4), 824-843.
- Chen, H., Zhou, R., Chen, H., & Lau, A. (2022). Static and Dynamic Resilience Assessment for Sustainable Urban Transportation Systems: A Case Study of Xi'an, China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 368, 133237.
- Churchman, C. W. (1967). Guest Editorial: Wicked Problems. *Management Science*, 14(4), B141-B142.
- Comfort, L. K., Boin, A., & Demchak, C. C. (Eds.) (2010). *Designing Resilience: Preparing for Extreme Events*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Conboy, K. (2009). Agility from First Principles: Reconstructing the Concept of Agility in Information Systems Development. *Information Systems Research*, 20(3), 329-354.
- Cowen, N. (2016). Introduction: Symposium on Robust Political Economy. *Critical Review*, 28(3-4), 420-439.
- Cretney, R. (2014). Resilience for Whom? Emerging Critical Geographies of Socio-Ecological Resilience. *Geography Compass*, 8(9), 627-640.
- Cristofoli, D., Cucciniello, M., Micacchi, M., Trivellato, B., Turrini, A., & Valotti, G. (2022). "One, None, and a Hundred Thousand" Recipes for a Robust Response to Turbulence. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 106-123.
- Dalton, R. J. & Welzel, C. (Eds.). (2014). *The Civic Culture Transformed: From Allegiant to Assertive Citizens*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Danneels, E. & Sethi, R. (2011). New Product Exploration Under Environmental Turbulence. *Organization Science*, 22(4), 1026-1039.
- Davidson, A. & Ridder, B. (2006). Turbulent Times for Urban Nature: Conserving and Re-Inventing Nature in Australian Cities. *Australian Zoologist*, 33(3), 306-314.
- Davidson, P. A. (2015). *Turbulence: An Introduction for Scientists and Engineers*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Davoudi, S., Shaw, K., Haider, L. J., Quinlan, A. E., Peterson, G. D., Wilkinson, C., ... & Davoudi, S. (2012). Resilience: A Bridging Concept or a Dead End? *Planning Theory & Practice*, 13(2), 299-333.
- Deloukas, A. & Apostolopoulou, E. (2017). Static and Dynamic Resilience of Transport Infrastructure and Demand: The Case of the Athens Metro. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 24, 459-466.
- Deng, H., Olson, M. A., Stoddart, J. F., & Yaghi, O. M. (2010). Robust Dynamics. *Nature Chemistry*, 2(6), 439-443.
- Dobbs, M., Gravey, V., & Petetin, L. (2021). Driving the European Green Deal in Turbulent Times. *Politics and Governance*, 9(3), 316-326.
- Drucker, P. F. (1993). *Managing in Turbulent Times*. London: Routledge.
- Dryzek, J. S. (1983). Don't Toss Coins in Garbage Cans: A Prologue to Policy Design. *Journal of Public Policy*, 3(4), 345-367.
- Duit, A., Galaz, V., Eckerberg, K., & Ebbesson, J. (2010). Governance, Complexity, and Resilience. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(3), 363-368.
- Durden, J. M., Murphy, K., Jaeckel, A., Van Dover, C. L., Christiansen, S., Gjerde, K., ... & Jones, D. O. (2017). A Procedural Framework for Robust Environmental Management of Deep-Sea Mining Projects Using a Conceptual Model. *Marine Policy*, 84, 193-201.
- Easton, D. (1965) *A Systems Analysis of Political Life*. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- Eckert, M. (2012). Turbulence before Marseille 1961. *Journal of Turbulence*, 13, N44.
- Emery, F. E. & Trist, E. L. (1965). The Causal Texture of Organizational Environments. *Human Relations*, 18(1), 21-32.
- Erbeyoğlu, G. & Bilge, Ü. (2020). A Robust Disaster Preparedness Model for Effective and Fair Disaster Response. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 280(2), 479-494.
- Esser, F. & Strömbäck, J. (Eds.) (2014). *Mediatization of Politics: Understanding the Transformation of Western Democracies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Falkovich, G. & Sreenivasan, K. R. (2006). Lessons from Hydrodynamic Turbulence. *Physics Today*, 59(4), 43-49.
- Fasko, D. (2001). Education and Creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, 13(3-4), 317-327.

- Fereiduni, M. & Shahanaghi, K. (2017). A Robust Optimization Model for Distribution and Evacuation in the Disaster Response Phase. *Journal of Industrial Engineering International*, 13, 117-141.
- Ferraro, F., Etzion, D., & Gehman, J. (2015). Tackling Grand Challenges Pragmatically: Robust Action Revisited. *Organization Studies*, 36(3), 363-390.
- Florice, S. & Miller, R. (2001). Strategizing for Anticipated Risks and Turbulence in Large-Scale Engineering Projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 19(8), 445-455.
- Folke, C. (2006). Resilience: The Emergence of a Perspective for Social–Ecological Systems Analyses. *Global Environmental Change*, 16(3), 253-267.
- Gaucher, E. C., Tournassat, C., Pearson, F. J., Blanc, P., Crouzet, C., Lerouge, C., & Altmann, S. (2009). A Robust Model for Pore-Water Chemistry of Clayrock. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 73(21), 6470-6487.
- Green-Pedersen, C. & Stubager, R. (2010). The Political Conditionality of Mass Media Influence: When Do Parties Follow Mass Media Attention? *British Journal of Political Science*, 40(3), 663-677.
- Griswold, C. P. (1999). Political Turbulence and Policy Research: The National Commission on Student Financial Assistance. *The Review of Higher Education*, 22(2), 143-164.
- Gruidl, J. & Hustedde, R. (2015). Towards a Robust Democracy: The Core Competencies Critical to Community Developers. *Community Development*, 46(3), 279-293.
- Haas, E. B. (1976). Turbulent Fields and the Theory of Regional Integration. *International Organization*, 30(2), 173-212.
- Hartley, K. & Howlett, M. (2021). Policy Assemblages and Policy Resilience: Lessons for Non-Design from Evolutionary Governance Theory. *Annual Review of Policy Design*, 9(1), 1-20.
- Hayward, S. (2021). *The Agile Leader: How to Create an Agile Business in the Digital Age*. Croydon: Kogan Page Publishers.
- Head, B. W. & Alford, J. (2015). Wicked Problems: Implications for Public Policy and Management. *Administration & Society*, 47(6), 711-739.
- Hermisson, J. & Wagner, G. P. (2004). The Population Genetic Theory of Hidden Variation and Genetic Robustness. *Genetics*, 168(4), 2271-2284.
- Holling, C. (1973). Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics* 4, 1–23.

- Holzer, M. & Yang, K. (2005). Administrative Discretion in a Turbulent Time: An Introduction. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 29(1/2), 128-139.
- Howlett, M. (2019). Procedural Policy Tools and the Temporal Dimensions of Policy Design: Resilience, Robustness and the Sequencing of Policy Mixes. *International Review of Public Policy*, 1(1), 27-45.
- Howlett, M. & Ramesh, M. (2022). Designing for Adaptation: Static and Dynamic Robustness in Policy-Making. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 23-35.
- Howlett, M., Capano, G., & Ramesh, M. (2018). Designing for Robustness: Surprise, Agility and Improvisation in Policy Design. *Policy and Society*, 37(4), 405-421.
- Huber, P. J. (1981). *Robust Statistics*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Huxham, C. (1996). *Creating Collaborative Advantage*. London: Sage Publications.
- Huxham, C. (2003). Theorizing Collaboration Practice. *Public Management Review*, 5(3), 401-423.
- Jen, E. (2005). *Robust Design: A Repertoire of Biological, Ecological, and Engineering Case Studies*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Jessop, B. (2002). *The Future of the Capitalist State*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Jiménez, J. (2003). Computing High-Reynolds-Number Turbulence: Will Simulations Ever Replace Experiments? *Journal of Turbulence*, 4(1), 022.
- Jiménez, J. (2020). Computers and Turbulence. *European Journal of Mechanics-B/Fluids*, 79, 1-11.
- Johnson, J. L. (2018). *The Marines, Counterinsurgency, and Strategic Culture: Lessons Learned and Lost in America's Wars*. Washington: Georgetown University Press.
- Johnston, E. W., Hicks, D., Nan, N., & Auer, J. C. (2011). Managing the Inclusion Process in Collaborative Governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 21(4), 699-721.
- Jones, B. D. & Baumgartner, F. R. (2005). *The Politics of Attention: How Government Prioritizes Problems*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kim, J., Park, K., & Ha, K. (2022). A Robust Framework on Each Disaster Management Issue: A Comparative Perspective. *International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management*, 12(4), 348-361.
- Kitano, H. (2004). Biological Robustness. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 5(11), 826-837.

- Kitano, H. (2007). Towards a Theory of Biological Robustness. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 3(1), 137.
- Klijn, E. H., Steijn, B., & Edelenbos, J. (2010). The Impact of Network Management on Outcomes in Governance Networks. *Public Administration*, 88(4), 1063-1082.
- Knobloch, L. K., Miller, L. E., & Carpenter, K. E. (2007). Using The Relational Turbulence Model to Understand Negative Emotion Within Courtship. *Personal Relationships*, 14(1), 91-112.
- Kochetkov, Y. M., Kravchik, T. N., & Podymova, O. A. (2019). Five Theorems of Turbulence and their Practical Application. *Russian Engineering Research*, 39(10), 855-861.
- Krakauer, D. C. (2006). Robustness in Biological Systems: A Provisional Taxonomy. In Deisboeck, T. S. & Kresh, J. Y. (Eds.), *Complex Systems Science in Biomedicine* (183-205). New York: Springer.
- Kurchner-Hawkins, R. & Miller, R. (2006). Organizational Politics: Building Positive Political Strategies in Turbulent Times. In Vigoda-Gadot, E. & Drory, A. (Eds.), *Handbook of Organizational Politics* (328-351). Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Lang, D. & Rumsey, C. (2018). Business Disruption is Here to Stay - What Should Leaders Do? *Quality-Access to Success*, 19(3), 35-40.
- LaPorte, T. R. (2007). Critical Infrastructure in the Face of a Predatory Future: Preparing for Untoward Surprise. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 15(1), 60-64.
- Launer, R. L. & Wilkinson, G. N. (Eds.) (2014). *Robustness in Statistics*. San Francisco: Academic Press.
- Layman, D. (2016). Robust Deliberative Democracy. *Critical Review*, 28(3-4), 494-516.
- Lazarus, R. J. (2009). Super Wicked Problems and Climate Change: Restraining the Present to Liberate the Future. *Cornell Law Review*, 94(5), 1153-1234.
- Leifer, E. M. (1991). *Actors as Observers: A Theory of Skill in Social Relationships*. New York: Garland.
- Lempert, R. J. & Schlesinger, M. E. (2000). Robust Strategies for Abating Climate Change. *Climatic Change*, 45(3-4), 387-401.
- Levin, K., Cashore, B., Bernstein, S., & Auld, G. (2012). Overcoming the Tragedy of Super Wicked Problems: Constraining Our Future Selves to Ameliorate Global Climate Change. *Policy Sciences*, 45, 123-152.

- Lewontin, R. C. & Goss, P. J. (2005). Developmental Canalization, Stochasticity. In Jen, E. (Ed.), *Robust Design: A Repertoire of Biological, Ecological, and Engineering Case Studies* (21-46). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Libby, P. A. (1996). *An Introduction to Turbulence*. London: Taylor & Francis.
- Lichtenthaler, U. (2009). Absorptive Capacity, Environmental Turbulence, and the Complementarity of Organizational Learning Processes. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(4), 822-846.
- Lieber, R. J. (2022). *Indispensable Nation: American Foreign Policy in a Turbulent World*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Light, P. C. (2005). *The Four Pillars of High Performance: How Robust Organizations Achieve Extraordinary Results: Lessons from the RAND Corporation*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Lumley, J. L. & Yaglom, A. M. (2001). A Century of Turbulence. *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion*, 66(3), 241-286.
- Luna, A. J. D. O., Kruchten, P., Pedrosa, M. L. D. E., Neto, H. R., & de Moura, H. P. (2014). State of the Art of Agile Governance: A Systematic Review. *arXiv: 1411.1922 (cs:SE)*.
- Lund, C. S. & Andersen, L. B. (2023). Professional Development Leadership in Turbulent Times: Public Administration Symposium: Robust Politics and Governance in Turbulent Times. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 124-141.
- Manrique, P. D., Huo, F., Oud, S. E., Zheng, M., Illari, L., & Johnson, N. F. (2022). Shockwaves and Turbulence Across Social Media. *arXiv: 2210.14382 (nlin.AO)*.
- Margetts, H., John, P., Hale, S., & Yasseri, T. (2015). *Political Turbulence: How Social Media Shape Collective Action*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Maronna, R. A., Martin, R. D., Yohai, V. J., & Salibián-Barrera, M. (2019). *Robust Statistics: Theory and Methods (with R)*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Mathews, J. A. (2006). *Strategizing, Disequilibrium, and Profit*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Maull, H. W. (2011). World Politics in Turbulence. *Internationale Politik und Gesellschaft Online*, 1, 11-25.
- McComb, W. D. (1990). *The Physics of Fluid Turbulence*. Oxford: Oxford Science Publications.

- McLean, J., Rosen, A., Roughan, N., & Wall, J. (2021). Legality in Times of Emergency: Assessing NZ's Response to COVID-19. *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand*, 51(sup1), S197-S213.
- Menter, F. R. (2011). *Turbulence Modeling for Engineering Flows*. ANSYS Inc (Technical Paper 25).
- Mergel, I., Ganapati, S., & Whitford, A. (2020). Making Government Agile. *American Society for Public Administration*, 3-4.
- Michaud, J. & Ovesen, J. (2013). *Turbulent Times and Enduring Peoples: Mountain Minorities in the South-East Asian Massif*. London: Routledge.
- Mingus, M. S. & Horiuchi, C. M. (2012). On Civility and Resilient Governance. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 36(1), 119-129.
- Murakami, S. (1998). Overview of Turbulence Models Applied in CWE-1997. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 74-76, 1-24.
- Nimijean, R. (2018). Introduction: Is Canada back? Brand Canada in a Turbulent World. *Canadian Foreign Policy Journal*, 24(2), 127-138.
- Nolte, I. M., Bushnell, A. M., & Mews, M. (2020). Public Administration Entering Turbulent Times: A Study of Service Quality During the Refugee Crisis. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 43(16), 1345-1356.
- Norris, F. H., Stevens, S. P., Pfefferbaum, B., Wyche, K. F., & Pfefferbaum, R. L. (2008). Community Resilience as a Metaphor, Theory, Set of Capacities, and Strategy for Disaster Readiness. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 41(1), 127-150.
- O'Malley, P. (2010). Resilient Subjects: Uncertainty, Warfare and Liberalism. *Economy & Society*, 39(4), 488-509.
- Padgett, J. F. & Ansell, C. K. (1993). Robust Action and the Rise of the Medici, 1400-1434. *American Journal of Sociology*, 98(6), 1259-1319.
- Padgett, J. F. & Powell, W. W. (2012). The Problem of Emergence. In Powell, W. W. & Padgett, J. F. (Eds.), *The Emergence of Organizations and Markets* (1-29). Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Parsons, T. (1951). Illness and the Role of the Physician: A Sociological Perspective. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 21(3), 452-460.
- Pennington, M. (2010). *Robust Political Economy: Classical Liberalism and the Future of Public Policy*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.

- Pennington, M. (2011). Robust Political Economy. *Policy: A Journal of Public Policy and Ideas*, 27(4), 8-11.
- Peters, B. G. (2017). What Is So Wicked About Wicked Problems? A Conceptual Analysis and a Research Program. *Policy and Society*, 36(3), 385-396.
- Peterson, L. L. & Davie, B. S. (2007). *Computer Networks: A Systems Approach*. Burlington: Elsevier.
- Pijpers, R. J. (2016). Mining, Expectations and Turbulent Times: Locating Accelerated Change in Rural Sierra Leone. *History and Anthropology*, 27(5), 504-520.
- Popper, K. R. (1966). *Of Clouds and Clocks: An Approach to the Problem of Rationality and the Freedom of Man*. St. Louis: Washington University.
- Radford, K. J. (1978). Decision-Making in a Turbulent Environment. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 29(7), 677-682.
- Reus-Smith, C. (2002). *Lost at Sea: Australia in the Turbulence of World Politics*. Working Paper 2002/4. Canberra: Australian National University.
- Reynolds, W. C. (2005). The Potential and Limitations of Direct and Large Eddy Simulations. In Lumley, J. L. (Ed.), *Whither Turbulence? Turbulence at the Crossroads: Proceedings of a Workshop Held at Cornell University, Ithaca, NY, March 22-24, 1989* (313-343). Berlin: Springer.
- Rittel, H. W. & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a General Theory of Planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4(2), 155-169.
- Roberts, N. (2000). Wicked Problems and Network Approaches to Resolution. *International Public Management Review*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Room, G. (2011). *Complexity, Institutions and Public Policy: Agile Decision-Making in a Turbulent World*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Rosenau, J. N. (1966). Turbulence in World Politics. *History*, 7(2), 279-292.
- Rosenau, J. N. (1995). Security in a Turbulent World. *Current History*, 94(592), 193-200.
- Rosenau, J. N. (1990). *Turbulence in World Politics: A Theory of Change and Continuity*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Rosenau, J. N. (1997a). The Person, the Household, the Community, and the Globe: Notes for a Theory of Multilateralism in a Turbulent World. In Cox, R. (Ed.), *The New Realism: Perspectives on Multilateralism and World Order* (57-80). Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

- Rosenau, J. N. (1997b). *Along the Domestic-Foreign Frontier: Exploring Governance in a Turbulent World*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Rosenau, J. N. (2018). *Turbulence in World Politics: A Theory of Change and Continuity*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Rosenthal, U., Charles, M. T., & 't Hart, P. (Eds.) (1989). *Coping with Crisis: The Management of Disasters, Riots and Terrorism*. Springfield: Charles C. Thomas.
- Rosenthal, U., Boin, A., & Comfort, L. K. (Eds.) (2001). *Managing Crises: Threats, Dilemmas, Opportunities*. Springfield: Charles C. Thomas.
- Rulinawaty, S. A., & Samboteng, L. (2020). Leading Agile Organization: Can Indonesian Bureaucracy Become Agile? *International Research Association for Talent Development and Excellence*, 12(1), 330-338.
- Sarasvathy, S., Kumar, K., York, J. G., & Bhagavatula, S. (2014). An Effectual Approach to International Entrepreneurship: Overlaps, Challenges, and Provocative Possibilities. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 38(1), 71-93.
- Schmitt, F. G. (2017). Turbulence from 1870 to 1920: The Birth of a Noun and of a Concept. *Comptes Rendus Mécanique*, 345(9), 620-626.
- Schultz, W. L., Crews, C., & Lum, R. (2012). Scenarios: A Hero's Journey Across Turbulent Systems. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 17(1), 129-140.
- Shahrokni, A. & Feldt, R. (2013). A Systematic Review of Software Robustness. *Information & Software Technology*, 55(1), 1-17.
- Shaw, K. & Maythorne, L. (2013). Managing for Local Resilience: Towards a Strategic Approach. *Public Policy and Administration*, 28(1), 43-65.
- Simmie, J. & Martin, R. (2010). The Economic Resilience of Regions: Towards an Evolutionary Approach. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 3(1), 27-43.
- Simonovic, S. P. & Arunkumar, R. (2016). Comparison of Static and Dynamic Resilience for a Multipurpose Reservoir Operation. *Water Resources Research*, 52(11), 8630-8649.
- Solomon, D. H. & Knobloch, L. K. (2004). A Model of Relational Turbulence: The Role of Intimacy, Relational Uncertainty, and Interference from Partners in Appraisals of Irritations. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 21(6), 795-816.

- Song, J. (2004). *Building Robust Chemical Reaction Mechanisms: Next Generation of Automatic Model Construction Software* (Doctoral dissertation). Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Sørensen, E. & Ansell, C. (2023). Towards a Concept of Political Robustness. *Political Studies*, 71(1), 69-88.
- Sørensen, E. & Torfing, J. (2019). Towards Robust Hybrid Democracy in Scandinavian Municipalities? *Scandinavian Political Studies*, 42(1), 25-49.
- Sreenivasan, K. R. (1999). Fluid Turbulence. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 71(2), S383-S395.
- Stelling, J., Sauer, U., Szallasi, Z., Doyle III, F. J., & Doyle, J. (2004). Robustness of Cellular Functions. *Cell*, 118(6), 675-685.
- Strecker, I. (1997). The Turbulence of Images: On Imagery, Media and Ethnographic Discourse. *Visual Anthropology*, 9(3-4), 207-227.
- Sypnowich, C. (1999). Utopia and the Rule of Law. In D. Dyzenhaus (Ed.), *Recrafting the Rule of Law: The Limits of Legal Order* (178-195). Portland: Hart Publishing.
- Taguchi, G., Chowdhury, S., & Taguchi, S. (2000). *Robust Engineering: Learn How to Boost Quality While Reducing Costs & Time to Market*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Tan, Q., Huang, G. H., & Cai, Y. P. (2013). Multi-Source Multi-Sector Sustainable Water Supply Under Multiple Uncertainties: An Inexact Fuzzy-Stochastic Quadratic Programming Approach. *Water Resources Management*, 27(2), 451-473.
- Tennekes, H., Lumley, J. L., & Lumley, J. L. (1972). *A First Course in Turbulence*. Cambridge: MIT press.
- Theiss, J. A., & Solomon, D. H. (2006). A Relational Turbulence Model of Communication about Irritations in Romantic Relationships. *Communication Research*, 33(5), 391-418.
- Theobald, S., Prenner, N., Krieg, A., & Schneider, K. (2020). Agile Leadership and Agile Management on Organizational Level-A Systematic Literature Review. In Morisio, M., Torchiano, M., & Jedlitschka, A. (Eds.), *Product-Focused Software Process Improvement, PROFES 2020* (20-36). Cham: Springer.
- Torfing, J., Peters, B. G., Pierre, J., & Sørensen, E. (2012). *Interactive Governance: Advancing the Paradigm*. Press on demand: Oxford University Press.

- Trepte, S. (2015). Social Media, Privacy, and Self-Disclosure: The Turbulence Caused by Social Media's Affordances. *Social Media & Society*, 1(1).
- Tsai, K. H. & Yang, S. Y. (2014). The Contingent Value of Firm Innovativeness for Business Performance Under Environmental Turbulence. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 10(2), 343-366.
- Turnbull, N. & Hoppe, R. (2019). Problematizing 'Wickedness': A Critique of the Wicked Problems Concept, from Philosophy to Practice. *Policy and Society*, 38(2), 315-337.
- van den Heuvel, C., Alison, L., & Power, N. (2014). Coping with Uncertainty: Police Strategies for Resilient Decision-Making and Action Implementation. *Cognition, Technology & Work*, 16(1), 25-45.
- Velasquez, G. A., Mayorga, M. E., & Özaltın, O. Y. (2020). Prepositioning Disaster Relief Supplies Using Robust Optimization. *IISE Transactions*, 52(10), 1122-1140.
- Waldo, D. (Ed.) (1971). *Public Administration in a Time of Turbulence*. Scranton: Chandler Publishing Company.
- Walker, B., Holling, C. S., Carpenter, S. R., & Kinzig, A. (2004). Resilience, Adaptability and Transformability in Social-Ecological Systems. *Ecology and Society*, 9(2), 5.
- Walker, B. H., Anderies, J. M., Kinzig, A. P. & Ryan, P. (2006). Exploring Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems through Comparative Studies and Theory Development: Introduction to the Special Issue. *Ecology & Society*, 11(1), 12.
- Webb, C. T. & Levin, S. A. (2005). Cross-System Perspectives on the Ecology. In Jen, E. (Ed.), *Robust Design: A Repertoire of Biological, Ecological, and Engineering Case Studies* (151-172). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Weber, E. P., & Khademian, A. M. (2008). Wicked Problems, Knowledge Challenges, and Collaborative Capacity Builders in Network Settings. *Public Administration Review*, 68(2), 334-349.
- Wikan, U. (1990). *Managing Turbulent Hearts: A Balinese Formula for Living*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Wilden, R. & Gudergan, S. P. (2015). The Impact of Dynamic Capabilities on Operational Marketing and Technological Capabilities: Investigating the Role of Environmental Turbulence. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(2), 181-199.

Willinger, W. & Doyle, J. (2005). Design and Evolution. In Jen, E. (Ed.), *Robust Design: A Repertoire of Biological, Ecological, and Engineering Case Studies* (231-272). New York: Oxford University Press.

Windle, G. (2011). What is Resilience? A Review and Concept Analysis. *Reviews in Clinical Gerontology, 21*(2), 152-169.

Wyngaard, J. C. (2010). *Turbulence in the Atmosphere*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Zang, H., Li, H., Zhang, W., Fu, Y., Chen, S., Xu, H., & Li, R. (2021). Robust and Ultralow-Energy-Threshold Ignition of a Lean Mixture by an Ultrashort-Pulsed Laser in the Filamentation Regime. *Light: Science & Applications, 10*(1), 49.

Zhong, W., Hu, Q., & Kapucu, N. (2023). Robust Crisis Communication in Turbulent Times: Conceptualization and Empirical Evidence from the United States. *Public Administration, 101*(1), 158-181.

Zuber-Skerritt, O. (Ed.) (2012). *Action Research for Sustainable Development in a Turbulent World*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing.

Appendix A: Summary of article for re-analysis

Financial crisis:

- 1) Bermeo, N. & Pontusson, J. (Eds.). (2012). *Coping with Crisis: Government Reactions to the Great Recession*. Russell Sage Foundation.

91 citations²

The first article is the introduction to an edited volume that conducts comparative political economy studies of policy responses to the financial crisis in the advanced economies of the world. The individual chapters of the volume mix analysis of economic policy instruments and governance mechanism. The introduction outlines the shared features of the contributions to the comparative studies in the book, which do not follow a shared analytical framework but nevertheless identify some common tendencies in government responses to the financial crisis.

The introduction highlights how government responses diverge from assumptions in the critical junctures approach. Critical junctures literature typically posit crisis as stemming from the international system but responses as stemming from power struggles within countries, which in turn depends to some degree on the ideational resources available to actors. Responses to the financial crisis diverge from this pattern in two ways.

Firstly, there are countries in which decisions in the international system trump national power struggles during the financial crisis. This goes especially for the Southern European countries (Greece, Italy, and to some degree Spain) whose national politics were overridden by the EU and the IMF. Here, shared policy instruments, such as the Euro area rules limiting public sector debt, end up determining national policy. This is not, however, only a consequence of rules being enforced automatically. Rather, participants in high-level governance forums such as the Euro-group meetings actively worked *not* to activate exceptions to the rules of the common currency, thereby delaying any form of solidarity solution to the problem of overleveraged national economies in Southern Europe. As a rule of thumb, the greater the degree of pre-crisis state liquidity (i.e., positive trade balances, financial headroom), the more policy autonomy during the crisis – and vice versa.

² Note that SCOPUS citation numbers are quite conservative and thus significantly lower than, e.g., Google Scholar. Although we use the SCOPUS numbers here, the relative ranking of the articles has been confirmed by searching in both of these databases.

Secondly, in those countries who did have autonomy due to their fiscal positions going into the crisis – countries where one would expect alternative coalitions to mobilize to make use of the window of opportunity presented by the crisis – saw no such push for alternatives to the existing economic policy regime. Rather, crisis responses in the wealthy countries generally followed the pattern of using narrowly targeted fiscal stimulus to double down on already well-established national growth strategies. So, in the US and the UK where growth policy had centered on the financial sector growth prior to the crisis targeted fiscal stimulus to the financial sector. Similarly, Germany and France and other countries with export-oriented growth models stimulated their manufacturing sectors. There was thus very little policy innovation during the financial crisis and rather a deepening of existing policy patterns. For example, the crisis *could* have been a moment for social solidarity, targeting some state spending towards social safety nets for the poor and unemployed. But across the advanced economies, even in the Nordic countries, policymakers sought instead to balance fiscal stimulus packages with social cuts and a tightening of workfare regimes. In terms of governance, already dominant actors thus seem to have reaffirmed their hold on the national policy consensus and national-level economic decision-making.

The lack of policy and institutional innovation also applies to the international system. Coming on the background of the long-term entrenchment of structural trade imbalances between countries with export-oriented and finance-oriented growth models, which had been supported by growing financial interdependency arising out of financial deregulation in the finance-driven countries, the crisis *could* have been the moment for returning to greater international regulation of capital flows as well as the reactivation of policies for trade balancing (currency devaluation, protectionism). Instead, the winners in the existing system used their influence over the institutions of the international system, such as the IMF, to muscle through an insistence on the existing growth models and international rules. In the EU, the crisis *could* have been a moment for strengthening fiscal policy integration within the Union. But member states, being more afraid of the potential individual costs that such integration would produce than they were interested in the collective gains for the group of member states, countered any such impulse.

The introduction emphasizes the spill-over costs of this rigidity in crisis management, which is a shared concern among authors in the edited volume. This rigidity seems to have dampened the positive effects of countercyclical fiscal stimulus and to have forced especially poorer countries to adopt austerity measures. It also seems in the process to have significantly impacted trust in international integration and sowed disenchantment with democracy itself. The introduction concludes, counter to the expectations of critical juncture theory, that a in international elite coalition promoting market solutions and resisting state activism successfully seized the moment of the crisis to strengthen business as usual, thereby hindering or delaying economic policy reforms.

- 2) Goodhart, C. A. (2008). The Regulatory Response to the Financial Crisis. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 4(4), 351-358.

66 citations

The second article is an essay that discusses regulatory responses to bank failure during the financial crisis and reform efforts aimed at ensuring better crisis management in the future. The essay focuses mainly on potential changes to the tools available to regulators and less on the governance process itself, although the recommendations made for institutional changes have significant governance implications (such as a redrawing of the lines between sectoral self-governance and democratic oversight). The essay's focus is on the rules and institutions of the banking sector, especially in the UK but also internationally. The main aim of the essay is to identify institutional changes that can better handle endogenous systemic risk, i.e., risk that arises out of the interactions of banks with other banks and with their customers.

The author criticizes some of the central post-crisis institutional changes already going on at the time, among them higher bank liquidity demands (CARs) and more market-sensitive asset pricing ("mark-to-market") to name two. The author claims that these tools will enhance rather than counteract procyclical systemic tendencies in the banking sector. Even as these changes serve to make individual banks more risk aware, they do little to incentivize countercyclical behavior. During economic upturns when asset prices rise, mark-to-market pricing will lead banks to follow the herd, while in a downturn such pricing will worsen the financial profile of the bank vis-à-vis credit rating agencies and auditors and enhance the risk of default. Higher capital requirements for their part may help avert bank runs but will otherwise do little to shape the behavior of banks.

The central argument in the essay is that in trying to make individual banks less prone to failure, these regulatory changes fail to target properties of the banking sector and financial system as a whole. While granting that the changes imposed may well help to make individual banks more risk aware and lead to more solid banks in a narrow sense, individual bank fragility was not really the cause of the financial crisis and so, the solution is directed at the wrong problem. The real root of the financial crisis, according to the author, lies in bank interdependency by which "the action of each individual bank impinges on all other banks". Regulatory responses should thus aim to contain systemic risk, not individual bank risk.

The author proposes a few regulatory changes to help counteract systemic risk. Firstly, CARs should be tied to the economic cycle so that capital requirements increase in the upturn (counteracting overheating in the economy) and decrease in the downturn (injecting liquidity into the economy when it is lacking). Second, efforts should be made to redraw the lines

between the inside and outside of the banking system, cleaning up bank practices of compartmentalizing risky assets and commitments through the use of subsidiaries and exotic contractual constructs. Third, at the level of national policy, policymakers should have ultimate veto power over decisions whether or not to bail out banks. This is to avoid situations like the failure of Northern Rock Bank in the UK, where the technical evaluation of the Treasury correctly identified the bank as insolvent but missed the bank's systemic importance, leading to a no-bailout decision by Treasury that in turn triggered the UK portion of the financial crisis. Fourth, countries should use international organizations such as the EU and the IMF to create and ex ante burden sharing facility in the case of multinational bank failures. If implemented, these proposals would together install breaks, buffers, and escape hatches (my metaphors) in the financial system that would bring down systemic risk and help the decisionmakers deal effectively with the turmoil of crisis.

- 3) Demirgüç-Kunt, A. & Servén, L. (2010). Are All the Sacred Cows Dead? Implications of the Financial Crisis for Macro-and Financial Policies. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 25(1), 91-124.

35 citations

Written during the onset of the crisis, this third article seeks to present lessons for decisionmakers in developing countries on how to react to the crisis responses of Western governments. Since so many long-standing best practices ("holy cows") of banking regulation seemed in the aftermath of the crisis to be rejected and reversed by Western governments, should governments in the Global South follow suit? The authors' conclusion is no.

To educate the reader, the authors draw two distinctions about crisis management. First, a distinction between short-term responses in the crisis containment stage and long-term readjustments during the crisis resolution stage. The authors warn against seeing the anomalous policies adopted in the containment stage as signs of any permanent paradigm shift. Rather, exceptional times call for exceptional measures, and in the long term, banking regulation is likely to return to normal. Second, a distinction between prudent crisis management plans and systems put in place during non-crisis periods of stability, and the rushed decision-making that takes place during a crisis when decisionmakers, who are not supported by good crisis preparedness, face challenges for which they themselves are unprepared and for which they consequently think there "is no playbook". The authors' overall argument is that despite the objective magnitude of the 2008 financial crisis, the only reason that policymakers react as if the crisis was a true black swan event is that they are uneducated in the history of financial crisis and thus overreact, give into pressures from threatened constituencies, and copy the mistakes of

others. The authors' overall advice is not to join in this panicked decision-making. This argument is played out in relation to a series of illustrative policies.

First, bank bailouts and guarantees meant that by the end of 2008, Western governments stood to be the largest stakeholders in their respective financial sectors. Does this mean the end of private banking? No, this is a temporary measure, well-known from other crises, and will be/should be followed by re-privatization of banks.

Second, blanket guarantees seem to signal that banks have become "too big to fail", leading to a *de facto* nationalization of the risk, even if the profits may return to private hands. Again, the authors argue against allowing this to happen. Their advice is that governments should take the time to assess the solvency of individual banks through some transparent test, e.g., whether or not a bank is able to raise half or more of its liquidity needs in private markets. If not, governments should not extend guarantees to the bank beyond insurances to small bank customers. In other words, insolvent banks should be allowed to fail. Even for those banks that do meet this criterion, strict rules should prevent the payout of dividends and bonuses before the government is paid out.

Third, bank failures called into question the strength of the existing regulatory framework (Basel II) in which capital requirements were decided on the basis of external ratings. The authors criticize this arrangement, because it ties capital requirements to *predictable* levels of default in certain asset classes (i.e., mortgages) and does nothing to shield banks against *unpredictable* risk. Does this mean that ratings agencies should be abandoned? Not necessarily, but the authors recommend that capital requirements should be decoupled from ratings agencies' assessments and tied instead to the *volatility* of banks' earnings – a measure that must come from elsewhere. A step on the way is "official" (i.e., state) oversight from bodies that must help not only to monitor development in volatile asset classes, but also to generate the very information that such independent monitoring should be based on. This solution would combine bank supervision with market oversight in one and the same public body. But the authors believe that revisions to the regulation of each step on the way towards the generation of such oversight – from private actors' disclosure to public bodies' assessments – must be revised. Not only must markets and market actors be forced into greater transparency about their risk-taking, but public actors should also be more easily held to account for their enforcement (or non-enforcement) of rules and regulations.

Fourth, monetary policy seems to have played a role in creating the crisis and some argue for changes. Monetary policy in the US during the 2000s thus aimed only at controlling inflation and ensuring job market participation, leaving "hidden" inflation in asset prices (such as housing) off its radar. Some suggest that monetary policy should react if asset prices deviate from their

fundamentals and thus “prick” bubbles before they grow too large to handle. Like Goodhart (FIN-2-2), the authors reject this notion and argue instead that a range of banking regulation instruments already existing (provisions, leverage ratios, loan-to-value ratios, and more) should be adjusted to become counter-cyclical, i.e., so that capital requirements rise when asset prices and lending increases rapidly.

Finally, capital controls come back in vogue when financial crisis spreads through global interconnectedness. Is this a good idea for developing countries, as a way of insulating themselves from the crisis in the West? The *pro* argument is that developing countries are impacted doubly by the financial crisis. First by the real slowdown of the global economy, second by financial currents causing increasing global borrowing rates, worsening currency exchange rates, and capital flight to safety. In this context, some advocate capital controls to impose temporary stability in national economies. The article reviews extensive evidence from the use of controls on both outflows and inflows of capital and concludes that, while temporary emergency controls remain a simple tool in any governments’ toolkit, no clear case can be made for long-term imposition of a new protectionist regime.

Refugee crisis:

- 1) Moreno-Lax, V. (2018): The EU Humanitarian Border and the Securitization of Human Rights: The ‘Rescue-Through-Interdiction/Rescue-Without-Protection’ Paradigm. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 56(1), pp. 119–140.

87 citations.

The first article investigates the discursive, legal, and organizational drivers behind the 2015 refugee crisis, where the EU notoriously failed to reach a joint solution to the sudden influx of more than a million refugees, mainly from Syria, Libya, and Afghanistan.

The article focuses especially on the handling of boat refugees coming across the Mediterranean identifies what the author names a “rescue-through-interdiction” paradigm, i.e., a practice whereby boat refugees in danger are rescued and then returned immediately to their place of origin (in direct violation of UN conventions). This paradigm has developed gradually through a series of legal and organizational “innovations”, each of which have been motivated by increasing numbers of boat migrants beginning already a decade earlier.

What the EU and Member States did *not* do was to build up organizational capacity for receiving these migrants safely, processing their asylum claims in accordance with international conventions on the human rights of refugees and migrants, and distributing lawfully entitled

arrivals across the European member states. Instead, the situation of refugees and migrants taking the perilous journey across the Mediterranean was increasingly viewed as a rescue situation, and the focus of policy increasingly became one of building capacity for saving lives. At the same time, increasingly muscular efforts were made to police human trafficking, first through joint policy missions, later through NATO collaborations.

These efforts were legitimized through laws and discourse casting the situation as one of humanitarian aid to people in dire straits. However, this legitimating narrative at the same time served to take focus away from the conventional human rights of the people in question, leaving refugees and migrants as legally lesser individuals than “real” refugees and migrants. Furthermore, with other efforts blocking ordinary access to the EU from outside – such as the EU-Turkey agreement to hold back migrants in Turkey – the EU was in fact pushing migrants towards cross-Mediterranean channels of access. This self-contradictory effect was made invisible through the humanitarian focus on refugees in distress.

The article does not unfold the consequences but leaves a clear picture to the reader. With this paradigm being in place when the 2015 crisis struck, none of the tools that would have been needed to deal with the crisis in a manner compatible with human rights commitments were in place. Instead, Member States without direct exposure to previous streams of refugees had become accustomed to ignoring the problem and its consequences for frontline countries and when the crisis struck, most countries doubled down on this individualized approach, leaving the frontline countries to deal with the problem.

- 2) Biermann, F., Guérin, N., Jagdhuber, S., Rittberger, B., & Weiss, M. (2019). Political (Non-) Reform in the Euro Crisis and the Refugee Crisis: A Liberal Intergovernmentalist Explanation. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(2), 246-266.

66 Citations

The second article analyzes the non-adoption of the reforms that would have helped EU members to deal with the 2015 crisis collective from the game theoretical perspective of Liberal Internationalism (LI). According to this framework as applied here, the “integration preferences” (i.e., preferences concerning joint EU policy) of EU member states along with the bargaining power of different member states (i.e., the cost of each member state of not reaching a joint solution based on their position in the crisis) can together explain the non-adoption of reforms. To prove this hypothesis, the authors map each of these and analyze their interactions.

The integration preferences of Member States, according to the authors, are already partially expressed in the rules of the Schengen rules. Here, the Dublin system, which governs how to

handle refugees and migrants arriving at the EU's external borders, dictates that the country in which people first arrive must both receive them safely and process their asylum claims. Only after the legality of their claims are determined can people move on to their ultimate destination country. Due to the uneven distribution of migrant flows, these nominally equal distributions of responsibility burden frontline countries more than other member states, which was well known at the time of the establishment of Schengen.

The question that was not clear before the crisis was whether the countries benefitting from this uneven distribution preferred the maintenance of this *de facto* inequality more or less than the openness of Schengen. Their bargaining power during the crisis depended on the answer. If open borders were valuable enough to countries with low migrant inflows were valuable enough, they would be compelled to reach a collective solution to the problems presented by the 2015 crisis. What happened instead was that their actions - including reinstalling border controls in contravention of Schengen - revealed the opposite preference. Rather than share in the burden of managing an explosive influx of migrants, countries chose to let the Schengen collaboration collapse. Frontline countries followed suit and allowed migrants to move through their territories to other member states without being legally processed – a “defect/defect” scenario in game theoretical terms. The authors analyze the sequence of events as a “suasion game”, i.e., a game in which the costs of defecting from the status quo are so much smaller than the costs of engaging in further integration that the frontline countries have no leverage in bargaining for collective action. Because there is no “common bad” that all parties are equally interested in avoiding, the breakdown of Schengen that occurred during the crisis was all but inevitable.

- 3) Morsut, C. & Kruke, B. I. (2018): Crisis Governance of the Refugee and Migrant Influx into Europe in 2015: A Tale of Disintegration. *Journal of European Integration*, 40(2), pp. 145–159.

28 citations

The third article analyzes the governance actions taken by the European Commission in attempting to reach a common solution. The aim is to understand whether the Commission used appropriate governance tools and, if not, what tools might have helped member states reach a joint solution.

The article makes use of a distinction proposed by Koimann (2000) between three modes of governance in which actors give up increasing degrees of autonomy: self-governance (full autonomy), co-governance (collective autonomy), and hierarchical governance (subjection to top-down government). The authors maintain that all three modes of governance are at play in the relationship between EU institutions and the member states.

When crises occur, especially crisis of large scale and of a transboundary nature, different modes of governance may be deployed for different purposes. Crisis self-governance may be appropriate for small-scale and localized events. Large events that cross borders may demand either co-governance or hierarchical governance or both. Utilizing these broader modes of governance make it possible to create a “holistic, cooperative and coordinated” response from all parts of the crisis governance system, e.g., the EU system. However, there is no guarantee that such coordination will occur because actors involved may opt for independence and go it alone.

During the crisis, the European Commission launched a series of proposals for collective action to address the apparent deficiencies in the existing immigration policy system (the Dublin regulation). The European Council, in which the Member States act in co-governance mode, agreed to these proposals with some changes. However, as migrant numbers continued to increase, individual member states began taking unilateral action to solve only those parts of the crisis that affected them directly, thereby undermining solidarity. In response, the European Commission attempted a switch to hierarchical crisis governance, invoking articles in the treaties governing the EU that would make emergency allocation of migrants to member states mandatory. These emergency measures were agreed by a qualified majority in the Council but again, individual member states took further action to reject migrants coming their way, with fences and border controls being built in many states. Meanwhile, implementation of the decision to relocate migrants across compliant member states came to a crawl.

Had the European Commission invoked a 2001 Council Directive on temporary burden sharing of migrants, a different mechanism could have been triggered that would have allowed the blending of hierarchical and co-governance modes with greater autonomy given to member states. The article argues that this or another mode of mixed governance would have been necessary to solve the crisis: some degree of autonomy maintained among member states, and some degree of hierarchical decision-making power bestowed on the European Commission. The article ultimately recommends that member states engage in such co-governance going forward to avoid the ungovernability of migration in the EU area.

The COVID-19 Pandemic:

- 1) Janssen, M. & van der Voort, H. (2020): Agile and Adaptive Governance in Crisis Response: Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Information Management*, 55, 102180

151 citations

The first article juxtaposes agile governance and adaptive governance in order to explore the explanatory power of each concept relevant to the COVID-19 crisis responses of governments, exemplified by the Dutch government. Since the COVID-19 pandemic demanded great flexibility of governance responses across sectors, and since both agility and adaptiveness are ways of conceptualizing flexibility, the interest of the article is in understanding how the two concepts diverge and overlap and what the interactions between the two may be.

Agile governance stems from software development. It seeks to continually improve the functionality of products and services by replacing master plans and long-term development processes with short iterations of development and deployment. Translated to public sector services, the idea is to enable frontline systems and workers to send feedback to public managers continually so that they may make ongoing adjustments and redesigns of the way that services are provided. In the context of COVID-19, the authors consider different public service delivery challenges, such as the delivery of health statistics to the public, the development of apps to support contact tracing, and the rearrangement of supply chains to ensure stable PPP supplies as challenges that would have required agility. Looking at evidence from the Netherlands, the performance of that country is mixed and there are some non-obvious findings. For example, the national statistics bureaucracy, which promoters of agile governance might have expected to act inefficiently, proved highly capable of adjusting their data gathering practices to support pandemic decision making with data of an acceptable (although not perfect) level of quality. In comparison, private software developers, which promoters of agility would expect to excel in such a fluid environment, took part in a one-week "app-athon" to compete for the best national COVID-19 tracking app. They all failed to build into their apps the kind of personal data protection that would be required for national deployment of such apps, partly an oversight of their own, partly a matter of under-specification by the government agency running the competition.

Adaptive governance by contrast stems from sustainable systems management. It seeks to achieve society-wide adaption to environmental conditions by developing capacities for adaptation, circumventing hierarchical decision-making whenever they prove too rigid to respond to warning signals. In the context of public sector governance, the idea is to have platforms and interfaces that enable cross-sectoral and multi-level decision-making in direct response to early warnings and other signals. The authors analyze several capacities activated or invented during COVID-19 as adaptivity capacities, including the activation of a national cross-sectoral management protocol, the establishment of a multi-institutional Outbreak Management Team, and the development of a COVID-19 Dashboard gathering multi-source data and information for decisionmakers to monitor trends in the pandemic. In general, the authors find

capacities for adaptiveness in the Netherlands lacking, and they recommend the maintenance and further development of such cross-cutting capacities in non-crisis times.

The authors find that agility and adaptiveness may counteract each other, given that one is a method for adjusting already running products and services while the other is a higher-level change capacity that may demand larger-scale changes of what products and services are delivered and how. To outline a joint conceptual framework, the authors draw on the distinction between single-loop and double-loop learning – the former being what agile governance excels in providing, the latter being what adaptivity demands. Both may be necessary in a crisis, and neither can be activated without proper capacity development beforehand.

- 2) Fakhrudin, B.S., Blanchard, K., & Ragupathy, D. (2020) Are We There Yet? The Transition from Response to Recovery for the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 7, 100102

66 citations

The second article presents reflections on how pandemic recovery differs from “ordinary” disaster recovery and develops policy recommendations to take these differences into account. In contrast to natural disasters such as earthquakes or hurricanes where the disaster happens in a limited space of time, after which the tasks of managers is to “bounce back” through recovery, pandemics unfold in a much longer timeframe during which the biological threat itself mutates. This means that recovery by necessity takes place even as the pandemic is still unfolding. As a consequence, constantly changing needs arise and plans and tools must be utilized flexibly, revised, or even invented anew.

These differences have great significance for the usefulness of established frameworks for disaster risk management, such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Reduction, which are largely based on traditional phases of disaster management. These frameworks do not consider the *cascading impact* of biological hazards and what they mean for handling risk at a systemic level. Instead, a new mode of thinking about pandemic preparedness is emerging in new frameworks, such as the Global Risk Assessment Framework, which aims at establishing “an integrated cycle of preparation, response and recovery”.

The central problem that emerging frameworks are trying to solve is that a number of governments around the world “failed to act on their warnings about the pandemic”, despite having a number of previous experiences from which to draw lessons (avian flu, MERS, and more). Indeed, while some countries managed to create *highly effective* responses (the authors mention Singapore, Germany, and New Zealand) other created *devastating* government

responses (e.g., Iran, Italy, South Korea, and the United States). Singapore learned from the SARS epidemic that bureaucracy could in itself worsen the effects of epidemics. The country therefore created a *well-coordinated, multi-stakeholder* response and recovery. New Zealand adopted *early and strong* actions (effective tracing, isolation protocols, and a shutdown of foreign inflows), which succeeded in limiting infection rates.

Based on studies of government responses, the article establishes a typology of *effective vs. ineffective* government responses. Effective responses include transparent governance, collaborative structures, effective information sharing, and more, while ineffective responses include top-down government, bureaucratic structures, slow and limited information sharing, and more. The same studies lead to a series of policy recommendations, among them a mindset of “when” rather than “if”, an integrated, interdisciplinary, and multi-sectoral approach to pandemic preparedness, strengthened international collaboration, the creation of socially accepted channels for data sharing, and an outlook that sees oncoming climate change as a driver of pandemics and other large-scale events.

- 3) Collins, A., Florin, M.-V., & Renn, O. (2020). COVID-19 Risk Governance: Drivers, Responses and Lessons to be Learned. *Journal of Risk Research*, 23(7-8), pp. 1073–1082

52 citations

The third article seeks to identify drivers of the pandemic crisis and based on this understanding, identify policy recommendations to avoid future pandemics turning into crises of the same magnitude. The basic contention of the article is that, despite myriad pronouncements to the contrary, the pandemic was *neither* unpredictable *nor* unforeseen. Based on previous outbreaks of novel viruses (SARS, MERS, etc.), experts had long been warning about the increased risk of zoonotic transmissions in places where human development encroaches on animal habitats as well as the systemic risks of global transmission that arise from increasing economic interconnectedness across the globe. The magnitude of the COVID-19 crisis is a consequence of the lack of responsiveness to these warnings, and better pandemic governance in the future will demand improvements in global risk governance.

More specifically, the article identifies several systemic drivers for the crisis. Most basically, the pace of viral transmission across countries was enabled the *lack of swift mitigation measures* (e.g., shutdown of air traffic) within a system of *increasing global interconnectedness*. These systemic risk factors are exasperated by *lacking health sector and state capacities* produced by a focus on lean service delivery and a general trend towards minimization public sector costs. To top it off, the swiftness of virus transmission led to the (necessary) adoption of emergency measures

(lockdowns etc.), which in turn created *cascading effects* turning the health crisis into an economic crisis impacting *socio-economic fragilities* left over from the 2008 financial crisis.

Analyzing government responses in terms of technical assessment, risk perception, evaluation of options, risk management, and communication, the article produces several policy recommendations aiming to counteract similar drivers being activated in the future. Most fundamentally, the article recommends dealing with *act on the warnings of experts* and to deal with new viruses, especially zoonotic diseases, *at the source*. However, recognizing the inevitability of future pandemics despite attempts at avoiding them, the central concern of the article is that public sector capacities to respond to novel health threats must be increased, not only in the health sector but in the state as a whole. This could involve interstate agreements for swift mitigation measures aimed at key nodes in the global system, such as plans for the emergency shutdown of air traffic. Importantly, strengthening the *science-policy nexus* and *technologies for crisis communication*, such as apps, should be prioritized alongside methods and mindsets for improved *risk communication* should also be prioritized. Meanwhile, learning from the positives that came out of the *societal disruptions* of COVID-19 is important in order that the recovery phase should not necessarily lead societies back to the status quo ante, but should rather integrated those elements of the pandemic mitigation that actually improved quality of life.